

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

1 - Contour cropping

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The practice of tilling sloped land along lines of consistent elevation in order to conserve rainwater and to reduce soil losses from surface erosion.

(Source of definition: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/contour-farming>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

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CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

1 – Contour cropping

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The rainfall and runoff factor higher than 10-15% limit the application of this practice.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	No
gently sloping (2-5%)	No
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

In principle, it can be said that the most important factor is the texture, the composition of the soil in sand, silt and clay, in fact the erodibility increases with the increase of the content of fine sand and silt.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	No
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	No
Large-scale corporate farming	No

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	No Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	No Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	No Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

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Comments or references for limiting soil factors

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Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

The greatest obstacle to the conservation of this hillside settlements is their inability to adapt to agricultural mechanization based on large tractors and large combine harvesters. Actually it is applied only in a few areas in Central Italy, featuring the agricultural landscape, as we know it and which has great historical and cultural value. (Emilio Sereni, Storia del paesaggio agrario, 1961)

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

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PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Circling the hill
 - 2 Straddling the hill
 - 3
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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

2 - Controlled traffic farming

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) enables controlled traffic farming (CTF) systems, where machinery drives along repeatable tracks with accuracy.

(Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The advent of high-precision positioning and auto-guiding systems has enabled the development of controlled traffic agriculture (CTF), which is a strategy for the circulation of agricultural equipment that confines all vehicles to the smallest possible area in permanent traffic lanes. CTF makes it possible to limit the surface of compacted soil during the circulation of vehicles in the field. A reduction in soil compaction could make cultivation processes significantly more efficient, more reliable and more productive, and improve soil functions such as infiltration and water retention (Holpp et al., 2013).

CTF has been used since the mid-1990s on a large scale in cereal crops in Australia (Holpp et al., 2013). Even if studies concerning the environmental impacts of the CTF exist, it is still little implemented in Europe (Gasso et al., 2013; Anken et al., 2016; Etana et al., 2020).

A study conducted in Switzerland showed that cropping system yields became more stable during periods of drought and heavy rainfall (Holpp et al., 2013; Latsch and Anken, 2019). The introduction of CTF influenced the soil physical parameters penetration resistance, macropore

volume, O₂-concentration of soil air and matric potential in a positive way (Anken et al., 2016).

In Denmark, Gasso et al. (2014) presented the significant potential for CTF to reduce environmental impacts through reduced greenhouse gas emissions in intensively managed arable cropping systems (in the range of 20-45% for N₂O and 370-2100% for methane (CH₄) with at least 20% reduction in direct emissions from field operations).

More recently, Hussein et al. (2021) reported a 30% increase in sorghum yield with CTF.

A 2018 survey of farmers in eight European countries (Belgium, United Kingdom, Netherlands, Ireland, Denmark, Germany, Sweden and France) identified the main factors limiting the CTF adoption (Tamirat et al., 2022). They appear to be lack of compatibility of machines and global navigation satellite systems (GNSS) from different manufacturers; high cost (equipment, access to the Real Time Kinetic GPS signal, modification of machines); lack of demonstrated benefits under local conditions; incomplete knowledge of research results and decision support tools; and a perception that CTF is not for small farms (Tamirat et al., 2022).

The technical and organisational effort to realise permanent traffic lanes for heavy standard machines is not to be underestimated (Latsch and Anken, 2019). CTF implementation may not be straightforward. For example, the cutting width of combines rarely matches the width of the drill. An alternative to CTF is the ‘‘CTF-light’’ where only the heaviest vehicles travel on permanent traffic lanes (Latsch and Anken, 2020).

In Australia, a calculator that helps farmers in their decision to adopt CTF is available.

The points of vigilance to be taken into account when considering the adoption of the CTF are the following:

- the equipment used since all the machines do not have the same dimensional characteristics or the same tires and that all the cultivation operations do not have the same working width,
- the type of soil because the gains depend on the sensitivity to soil compaction,
- the slope, as there may be an increased risk of erosion in the event of bare ground in sloping traffic areas,
- weeds whose control in traffic areas is more difficult,
- a risk of loss of driving skills for farmers,
- greater dependence on satellites.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

2 – Controlled traffic farming

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The practice of CTF has no identified limiting climatic factor. On the other hand, it can be less interesting in the event of climatic conditions which do not favor soil compaction.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Uncertain
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : The more the soil is sensitive to compaction, the more CTF is relevant.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

There is no soil for which CTF is not recommended. On the other hand, it is less interesting in case of soil that is not sensitive to compaction.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	No

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

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Comments or references for limiting soil factors

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Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

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Comments or references linked to soil challenges

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PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

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bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

3 - Cover crop termination with no herbicides and ploughing

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The shallow incorporation of plant residues or cover crops with a rotor, a cultivator or a skim plough. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The shallow incorporation of plant residues or cover crops with a rotor, a cultivator or a shallow plough.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

3 – Cover crop termination with no herbicides and ploughing

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

It must be possible to grow cover crops (e.g. suitable length of the growing season)

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

In clayey soils the use of PTO-driven units (e.g. tillers) or multiple runs of a cultivator can be advisable.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

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Comments or references for limiting soil factors

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Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

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Comments or references linked to soil challenges

The impact of herbicide-free reduced tillage in organic farming is the subject of many studies and reviews, such as Cooper et al. (2016) or Krauss et al. (2020). However, such studies often compare systems and not the effects of certain practices such as cover cropping. Additionally, some studies on cover crops focus on yield effect (e.g. Wittwer et al. 2017 and 2020) or do not consider the combination of cover crops with tillage practices (e.g. Adetunji et al., 2021). The impact statements above are to our best knowledge and judgment.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

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bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

4 - Deep Ploughing

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Deep plowing is a plowing to a depth greater than 50 cm as compared to ordinary plowing which rarely exceeds 20 cm. (Source of definition: Baumhardt et al., 2008, doi: 10.2136/sssaj2007.0122)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Deep plowing is a plowing to a depth greater than 50 cm as compared to ordinary plowing which rarely exceeds 30 cm (Schneider et al., 2019).

According to Schneider et al. (2017): Single or unfrequent ploughing treatment reaching deeper than conventional ploughing (= depth of Ap horizon) with the goal of long-term soil melioration. Deep ploughing turns soil horizons and results in complete or semicomplete inversion of the soil profile, with subsoil horizons ending up at the soil surface and topsoil horizons buried in the deep soil.

According to DIN 1185 (1973): Deep ploughing (meliorative ploughing) refers to ploughing soil to least 60 cm depth with a single-furrow plough specially designed for this purpose.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

4 – Deep Ploughing

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

No, they do not limit the application.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment : Historically, in Germany and the Netherlands, large areas of excavated peatlands were deep-ploughed in order to mix the remaining low quality peat with underlying pleistocene sands to enable farming. However, converting peatland to mineral soils is not line line anymore with today's environmental standards.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Soil water content has an effect on it (Schneider et al., 2017). Other soil properties that can influence this practice are:

- Soil depth should be larger than deep tillage depth
- Rock fragments < 20 vol-%
- Clay < 20 %
- Silt < 70%
- No drainage pipes that could be damaged by deep ploughing
- In heavy soils, no groundwater (Gr-horizon)
- Only in mineral soils

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	No

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Adverse Effect

Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Beneficial Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Unknown Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Adverse Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

As stated by Schneider et al. (2017), When deep ploughing, heavy soil should neither be too dry (pulling resistance) nor too wet (smearing effects instead of loosening).

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

For Germany, a detailed analysis on the potential area of application has been carried out by Florian (2020)

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Deep ploughing is a high risk intervention. Maintain/increase SOC is well documented in Alcántara et al. (2016). Avoiding N₂O, CH₄ emissions from soils: Potentially adverse effect. But understudied. Avoid acidification: In theory, it can be beneficial if only the topsoil suffers from acidification while the subsoil still harbours pedogenic calcareous materials. Research

trials have been made on this. But little success and definitely not the primary goal of deep tillage. Avoid soil erosion: short term: higher soil erosion (until vegetation cover establishes again), long term: less soil erosion through increased infiltration capacities. Avoid soil sealing: several studies have shown to loosen the soil and increase infiltration rates... especially in saline-sodic soils under irrigation. Avoid salinisation: several studies have shown to loosen the soil and increase infiltration rates... especially in saline-sodic soils under irrigation. Optimal soil structure: If conducted wrong (e.g. deep tillage in soil with > 70 % silt or high water content) it can go horribly wrong. Under optimal conditions beneficial. Enhance soil biodiversity: Understudied. But the few studies available point towards adverse effects. Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency: Understudied. Not primary goal of deep tillage. Enhance water storage capacity: Potentially yes, by loosening compacted soil but not primary goal of deep tillage.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

1	deep tillage
2	meliorative ploughing
3	
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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

5 - Dyker

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A dyker is a tool that can be attached to the rear end of a potato planting machine. The dyker digs holes into the bottom of the furrows between the potato ridges to facilitate water infiltration. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The dyker is a tool that can be attached to the rear end of a potato planting machine. It consists of a set of wheels with diggers facing radially outward or a comparable construction. The dyker is intended to dig holes into the bottom of the furrows between the potato ridges to facilitate water infiltration. Therefore, it should minimize surface runoff and soil erosion (Lemann et al., 2019).

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

5 – Dyker

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The climatic factors do not influence the adoption of this practice

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The other soil properties do not influence the adoption of this practice

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	No Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	No Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Unknown Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

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Comments or references for limiting soil factors

None known

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Can be applied where potatoes (or other crops) are grown on ridges.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

The study of Lemann et al. (2019) in Switzerland showed, that the dyker changed the soil surface structure in the furrows of potato fields and increased the infiltration in the topsoil and below. A study by Olivier et al. (2014) showed that surface runoff was reduced by the dyker. These findings indicate, that the dyker can reduce soil erosion and prevent waterlogging. Combined, these effects may increase the nutrient use efficiency and the water storage in the soil. However, we found no published evidence on these effects.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Terraprotect
 - 2 Cross dam heap
 - 3 Hole star
 - 4
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bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

6 - Lightweight autonomous field robot

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The lightweight autonomous field robots are agricultural vehicles capable of doing field operations by working in fleets within a field. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The lightweight autonomous field robots are agricultural vehicles capable of doing field operations by working in fleets within a field.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

6 – Lightweight autonomous field robot

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	
strongly sloping (10-15%)	
moderately steep (15-30%)	
steep (30-60%)	
very steep (>60%)	

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	
Avoid salinisation	
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	
Avoid Peat degradation	

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

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Comments or references for limiting soil factors

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Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

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Comments or references linked to soil challenges

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PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

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bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

7 - Low pressure in tyres

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Low-pressure tyres distribute the weight to the ground over a larger contact patch so that the weight of the tractor or trailer is spread out better.

(Source of definition: <https://blog.bridgestone-agriculture.eu/7-advantages-of-low-pressure-tyres-compared-to-normal-tyres>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

/

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

7 – Low pressure in tires

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)

gently sloping (2-5%)

sloping (5-10%)

strongly sloping (10-15%)

moderately steep (15-30%)

steep (30-60%)

very steep (>60%)

Management of organic soils/peatlands

-- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land

2.1.2 permanently irrigated land

2.1.3 rice fields

2.2.1 vineyards

2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations

2.2.3 olive groves

2.3 Pastures

2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)

3.2.1 Natural grasslands

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming
Extensive farming in less favoured areas
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming
Large-scale corporate farming

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming
Conservation Agriculture
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)
Terrace Farming

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC
Avoiding N₂O, CH₄ emissions from soils
Avoid acidification
Avoid soil erosion
Avoid soil sealing
Avoid salinisation
Avoid contamination
Optimal soil structure
Enhance soil biodiversity
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency
Enhance water storage capacity
Avoid Peat degradation

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

8 - No-till / direct seeding

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The practice of drill-seeding with no prior tillage of soil. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Additional description was made by coordinators of the two involved countries. In detail, no-till is the practice of drill-seeding with no prior tillage of soil. In the last years in Spain conservation practices such as no-till have been implanted and extended. These practices present environmental advantages such as reduced erosion, fuel savings and increased organic matter in the soil compared to traditional tillage practices. This has led to a decrease in the net emission of greenhouse gases (CO₂). No tillage and/or direct seeding is one of these practices. No till is mainly applied in woody crops, it implies plantations that do not receive mechanical tillage, no vegetation cover is maintained at any time and problems of compaction can exist. Direct seeding is defined as the establishment of an annual crop in a field that does not receive any work from the harvest of the crop to the sowing of the next; in which an attempt has been made to maintain the soil covered by the homogeneous distribution of the vegetal remains from the previous crop; with which the excessive compaction due to the passage of machinery and livestock; and having previously controlled herbs at sowing, by applying reduced doses of low-hazard herbicides. The seeders have to be accompanied by stubble separating cutting discs.

No till represents in Spain the 9.08% while the minimum tillage has been the main soil maintenance technique used in Spain in 2020, representing 43.03% of the total area (5,294,596 ha). Next, and at a great distance, is that of spontaneous vegetation cover with 1,176,922 ha (22.23%) and traditional tillage that accounts for 14.92% of the total area. From 2010 to 2020, no tillage has increased by 8.42%. In the last ten years, the use of ground covers has been the technique with the greatest increase, both in net value (181,515 ha) and in percentage (15.98%). By autonomous communities Andalusia (Mediterranean south area) concentrates more than 59.62% of the national total of no-tillage area (woody crops). Within this community, of 286,575 hectares cultivated under this technique, 83.45% of the surface (239,140 ha) correspond to the cultivation of olive groves. With no tillage, the olive grove and citrus fruits stand out. However, in other fruit trees (41.86%), vineyards (64.90%) and olive groves (40.28%), minimum tillage is the most common practice (ESYRCE, 2020).

The direct seeding covers an area of 768,173 ha compared with traditional sowing, which covers an area of 6,280,889 ha (88.9% of the reference area). Cereals and other forages are the groups where a higher percentage of direct seeding is observed in addition to corn and sunflower. In the last ten years the percentage of direct seeding has increased by more than six percentage points, it has almost doubled its surface since the year 2010 in the reference crops. Traditional sowing is declining in favor of direct seeding. In Castilla y León, direct seeding is located in 36.61% of the cultivated area under this system in Spain (768173 ha), mainly due to the cereal-based agriculture in this region. They are followed in importance by Aragon (18.11%), Andalusia (13.59%) and Catalonia (9.32%). In the rest of the communities as a whole, the area cultivated under the technique represents 22.37%. Castilla - La Mancha, despite being the second community with the largest surface area of the study species (1,483,757 - 21.00%), is the fifth in the implementation of direct seeding. In the Region of Murcia, most of the area of grain cereals, sunflower, corn and other forages are cultivated under the direct seeding system (39.12% of its cultivated area). It is followed in order of importance in the application of this technique by the Canary Islands (38.56%), the Valencian Community (25.93%), Navarra (20.63%), Catalonia (19.38%) and Asturias (19.62%). In the rest of the Autonomous Regions, direct seeding does not exceed 17% of the reference crop area in each of them (ESYRCE, 2020).

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

8 – No till

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

In Mediterranean basin, no-till yields are usually same or exceed those after ploughing, whereas in Boreal zone, no-till yields rarely exceed those after plowing. In Boreal, the yield has been 65-100% of the conventional tilled (Soane et al. 2014). In extreme aridity northern Spain the barley yields may be up to twice those with conventional tillage (Fernández-Ugalde et al. 2009). No-till is ideal in Mediterranean zone, where it decreases erosion and surface runoff and increases the yields. In Boreal zone, the practice is more suitable to decrease fuel costs and labour demand as well as to decrease loss of particle P to watercourses. In Alpine South zone, high precipitation rate (900-1800 mm) with relatively warm climate (11 Celsius degrees) may enable intense growth of thermophile weeds in no-tilled fields during summer increasing the use of herbicides. Some fungal disease and pests may also cause problems. In detail, Mediterranean Nord Area. Cereal Cultivation (mainly Castilla y Leon área in Spain). Total Precipitation: areas up to 400 mm or (L/m²) (See map area) (AEMET and ITACYL). Temperature (mean year): between 11-12°C (See map area) (AEMET and ITACYL). Start of growing period: From 15-31 January until 18-29 February (See map area) (AEMET and ITACYL). Solar radiation 4.45-6.45 GJ m³.year (See map area) (AEMET and ITACYL). Length of summer drought.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : P9 - LUKE (Finland) clarified that no-till is suitable for organic soils/peatlands because reducing or eliminating tillage reduces peat decomposition.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Some light soils may enable weed (e.g. couch grass) invasion causing problems if the soil is not plowed.

The roots of trees and shrubs on the surface of the earth may cause problems.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Uncertain
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

I1 - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	
Avoid acidification	Adverse Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Adverse Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

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Comments or references for limiting soil factors

In Boreal, clay soils are less suitable for direct drilling of barley in spring. The spring crop yields were 60-80% of those after ploughing (Känkänen et al. 2011). The worst situation is in the fields with barley monoculture.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

If the purchase of a no-till drill is too expensive for small farms, the use of a contractor or purchase of a no-till drill together could be considered.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Increased soil organic carbon in surface layers of no-till soils may not be associated with increased carbon sequestration through the profile (Soane et al. 2014). No-till may maintain the soil SOC but its increase seems non-existent when the no-till yields are often worse than conventional ones in Boreal conditions. There may, however, be in the soil layers below 10 cm unutilized potential for carbon sequestration (Honkanen et al. 2021). While in Mediterranean conditions, no-till may enhance SOC accumulation at a rate of 1% of annual increase, yielding average C sequestration rates of 0.44 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ (Aguilera et al., 2013) compared to conventional tillage management.

More research is needed on the effects of no-till on N₂O and CH₄ emissions. In short term no-till may enhance direct N₂O emissions especially in poorly drained soils (Sanz-Cobena et al. 2017). No-till reduces erosion and nutrient losses into the aquatic environment but the loss of dissolved reactive P loss is increased.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Zero tillage
 - 2 Direct drilling
 - 3 Sod seeding
 - 4 Direct seeding
 - 5 Zero till
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

9 - On-Land ploughing

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The tractor for ploughing runs on covered soil, as opposed to in-furrow ploughing.

(Source of definition: WOCAT)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The main difference between on-land ploughing and conventional ploughing is that all the tractor wheels -- even the wheels on the furrow side - are running on the unploughed soil surface. Compared to the conventional in-furrow design, on-land ploughs have reinforced frame elements, additional hydraulic equipment and a continuously adjustable parallelogram for setting the plough in on-land position; however, on-land ploughs can also be used for in-furrow ploughing, if necessary. Due to the modified design, on-land ploughs may be slightly heavier than comparable in-furrow models. On-land ploughing gives best results when plough and tractor are professionally adjusted. Because the steering support by the furrow is missing in on-land mode, on-land ploughing benefits from tractors equipped with a steering aid that automatically keeps the tractor on course when driving outside the furrow.

The main advantage of on-land ploughing is that mechanical soil stresses are removed from the subsoil and put on the soil surface, where they can be reduced by improved tyre equipment (wide or twin tyres) and better compensated by a higher soil strength (dry, well rooted soil).

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

9 – On-Land ploughing

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Climatic factors do not influence the adoption of this practice

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The other soil properties do not influence the adoption of this practice

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Unknown Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

In general, everywhere where in-furrow ploughing is applied, on-land ploughing can be applied. Exceptions are steep slopes or soils with a thick, wet, and slippery mulch layer.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

On-land ploughing was found to be beneficial for the soil structure and lead to enhanced soil hydraulic properties. The subsoil stresses and vertical soil displacement are reduced in on-land ploughing compared to in-furrow ploughing (Weisskopf et al., 2000; Keller et al., 2002). The reduced stresses can lead to a reduced formation of plough pans, increased saturated conductivity at a lower degree of preferential flow, as well as increased aeration of the subsoil (Weisskopf et al, 2000; Munkholm et al, 2005a). A study by Bakket et al. (2009) found that if conventional tillage was performed by light machinery (<5 t) in relatively dry conditions (at or below field capacity) and with low tyre inflation pressures (at or below 80 kPa) its effects on the sub soil are comparable to the effects of on-land ploughing.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

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bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

10 - Reduced tillage / Conservation tillage

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Reduced or conservation tillage is a practice that leaves crop residues on the surface. It is a practice to reduce the effects of tillage on soils, however, it still depends on tillage as the structure forming element in the soil. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The global description of Conservation Tillage provided by the coordinators was 'Conservation tillage is a practice that leaves crop residues on the surface which increases water infiltration and reduces erosion. It is a practice to reduce the effects of tillage on soil erosion, however, it still depends on tillage as the structure forming element in the soil'.

Eurostat refers to conservational tillage as 'a tillage practice or system of practices that leaves plant residues (at least 30 %) on the soil surface for erosion control and moisture conservation, normally by not inverting the soil'. According to Eurostat conservation tillage can include the following systems: 1) strip tillage or zonal tillage; 2) tined tillage or vertical tillage; 3) ridge tillage with the objective to conserve moisture or drain excess moisture.

Reubens et al. (2012) and Bijttebier et al. (2018) point out that it is not possible to give an unambiguous definition for the term conservation tillage. It is a collective name for a wide range of practices, which are interpreted in a variety of ways and which can have very different effects

on a system. A simple classification is hence inadequate, and it is important to include several factors when trying to define a practice. Examples of such factors are: the working depth, the intensity of the operation and the condition of the soil (including its history) (Reubens et al., 2012).

When defining conservation tillage the following aspects should be considered in order to not exclude any forms of conservation tillage:

1. In most cases of conservation tillage practices, the main distinction with conventional tillage is that the soil is not inverted by a plough, hence the term 'non-inversion tillage'. Certain non-inversion tillage practices only impact the topsoil, whereas other conservation tillage practices impact the deeper soil layers (Reubens et al., 2012; Van den Putte, 2011). One could argue that also inversion tillage practices with a very shallow working depth should also be considered as conservation tillage. For example, an operation with the eco-plow is less than 10 cm deep and only impacts the soil layers near the surface.
2. Eurostat states that conservation tillage should lead to a soil cover with plant residues of 30%. However, it is not always possible to leave this amount of crop residues at the surface, and instead of crop residues also organic manure can be left on the soil surface in conservation tillage systems (Willekens et al., 2014).
3. The global definition initially provided by the coordinators and Eurostat only mentions beneficial effects on soil moisture/infiltration and erosion and state that the aim for conservation tillage is erosion control. However, conservation tillage is also applied in areas where soil erosion is not a major issue and aside of reducing soil erosion, conserving soil moisture and increasing water infiltration, other beneficial effects are also to be expected such as increased aggregate stability in the top soil and a stimulation of earthworms (Catch-C project KnowSoil and Fact-Sheet) because the tunnels of earthworms are less damaged and deeper earthworms are stimulated by the crops that are lying on the surface (D'Hose et al., 2014; KnowSoil (catch-c.eu)).

Therefore we propose the following definition:

'Conservation tillage is a practice that concentrates crop residues and organic manures in the top layer, by not inverting the soil or with an inversion operation at very shallow depth. Tillage remains important for soil structure forming. It is often applied for moisture conservation and erosion control purposes, but also leads to other beneficial effects such as higher earthworm abundance and larger aggregate stability of the top layer'.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

10 – Conservation tillage

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

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Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : We suspect that conservation tillage is possible on organic soils, because it is mentioned in several publications.

Ploughing has been recorded to have adverse effects on the carbon storage in peatlands through an increased peat oxidation (Geurts and Fritz, 2018). In an ongoing experiment in the Netherlands, the use of conservation tillage practices are being compared to conventional tillage practices on peatlands cultivated with maize (Veenweide Fryslan, 2019). Among other benefits it is assumed that the application of conservation tillage techniques will lead to less peat oxidation and that it will be better for the conservation of soil carbon in peatlands. The results of this research are not available yet.

Gambolati et al. (2005) observed that agricultural practices in the southernmost part of the Venice Lagoon catchment promote the bio-oxidation of the Histosols. Histosols represent a large proportion of the outcropping soils in the area. Seasonal ploughing contributes to the exposure of new organic material to the atmosphere and consequently promotes its bio-oxidation. It was observed that the bio-oxidation reaction is fastest during hot and dry summers, when the soil moisture content is relatively low and the soil temperature is relatively high (Gambolati et al., 2005). Conservation tillage was suggested to be a more adequate agricultural practice since it decreases the exposure of unmineralized peat to the atmosphere.

References:

Gambolati, G., Putti, M., Teatini, P., Camporese, M., Ferraris, S., Stori, G. G., ... & Tosi, L. (2005). Peat land oxidation enhances subsidence in the Venice watershed. *Eos, Transactions American Geophysical Union*, 86(23), 217-220.

Geurts, J. J. M., & Fritz, C. (2018). Paludiculture pilots and experiments with focus on cattail and reed in the Netherlands-Technical report-CINDERELLA project FACCE-JPI ERA-NET Plus on Climate Smart Agriculture.

Veenweide Fryslan. (2019). Teelt van mais op veen duurzamer. Geraadpleegd op 30 juli 2021: Teelt van mais op veen duurzamer | Veenweide (veenweidefryslan.fr).

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

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Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming
 Extensive farming in less favoured areas
 Medium intensives, mixed farming systems
 Intensive, larger-scale crop farming
 Large-scale corporate farming

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	No
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

Van Kessel et al. (2013) compared the impact of no-tillage (NT)/ reduced tillage (RT) practices and conventional tillage (CONT) practices on N₂O emissions in humid and in dry climates.

The dataset used for the meta-analysis consisted of 239 direct comparisons between NT/RT systems and CONT systems spread over the world.

It was observed that on average there is no change in the N₂O emission when making the conversion from CONT to NT/RT. On the long-term (> 10 years of implementation) there is a significant reduction in N₂O emission in NT/RT systems relative to CONT. When separating the data by climate category (dry or humid) the reduction was only significant in dry climates (a reduction of 34% relative to CONT) (Van Kessel et al., 2013).

Short term NT/RT operations increased the N₂O emissions by 38 % relative to CONT (Van Kessel et al., 2013). If N fertilizer was applied in NT/ RT systems at a sufficient depth (> 5 cm), a reduction of 27% in N₂O emissions was observed in humid climates. Van Kessel et al. (2013) observed a yield decline when applying NT/RT of 5% relative to CONT, and this was significantly greater in dry climates (11%) than in humid climates (3%). In humid climates the decline was only significant on the long-term (6%), whereas in dry climates the decline was only significant on the short-term (12%) (Van Kessel et al., 2013).

Bijttebier et al. (2018) studied barriers and drivers for the implementation of non-inversion tillage as perceived by farmers in Europe. The study was spread over 8 farm type zones (FTZ) across 4 countries (Belgium, the Netherlands, Germany and Italy). In 2 of the 8 zones the barriers for implementation of non-inversion tillage included a climatic factor. In one zone in Belgium farmers mentioned that the soils dry more slowly in spring and in one zone in Germany farmers perceived it as a barrier that the soils warm up more slowly in spring under non-inversion tillage (Bijttebier et al., 2018).

Non-inversion tillage should be conducted under sufficient dry conditions because under wet conditions reduced tillage techniques are less able to loosen the soil compared to conventional tillage techniques (Vermang, 2012). It was observed that harvest and subsequent tillage under wet conditions lead to compaction of the soil (0-30 cm layer), a frequent problem of the agricultural soils in Belgium. As a consequence, in wet years, Vermang (2012) observed a higher run-off rate and a higher rate of soil erosion in fields that were managed with reduced tillage practices compared to fields that were managed with conventional tillage practices.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

Barriers for the adoption of conservation tillage are depending on local situations including climate, soil and farming systems. Therefore, the exact execution of the practice is depending on the local context and conclusions or good practices from one region cannot be transferred automatically to another region.

Bijttebier et al. (2018) observed a high variability in the adoption rate of non-inversion tillage (NIT) across 8 studied farm type zones (FTZ) in Europe, varying between 19 % and 80 %.

General concerns of farmers across were: more weeds, weeds in seedbed preparation, increased herbicide use and more difficult elimination of weeds. In all zones, except for the zones located in Italy, more crop diseases, pests and a higher herbicide use were also mentioned as negative outcomes of NIT. The following factors have been mentioned as barriers in one or more of the FTZ studied by Bijttebier et al. (2018): clay soils, labour peaks during soil preparation for maize, no financial advantage, no appropriate machinery, good results with ploughing, incorporation of (winter-hardy) cover crops, rye grass before maize, not enough technical knowledge, not frequently applied by farmers and no/little experience. Certain farmers that had started applying non-inversion tillage techniques returned to ploughing due to unforeseen constraints (Bijttebier et al., 2018).

In Flanders non-inversion tillage is mostly conducted to ploughing depth or even deeper, because soil is often compacted due to heavy slurry tanks and late harvest under wet conditions. . Deeper tillage is then needed to lift this compaction and to avoid problems with crop growth and soil erosion (Vermang 2012). Therefore, results from international literature on reduced or even no-till cannot always be translated to the Flemish farming context (Ruysschaert et al., 2021).

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

In general, the soil moisture content is higher in soils where non-inversion tillage practices are applied compared to conventional tillage (Abdalla et al, 2013; Ruysschaert et al., 2021; Van den Putte et al., 2012). During the growing season Reubens et al. (2012) recorded higher soil moisture contents in the topsoil (0-10 cm) in non-inversion systems compared to conventional systems. In ploughing systems, a higher moisture content has been observed in the soil layer between 20 and 30 cm, which increases the risk of compaction (Reubens et al., 2012). Superficial conservation tillage techniques have also been observed to lead to compaction (Reubens et al., 2012). Deep conservation tillage avoids soil compaction compared to superficial conservation tillage and in some cases even protects the subsoil from further compaction (Van den Putte et al., 2012).

Van den Putte et al. (2012) investigated the impact of superficial conservation tillage (SCT, 0.15 -- 0.20 m depth) and deep conservation tillage (DCT, 0.30-0.40 m depth) on soil characteristics and crop yield on agricultural silt loam soils in Belgium. It was observed that the application of conservation tillage techniques slight increases the water retained in the soil compared to mouldboard ploughing (MP) . A higher volumetric water content was recorded in the topsoil under MP, especially after heavy rainfall (Van den Putte, 2011). The moisture content was

significantly higher in the subsoil under SCT compared to MP and DCT during the whole growing season. Overall, the difference in moisture content between MP and DCT was small, but DCT might offer an advantage over MP during dry summers due to the slightly higher moisture content in the subsoil (> 30 cm) (Van den Putte, 2011).

Consequences of a higher soil moisture content are, however, that the soil dries and warms up more slowly in the spring. These consequences have been recorded to be barriers of the application of non-inversion tillage techniques by farmers in Europe (Belgium and Germany) (Bijttebier et al., 2018).

In addition, reduced tillage techniques have been recorded to adversely affect greenhouse gas emissions (Beheydt et al., 2008 D'Haene et al., 2008). Beheydt et al. (2008) observed significantly higher N₂O emission in minimal tilled soils with maize and summer oat compared to conventional tilled soils with maize. It was observed that minimal tilled soils had a higher soil moisture content than the CT soils (Beheydt et al., 2008). Likewise, Krauss et al. (2018) (based on a long-term trial in Switzerland) observed higher N₂O fluxes under RT which were positively correlated with water filled pore space level. Van Kessel et al. (2013) did a meta-analysis on 239 direct comparisons between conventional tillage (CONT) and no-tillage (NT)/reduced tillage (RT) and observed that overall, there is no change in area-scaled and yield-scaled N₂O emissions when converting from CONT to NT/RT. However, it was observed that when RT/NT practices were applied > 10 years this led to a significant reduction in N₂O emissions (Van Kessel et al., 2013). Krauss et al. (2018) observed no significant differences between N₂O emissions between RT and CT in a 2 years study (on soils where RT and CT practices have been applied > 10 years), although the N₂O emissions were higher in RT than in CT. Guenet et al. (2021) concluded that zero or reduced tillage most often does not or only minimally reduces soil-borne N₂O emissions. However, the effect may be impacted by local environmental conditions (e.g., climate, soil type).

In their review, Abdalla et al. (2013) indicated that conversion to CT has no effect on CH₄ emissions. Intensive soil cultivation breaks down soil organic matter (SOM), producing CO₂ and reducing the C stock in the soil. The studies considered in the review indicated that the CO₂ emissions are generally reduced after the adoption of conservation tillage compared to conventional tillage.

In several studies on NT/RT a redistribution of the organic carbon towards the soil surface has been observed, rather than a change in the absolute amount (D'Hose et al., 2016; Reubens et al., 2012; Van den Putte et al., 2012; Willekens et al., 2014). The carbon content is better retained in the topsoil (0-10 cm) in RT compared to CONT due to the differences in incorporation depth (crop residues are left on the surface by conservation tillage) and soil disturbance (Van den Putte et al., 2012; Willekens et al., 2014).

The accumulation of organic matter in the topsoil is beneficial since mineral N that is released from organic matter will be situated higher up in the soil and be more utilized by plants (D'Hose et al. 2016; Willekens et al. 2014). In addition, there is less risk of acidification and nutrients are less prone to leaching (Ruysschaert et al., 2021; Van den Putte et al., 2012). Van den Putte et al. (2012) observed reduced nitrate content in deeper soil layers when applying RT/NT compared to conventional tillage which indicates that RT does not lead to increased nitrate leaching. The research of Pecio et al. (2014) indicated that there is no significant difference in soil pH between non-inversion tillage and conventional ploughing.

According to literature the aggregate stability in the topsoil should be higher in CT systems. This is linked to the stratification of OM and the less intensive interruptions (Reubens et al., 2012). Under conventional ploughing macro-aggregates are readily broken down, this leads to a reduction of the C that is protected in micro-aggregates (Chivenge et al., 2007). NT and non-inversion tillage have been recorded to improve aggregate stability (Guzmán Díaz et al., 2015).

Implementation of non-inversion tillage (in combination with a cover crop) can reduce sediment loss by water erosion up to 85%, having a positive impact on soil structure and reducing soil erosion (Reubens et al., 2012). The research of Reubens et al. (2012) suggested that there is less run-off in CT systems due to the soil surface becoming rougher. Results from the "practice" indicate the potential influence of the intensity of the seedbed preparation and plant bed preparation and the combination of the used machines on the soil quality in the topsoil (Reubens et al., 2012). On the short term the amount of macropores decreases when applying non-inversion tillage techniques. Literature suggests however, that the amount of macro-pores increases again on the long term due to increasing activity of soil fauna at increasing OM contents and the creation of new macropores due to soil roots (Reubens et al., 2012).

The outcomes of the Gomeros-project (Vanden Nest et al., 2019) indicated that the erosion reduction potential of non-inversion tillage is crop dependent. This is related to several factors such as: the surface cover by the crop, plant architecture, method of seedbed preparation and sowing method (Vanden Nest et al., 2019). It has been observed that NIT is a very effective to reduce erosion in maize fields and to a lesser extent in fields with cabbages and peas. Experiments on maize fields showed an average erosion reduction of 85% (median of 91%) on all fields and 92% (median 91%) on fields that were most sensitive to erosion (Vanden Nest et al., 2019).

Literature on non-inversion tillage (NIT) systems indicate an increase in microbial biomass, and an increase in the amount and biomass of earthworms and pot worms (D'Hose et al., 2018; Reubens et al., 2012; Valck et al., 2011). The abundance of gram-negative bacteria and fungi have been recorded to be higher in the topsoil (0-7.5 cm) under RT compared to conventional tillage (Willekens, 2016).

D'Hose et al. (2018) compiled a dataset on soil biota based on more than 60 European multi-year experiments. The data included information on the applied tillage techniques and was retrieved from scientific literature and research reports and covered multiple climatic zones in Europe. It was observed that both shallow non-inversion tillage and no tillage techniques significantly increased earthworm number and biomass compared to ploughing. For deep non-inversion tillage no significant effect was observed. No tillage techniques significantly increased earthworm biomass compared to non-inversion tillage techniques (D'Hose et al., 2018).

The microbial biomass was observed to increase for non-inversion and no tillage practices. The largest difference was found in the topsoil, where the application of non-inversion tillage and no tillage techniques both resulted in an increase in the microbial biomass of 48% compared to ploughing. This was attributed to the relatively high amount of organic matter in the topsoil compared to ploughing, as it is not being dispersed to deeper soil layers. In the deeper soil layers (10-30 cm) a decrease of 14% and 4% in microbial biomass was observed for non-inversion tillage and no tillage respectively, compared to ploughing (D'Hose et al., 2018).

Further research is needed on the soil-plant interactions before the maximization of soil biota can be suggested as a main driver for farmers. In order to enhance soil biological activity however, one should not only focus on one good practice but rather one should consider the combination of RT/NT with a wider crop rotation, cover/green manure and organic amendments (D'Hose et al., 2018).

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 non-inversion tillage
 - 2 minimum tillage
 - 3 eco-tillage
 - 4 mulch tillage

5 reduced tillage, zone tillage, tined tillage, vertical tillage, deep conservation tillage,
superficial conservation tillage

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

11 - Reduced tillage in permanent crops

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Minimum tillage may be performed in alternated inter-row zones of permanent crops. (Source of definition: WOCAT)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Minimum tillage in vineyards is performed in the alternated inter-row zone, to promote soil decompaction and maintain partial vegetation cover. The following treatments were applied in four replicates: (soil cultivation experiment) SC1, natural grass cover; SC2, mechanical soil cultivation; and SC3, organic mulch (crop residues), and (nutrient supply experiment) NS1, unfertilized control, NS2, nitrogen (N) fertilizer (NH_4NO_3) 50 kg ha^{-1} ; and NS3, farmyard manure (34 tons ha^{-1}).

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

11 – Reduced tillage in permanent crops

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Most of the authors recommend the use of agricultural and communal residue for mulching in vineyards where the annual precipitation is below 700--800 mm (Varga et al., 2012). Soil water deficit due to extreme draught (Varga et al. 2012).

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	
gently sloping (2-5%)	
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	
very steep (>60%)	

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : Mulching with crop residues had a favorable influence on soil moisture levels at different soil layers while in plots with natural grass cover, decreases were observed in soil moisture compared to the level in plots receiving mechanical cultivation. (Varga et al. 2012)

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Former volcanic activity was an important factor in the development of the brown forest soils (Cambisols) (Varga et al., 2012).

It is known that site conditions may have a great impact on grape and wine quality. Soil depth, parent rocks, exposition, and altitude influence the development of ripeness and overripeness and explain the marked differences in the composition of the grape (Barbeau et al. 2001.) (Varga et al. 2012).

Soil chemistry: NPK concentrations; depth to bedrock; soil hydraulic properties.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	
2.1.3 rice fields	
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	
2.3 Pastures	
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	No

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

I1 - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	
Avoid contamination	
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

Soil water deficit due to extreme draught (Varga et al. 2012).

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

It was suggested that for effective grape growing on these soils, formed on basaltic rubble parent rock and having a shallow root zone, unfavorable water management characteristics, and low soil organic-matter content, maintaining adequate soil moisture levels and satisfactory

N supply are essential (considerable amounts of nutrients may be released by the weathering of basalt). (Varga et al. 2012)

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

1	adaptive and environmentally friendly soil cultivation
2	
3	
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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

12 - Ridging

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The technology consists of shaping the land in small ridges. Ridges are the place where the plants are growing. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

/

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

12 – Ridging

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

not too dry -- ridges dry out quicker

not too hot -- ridges warm up faster

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	No
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Hatfield, J. L., Allmaras, R. R., Rehm, G. W., & Lowery, B. I. R. L. (1998). Ridge tillage for corn and soybean production: environmental quality impacts. *Soil and tillage research*, 48(3), 145-154.

Shi, X. H., Yang, X. M., Drury, C. F., Reynolds, W. D., McLaughlin, N. B., & Zhang, X. P. (2012). Impact of ridge tillage on soil organic carbon and selected physical properties of a clay loam in southwestern Ontario. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 120, 1-7.

Varvel, G. E., & Wilhelm, W. W. (2010). Long-term soil organic carbon as affected by tillage and cropping systems. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 74(3), 915-921.

Yuan-zhi, Y. (2015). Effects of ridge tillage on photosynthesis and root characters of rice. *Chilean journal of agricultural research*, 75(1), 35-41.

Bezdicek, D. F., Beaver, T., & Granatstein, D. (2003). Subsoil ridge tillage and lime effects on soil microbial activity, soil pH, erosion, and wheat and pea yield in the Pacific Northwest, USA. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 74(1), 55-63.

Zheng, H., Huang, H., Liu, J., Yao, L., & He, H. (2014). Recent progress and prospects in the development of ridge tillage cultivation technology in China. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 142, 1-7.

<https://www.dammkultur.info/>

Henriksen, C. B., Rasmussen, J., & Sogaard, C. (2006). Ridging in autumn as an alternative to mouldboard ploughing in a humid-temperate region. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 85(1-2), 27-37.

Müller, E., et al., Spatial patterns of soil biological and physical properties in a ridge tilled and a ploughed Luvisol. *Soil Tillage Res.* (2009)

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

1 hilling

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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

13 - Rotovated band seeding

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A tillage system for row crops which reduces cultivation and tillage with a rotary tiller to the stripes, in which the seeds are planted. Between the tilled strips, the soil and soil cover remain untilled. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

A tillage system for row crops which reduces cultivation and tillage with a rotary tiller to the stripes, in which the seeds are planted. Between the tilled strips, the soil and soil cover remain untilled.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

13 – Rotovated band seeding

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

None known

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

None known

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Uncertain
Conservation Agriculture	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

The application of this practice in organic farming is limited due to the challenging herbicide-free control of the vegetation between the tilled strips (BioAktuell, 2014).

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

According to Agridea (2010, 2019) the practice enhances the soils structure and stability between the tilled rows. Additionally, the nutrient losses the sources claim that nutrient-leaching is reduced. Prasuhn (2020) documented reduced erosion in the Frienisberg Region (Switzerland) due to the widespread application of this and other soil management practices.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

1 rotary band seeding

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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

14 - Soil drilling

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Drilling holes in compacted agricultural fields to counteract soil compaction, and to enhance the soil structure and water infiltration capacity. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Drilling holes in compacted agricultural fields to counteract soil compaction, and to enhance the soil structure and water infiltration capacity.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

14 – Soil drilling

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

- wet soil conditions

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

No

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	No Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

- wet soil conditions: in case of clay soils, the soil needs to be dry to prevent soil slacking.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

- The practice aims at eliminating soil compaction, the practice therefore will be more successful on soils that are subject to subsurface soil compaction. Top soil texture does not limit the application, as the practice already has been tested on sandy, clay and peat soils.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

The practice is in its experimental phase, currently being tested on several fields.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

The practice is in the experimental phase: it has been tested and will be further developed. Researchers are currently evaluating the results, published research results are limited.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

1 Mechanic earthworm

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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

15 - Strip tillage

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Strip-till is a conservation system that reduces tillage to the strips where the plants are seeded. It combines the soil drying and warming benefits of conventional tillage with the soil-protecting advantages of no-till by disturbing only the portion of the soil that is to contain the seed row.

(Source of definition: http://aims.fao.org/aos/agrovoc/c_1516cbf3)

Specificities or other description of the practice

/

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

15 – Strip tillage

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)

gently sloping (2-5%)

sloping (5-10%)

strongly sloping (10-15%)

moderately steep (15-30%)

steep (30-60%)

very steep (>60%)

Management of organic soils/peatlands

-- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land

2.1.2 permanently irrigated land

2.1.3 rice fields

2.2.1 vineyards

2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations

2.2.3 olive groves

2.3 Pastures

2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)

3.2.1 Natural grasslands

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming
Extensive farming in less favoured areas
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming
Large-scale corporate farming

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming
Conservation Agriculture
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)
Terrace Farming

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC
Avoiding N₂O, CH₄ emissions from soils
Avoid acidification
Avoid soil erosion
Avoid soil sealing
Avoid salinisation
Avoid contamination
Optimal soil structure
Enhance soil biodiversity
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency
Enhance water storage capacity
Avoid Peat degradation

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

1	strip tilling
2	
3	
4	
5	

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

16 - Temporary ditches

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Conservation measures for eroded cropland. Level ditches of various lengths are dug along a contour. (Source of definition: WOCAT)

Specificities or other description of the practice

/

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

16 – Temporary ditches

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	NA
gently sloping (2-5%)	NA
sloping (5-10%)	NA
strongly sloping (10-15%)	NA
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

NA -- comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	NA
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	NA
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	NA
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	NA
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	NA
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	NA
Large-scale corporate farming	NA

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	NA
Conservation Agriculture	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

No data

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

1	NA
2	NA
3	NA
4	NA
5	NA

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

17 - Tyre Inflation System (TIS)

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Tyre Inflation System is a system which allows the adaptation of the inflation pressure of the tyres in order to improve their performance according to the type of surface. In field, the reduction in pressure increases the footprint on the soil, which has the effect of increasing performance in terms of traction while reducing soil compaction. On the road, increasing the pressure especially reduces tyre wear and fuel consumption. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Tyre Inflation System is a system which allows the adaptation of the inflation pressure of the tires in order to improve their performance according to the type of surface. In field, the reduction in pressure increases the footprint on the soil, which has the effect of increasing performance in terms of traction while reducing soil compaction. On the road, increasing the pressure especially reduces tire wear and fuel consumption.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

17 – Tyre Inflation System (TIS)

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The drier the climate, the less interest there is in this system, since it is in wet periods that soils are most sensitive to compaction

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

No limit has been identified. The system is all the more interesting as the soil texture is sensitive to compaction.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	
2.2.1 vineyards	
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	
2.3 Pastures	
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	
Terrace Farming	

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	
Avoid acidification	
Avoid soil erosion	
Avoid soil sealing	
Avoid salinisation	
Avoid contamination	
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

The practice is interesting to use whenever there are soils sensitive to compaction.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

The practice has the same benefits as any practice aimed at reducing soil compaction, for which the consequences are not necessarily identical (e.g., Nawaz et al., 2013).

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Central Tyre Inflation System (CTIS)
 - 2 Tyre Pressure Adjustment System (TPAS)
 - 3
 - 4

5

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

18 - Cover crops

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A crop grown to prevent soil erosion by covering the soil with living vegetation and roots that hold on to the soil. Cover crops are also grown to help maintain soil organic matter and increase nitrogen availability (green manure crop), and to ``hold on'' to excess nutrients (a catch crop) still in the soil, following an economic crop. Other benefits of cover crops include weed suppression and attraction of beneficial insects.

(Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Cover crops are grown to achieve direct benefits in the agroecosystems and for a future arable crop. Such cover crops do not provide a cash return and they are used to protect and improve the soil. There are a wide range of different cover crops used in terms of different species and mixtures of species. Cover crops can be classed according to the type of species. The major groups are: (1) with grasses (including cereals e.g. oats and rye), (2) legumes e.g. vetch and clover and (3) brassicas e.g. mustard, radish and turnips. It is common for a mixture of species to be used in order to utilise specific traits from each species. The establishment of cover crops varies across the UK. Likewise the length of growing season differs greatly from south (longer) to north (shorter). Regardless of the specific site location cover crops should be sown early enough to achieve a minimum of 25% crop cover before early winter.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

18 – Cover crops

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

At the moment there are no specific concerns on the application of this practice. Climate change may contribute to increase temperatures and reduce rainfalls over the next 20 years thus potentially affecting cover crops establishment. On the other side intense rainfall events in the autumn could increase soil erosion and negatively affect cover crops.

Generally, in Central and Northern Europe there are problems to grow winter cover crops in cool areas (higher latitudes/altitudes) where there is little time for the cover crop to develop before winter. Cover cropping may also be a challenge in very dry areas where is limited water available for crop development.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

In this regards, too wet (water logging) and too dry soil conditions (poor water holding capacity in dry area) are a challenge. Otherwise, species/cultivars are selected to optimize cover cropping in specific pedo-climatic areas.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Uncertain
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Numerous papers have been published on the influence on C storage (Thomsen and Christensen, 2004; Poplau and Don, 2015). Some other papers specifically focused on the impact on N₂O emissions (Mutegi et al., 2010; Petersen et al., 2011; Duan et al. 2018), while few papers have quantified bio-tillage effect of cover crops (top and subsoil) - e.g. Pulido-Moncada 2020,

2021; Zhang and Peng, 2021. Numerous papers on the impact of cover crops on nutrient use efficiency/retention and N leaching (e.g. Vogeler et al. 2019).

In this regard, White et al. (2016) stated there are several areas where cover crops effect soil function through changing soil properties; and subsequently this leads to a change on ecosystem services. The areas are: (1) soil fertility and soil structure, (2) pest control, and (3) the environment which includes services such as erosion and water quality (via nutrient leaching). Some cover crop species are able to improve soil fertility and increase crop yields. For example, vetch and cover crops are able to recover up to 90 kg N ha⁻¹ (Bhogal et al. 2020). Crotty and Stoate (2019) observed that there was very little effect from cover crop mixtures on N, P, K, Mg, Ca and organic matter. Bhogal et al. (2020) reported that after just one year of growing cover crop mixtures are able to provide soil structural improvement. Research by Storr et al. (2017) indicated that cover crops were only able to provide short-term benefits to structure. A UK wide survey of cover crop users found that up to 80 % of farmers observed a benefit to soil structure (Storr et al. 2019). The use of cover crops can alter the abundance and composition of soil biota. The effects derived from cover crops are specific according to each species. Thus, how well pests are controlled will depend on the type of crop being grown. Nevertheless, previous studies in the UK provide some indication how cover crops can effect pest control; e.g. Detheridge et al. (2016) found that there was a legacy effect from cover crops on the soil fungal populations of following cereal crops. In specific the white clover treatments had lower levels of root endophytic fungi. It has been reported that nematodes are most abundant where ryegrass is grown, while the greatest numbers of earthworms were found for white clover (Crotty et al. 2016). There is evidence that Brassica juncea can control of potato cyst nematode (PCN) (Wood et al. 2018). Further understanding is required on the effects from other cover crop species on soil biota.

Over winter or autumn-sown cover crops are able to protect the soil surface during the winter. Thus, cover crops are able to reduce the risk of soil erosion. Good management of over-winter cover crops should ensure that there is adequate growth in the autumn before the onset of cold and wet conditions in winter. Early establishment and/ or quick growing species are most likely to decrease the 'window of opportunity' of soil erosion (Boardman and Favis-Mortlock, 2014).

A cover crop can be used to increase the level of crop nutrient uptake. Moreover, there is evidence that cover crops can reduce nutrient loss from arable land. For example, Cooper et al. (2017) reported that a radish cover crop was able to reduce the nitrate leaching losses by 75--97% in comparison to fallow land, although there was no impact upon P losses. In contrast, when compared to winter cereals there was no significant improvement from cover crops to reduce nitrate leaching during winter (Macdonald et al. 2005). Thus, while there is potential for cover crops to improve water quality (through a decrease in nitrate leaching) at a wider catchment scale, but there is lack of evidence to support this.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

1	Catch crops
2	
3	
4	
5	

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

19 - Cover crops in permanent crops

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The technology involves soil management with cover crops (natural or spontaneous) in the streets of permanent crops.

(Source of definition: WOCAT)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The technology involves soil management with cover crops (natural or spontaneous) between the rows of permanent crops to evaluate their effectiveness against soil loss by water erosion.

In Spain, the soil under the cover crops in permanent crops practice does not receive mechanical tillage and it is protected by a spontaneous cover crop, being its growth controlled by mechanical (harvest), chemical (herbicides) or grazing. Cover crops provide a suitable soil and water conservation practice for vineyards, citrus and fruit orchard and olive-cropping farms in Southern Europe. In the year 2020, 1,176,922 ha (22.23% of the total surface) were managed with spontaneous cover crops. According to data given by the Spanish Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (MAPA, ESYRCE, 2020), from the total surface with permanent crops (5.294.596 ha of woody crops), 1,317,152 ha are covered with green manure and spontaneous cover crops. The major surface of permanent crops is concentrated in Andalusia and Castilla-La Mancha regions (59.72% of the national surface). The spontaneous cover crops are concentrated in Andalusia region (south Spain), representing the 59.20% of the national

cropped surface. Other regions where this practice represents > 5% of the surface are Catalonia (7.87%), Extremadura (6.93%), Valencia (6.05%), and Castilla-La Mancha (5.09). The spontaneous cover crops are concentrated in olive groves (64.70%). Cover crops in permanent crops are also common in fruit trees (13.71%). In the rest of permanent crops, spontaneous cover crops represent < 9%, although this sustainable management practice is the major practice applied in citrus trees (8.06%), pome-fruit trees (3.20%) and stone fruit trees (5.27%). Cover crops in permanent crops practice represent the most common soil management technique in citrus orchard (30.89%), pome fruit trees (71.86%), stone fruit trees (45.09%), other fruit trees (15.53%), vineyard (5.51%), olive groves (27.68%), and other woody permanent crops (14.89%) (MAPA, ESYRCE, 2020).

A vegetative cover in woody crops is a highly effective technique for reducing soil loss and an acceptable one for diminishing water losses from runoff (Espejo-Pérez et al., 2013). Cover crops (avoiding bare soil during long periods) have been proposed as management practices to overcome the loss of soil, SOM and nutrients in woody crops (López-Vicente et al., 2020; Morugán-Coronado et al., 2020). Cover crops are effective to conserve and improve soil quality by improving soil carbon sink (Marquez-García et al., 2013). Cover crops in permanent crops represent environmental benefits as reduction of soil erosion, increase of soil organic matter content and decrease in the GHGs emissions (CO₂) and economical benefits as fuel saving (Sastre et al., 2016; Mirás-Avalos et al., 2020; Morugán-Coronado et al., 2020). Caltrava et al. (2021) pointed out the positive effects of cover crops in almond, citrus and olive orchards, with decrease of erosion rate, increase soil organic matter and foster soil carbon sequestration and improve soil structure and fertility.

Barriers for cover crops implementation derive from the high dependence of its effects on selected crop species, agricultural management, climate, weather, and soil conditions, resulting in large yearly variations. As soil properties in olive orchards and vineyards have a large within-farm variation as influenced by tree, cover crop, and areas of bare soil, cover crops benefits tend to be limited to their implanted area, mostly concentrating in the top 0-20 cm. Moreover, the provision of enough ground cover is dependent on differences in the seed bank, and soil quality and management among different orchards. Cover crops may also reduce the yields of vines and olives, and farmers believe that tillage reduction, cover crops or intercropping could negatively affect tree water status. Besides, they prefer bare alleys and removing cover crops to avoid ‘‘dirty fields’’ (Morugán-Coronado et al., 2020). These barriers may explain why seeded cover crops are just used in just 0.45% of woody crops area in Spain while spontaneous vegetation has a much larger share (22.23%) (data from year 2020, MAPA, ESYRCE, 2020).

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

19 – Cover crops in permanent crops

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

For instance, in Hungary in the year 2014 from January until October 31st 896 mm of rain fell. In this case, the most challenging task was the protection against erosion. In the year 2017 until October 31st the 534 mm of rain fell. In this case, the most challenging task was water retention in most part of the year, but in September and October, as reported by Varga & Májer, 2019.

In Mediterranean basin, such as Spain the length of summer drought one of the most important limiting climatic factors

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Soil moisture content, soil compaction, biological activity in the soil.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	
2.1.3 rice fields	
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes

2.3 Pastures

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)

3.2.1 Natural grasslands

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	
Terrace Farming	

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

I1 - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	
Avoid salinisation	
Avoid contamination	
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

It has been forecasted that droughts events will become increasingly more frequent as a result of the effect of climatic change. The average temperature will raise and violent rainfalls can be expected more frequently. Abiotic stress effects due to inappropriate soil cultivation have a negative effect on vine growth.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

Soil nutrient levels can be considered other important limiting soil factors.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

In Hungary, The NARIC Research Institute for Viticulture and Enology (NARIC RIVE) in Badacsony setup trials using a legume seed mixture (red clover, crimson clover, white clover, common vetch and fodder peas). For the temporary plant coverage they used Winter wheat, Triticale and weed mixtures characteristic of the area, furthermore between the rows they planted just Phacelia on its own. During the trials in the 2014-2017 period, the NARIC RIVE have drawn comparisons on a slope (hill-valley directional) system between mulching with organic plant wastes, and lasting and temporary plant coverage, and also mechanical soil cultivation (Varga & Májer 2019).

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

In vineyards, where the probability of evenly distributed rainfall of 700-800 mm per year is low, it is recommended to use agricultural and municipal waste for land cover. These materials, in addition to improving soil organic matter management, reduce the risk of erosion and retain

moisture for the crop (Basler, 1992; Varga, 1994; Boller et al. 1998). Due to the significant water competition of cover crops, the use of permanent cover stock is recommended only in wetter areas (Varga et al., 2007). In those vineyard areas where the yearly rainfall is 500-520 mm, it is recommended to grass only strong-growing vines (Varga & Májer, 2019). As a result of the cover plant, soil nitrate levels are regulated throughout the year, remaining relatively low, thus reducing the risk of nitrogen leaching (Zanathy, 1998).

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 spontaneous cover crops in woody crops; natural cover crops in woody crops; vegetative cover in woody crops
 - 2 ground cover in permanent crops; spontaneous vegetation
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

20 - Crop rotation

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The practice of alternating the species or families of annual and/or biannual crops grown on a specific field in a planned pattern or sequence. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The practice of crop rotation is a strategy currently recommended to control weeds without excessive application of herbicides. Weed competition with crops can be limited by maintaining live soil cover through crop rotations, thereby making weed establishment more difficult. Cover crop rotations with leguminous and oilseed species provide the additional benefit of dietary diversity (for both animals and humans), improving soil nitrogen fixation, and has showed to be an effective practice to reduce the use of herbicides in semi-arid regions. Following these new policies, switching from cereal-intensive crop rotations towards diverse cropping sequencing (e.g. rotations of wheat or barley / rapeseed, sunflower or leguminous species) start to be frequent under rainfed conditions in different regions of Spain. Taking into account that cereals are the most extensive crops in Spain and Castilla y León region, where rainfed cereal crops represent more than 85% of the total cultivated hectares, and that the most common crop grown in Castile and Leon region in rotational system is wheat, a growing switch from cereal monoculture to rotational practices is expected in the next years (INNOVATRIGO). Diverse cropping sequencing benefits the environment, e.g. through better nutrient management, reduced need

for nitrogen (N) fertilizers, increased biodiversity, improved soil conditions and functions and reduced pest, disease and weed risks. Optimizing the production of rotational crops in Spain, is of growing importance in the context of the demands posed by the Common Agricultural Policy of the European Community (CAP, 2020). So, one of the nine "eco-schemes" included in the new Spanish CAP proposal has as aim the crop rotation with breeding species such as leguminous (pea (*Pisum sativum* L.), bean (*Vicia faba* L.), sweet lupine (*Lupinus* spp.), vetch (*Vicia sativa* L.), yeros (*Vicia ervilia* (L.) Willd.), locust bean (*Vicia monanthos* Desf.), titarros or almortas (*Lathyrus sativus* L.), fenugreek (*Trigonella foenum-graecum* L.), alberjón (*Vicia narbonensis* L.), alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.), sainfoin (*Onobrychis viciifolia* Scop.), zulla (*Hedysarum coronarium* L.), bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L., *Phaseolus lunatus* L., *Phaseolus coccineus* L.), cowpea or black bean (*Vigna unguiculata* [L.] Walp.), chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.), lentil (*Lens sculenta* Moench, *Lens culinaris* Moench), crotalaria (*Crotalaria juncea* L.), oleaginous (sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.), rapeseed (*Brassica napus* L), soybeans (*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill) y camelina (*Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz), safflower (*Carthamus tinctorius* L.)), and other species (garlic, radish, etc.) (PAC, 2020). Positive effects in C sequestration have been found in experiments lasting more than 29 years, dependent on crop residue management and the type of crops in the rotation (Lopez-Bellido et al., 2020; Bienes et al., 2021). Crop rotations can help in restoring soil fertility and structure, preventing soil erosion, runoff and sediment losses (Nuñez et al., 2013; Baldivieso-Freitas et al., 2018). They have been considered for reduction of weed infestations (integrated weed control) and low use of herbicides (Pardo et al., 2021) and increase available water and water retention through higher soil porosity and macroaggregate stability (Bienes et al., 2021). Crop rotations are common in Spain for winter cereals (wheat and barley). Typically, they imply either two- or three- year rotations, depending on whether fallow is included, and usually they alternate winter cereals (wheat or barley) with pea, oats, vetch or sunflower (MAPA, ESYRCE 2020). The most frequent crop rotations in Spain for the years 2019-2020 have been wheat-barley (23.4%), wheat-sunflower (12.5%), barley-wheat (11.8%), barley-sunflower (8.3%), barley-leguminous (4.4%), and wheat-leguminous (3.2%), (MAPA-ESYRCE, 2020). Crop rotation require more detailed planning than monoculture approaches regarding selection of crop species, and nutrient and weed control practices. Nevertheless, they can contribute to reduce the use of fertilizers, pesticides and herbicides, and possible enhance crop yield and soil quality improvements in the long term (Cámara-Salim et al., 2021; Pardo et al., 2021). Besides, low investment and operational costs are associated to their introduction. Moreover, the cultivation of legumes in crop rotations has the potential to fix nitrogen, consequently decreasing the need for nitrogen fertilizer inputs (Cámara-Salim et al., 2021). Crop rotation does not have to follow a fixed sequence, but crops can rotate differently according to specific needs, such as market requests or climate changes. In general, the main reason for adopting crop rotation has been the search for the best economic result of the enterprise. This could be done through sharing the risk of farming between crops (for instance introducing vegetables in the arable crop rotation), a better farm organisation (complementarity of workload) and more flexibility to cope with market and cli-

mate instability. Lower energy inputs and costs for machinery, fertilisers and pesticides were also important economic incentives. Similarly, P20 - NPPC (Slovakia), clarified that crop diversification is part of adaptation to climate change, increasing biodiversity, improving soil properties, soil water regime, storing carbon in the soil and increasing the level of provision of ecosystem services of agricultural land. In recent decades, the diversity of cultivated crops has decreased in Slovakia, a substantial majority of the area is occupied by 10 crops, and of these 10 crops, the five most widespread over 80% of arable land. In addition, monocultures often take up large fields and the average size of agricultural parcels is large, one of the highest in the EU (highest average area in EU). The introduction of ‘‘greening’’ as one of the CAP tools in this respect was positive for the agricultural land of the Slovak Republic. Change in the setting of the Common Agricultural Policy could bring support for green elements/ features in agricultural land, reducing the area of monocultural fields, growing crops with or diversification of cultivated crops. Crop diversification within the farm affects the diversity of crops, fruits and vegetables grown. The minimum number of cultivated crops and the share of their acreage within an agricultural enterprise is set out in the Regulation of the Government of the Slovak Republic no. 342/2014 Coll., Which lays down the rules for providing support in agriculture in connection with decoupled direct payment schemes. This is an interpretation of Article 44 of Regulation (EU) No 182/2011. 1307/2013. Area of arable land declared by the holding for the purpose of granting payment for agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and the environment required number of cultivated crops According this Law the required area of crops in the sowing procedure: up to 10 ha -- 10-30 ha at least 2 main crops may not cover more than 75% of the arable land area over 30 ha at least 3 main crops may not cover more than 75% of the arable land area two main crops may not cover more than 95% of the arable land area. Therefore, all farmers over 10 ha of arable land, if they receive support payment for agricultural practices beneficial for the climate and the environment, are obliged to carry out crop diversification.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

20 – Crop rotation

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The application of this practice in all the main environmental areas of Europe. No limitation by climatic features has been found in these regions.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	No
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	No
Terrace Farming	No

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

In a research study carried out in Slovakia crop productivity in organic farming was lower. However, on soils with good nutrient status, difference between organic and conventional farming was not significant. Balance of energy-material flows in field ecological sensitive agroecosystem.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

1 successive crop

2 rotational crop

3

4

5

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

21 - Deep rooting plants

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Plants with high root growth capacity as a practice to improve soil quality.

(Source of definition: WOCAT)

Specificities or other description of the practice

These are annual and perennial herbaceous plants with a deeply penetrating root system. Deep roots are a common trait among a wide range of plant species and biomes, and are pivotal to the very existence of ecosystem services such as pedogenesis, groundwater and streamflow regulation, soil carbon sequestration and moisture content in the lower troposphere.

Deep roots definition is challenging to express. Pierret et al. (2016) proposed that 'deep roots' be defined as roots growing at soil depths of at least 1 m.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

21 – Deep rooting plants

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

There are no general climatic factors that limit all deep rooting plants. factors may be: drought, precipitation amount, transpiration.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : The plant species must be suitable for peatland.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

- 1) soil compaction: penetrometer resistances >2MPa, air-filled volume of <10%, and a matric potential greater than -1.5MPa;
- 2) Al toxicity pH of ~4.8;
- 3) Mn toxicity pH of <5.3 and ph-7.0;
- 4) in arid regions, subsoils can contain toxic levels of sodium (Na), boron (B), and salinity;
- 5) low Ca and P availability;
- 6) vertical temperature gradients;
- 7) hypoxia.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

The water infiltration depths and evaporative demand are the main climatic factors to determine vertical root distributions on a global scale.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

In Agro-forestry system on dry climatic conditions, tree with deep root system might reduce moisture regime. Therefore, deep-rooted plants are weaker.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Kristian Thorup-Kristensen, Niels Halberg, Mette Nicolaisen, Jørgen Eivind Olesen, Timothy E. Crews, Philippe Hinsinger, John Kirkegaard, Alain Pierret, Dorte Bodin Dresbøll, Digging

Deeper for Agricultural Resources, the Value of Deep Rooting, Trends in Plant Science, Volume 25, Issue 4, 2020, Pages 406-417, ISSN 1360-1385, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tplants.2019.12.007>.

Timo Kautz, Wulf Amelung, Frank Ewert, Thomas Gaiser, Rainer Horn, Reinhold Jahn, Mathieu Javaux, Andreas Kemna, Yakov Kuzyakov, Jean-Charles Munch, Stefan Pätzold, Stephan Peth, Heinrich W. Scherer, Michael Schloter, Heike Schneider, Jan Vanderborght, Doris Vetterlein, Achim Walter, Guido L.B. Wiesenberg, Ulrich Köpke, Nutrient acquisition from arable subsoils in temperate climates: A review, Soil Biology and Biochemistry, Volume 57, 2013, Pages 1003-1022, ISSN 0038-0717, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2012.09.014>.

Alain Pierret, Jean-Luc Maeght, Corentin Clément, Jean-Pierre Montoroi, Christian Hartmann, Santimaitree Gonkhamdee, Understanding deep roots and their functions in ecosystems: an advocacy for more unconventional research, Annals of Botany, Volume 118, Issue 4, October 2016, Pages 621--635, <https://doi.org/10.1093/aob/mcw130>

Gao W., Jin K, Watts C.W., Ashton R.W., Shen J., Ren T., Dodd I.C., Binley A., Phillips A.L., Hedden P., Hawkesford M. J., Whalley W.R. 2016. Deep roots and soil structure. Plant. Cell & Environment. Volume39, Issue8, pp. 1662-1668

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Land reclamation plants
 - 2 Soil improvement plants
 - 3 Services plants
 - 4 Deep riping plants
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

22 - Establishment of permanent grassland

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Forage established with domesticated introduced or indigenous species that may receive periodic cultural treatment such as renovation, fertilization or weed control. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Includes grazed pastures and grassland harvested for hay, silage or a combination of both. They receive high external inputs of fertiliser and disturbance (e.g. biomass removal, reseeding and drainage) and are typically dominated by productive forage grasses such as perennial ryegrass (*Lolium perenne*) and to a lesser extent by herbs and white clover (*Trifolium repens*).

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

22 – Establishment and maintenance of permanent grassland

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Yes. Productive grasslands require mild, moist temperate climatic conditions to support a prolonged grass growing season. Soils require high organic matter, temperatures should be moderate and there should be sufficient / high rainfall (e.g. as high as 900 - 2000 mm annually).

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	No
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : Permanent grasslands are undisturbed soils. The grass roots promote carbon sequestration, storage of organic matter and cycling of nutrients. The soil surface is permanently covered by grass, reducing soil exposure and soil erosion risk.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The following practices limit production of permanent grassland:

1. soil compaction
2. poor drainage
3. acidity and infrequent liming

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	No
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Adverse Effect
Avoid acidification	Adverse Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Most suitable for temperate climatic zones

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

High N fertiliser inputs can increase N₂O emissions. Grazing livestock can increase NH₄ emissions. High N fertiliser inputs and high rainfall increase soil acidity. lime is required. The grass roots improve soil structure and promote carbon storage. Grassland promotes high organic matter storage and fertile soils. Good soil structure improves soil water storage capacity.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

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bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

23 - Grassland with legumes

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Grass-legume mixtures are commonly cultivated to increase grassland productivity while reducing the need for nitrogen (N) fertilizer.

(Source of definition: Arlete et al., 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11104-019-04338-w)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Grass-legume mixtures are commonly cultivated to increase grassland productivity while reducing the need for nitrogen (N) fertiliser. Forage legumes have a key role as the main source of N supply in place of fertilizers in permanent and temporary grassland as well. Moreover, grass-legume mixtures may improve a number of ecosystem services including soil structure maintenance, carbon sequestration, nutrient cycling, water regulation and purification, biodiversity conservation. Besides environmental benefits, grass-legume mixtures improve herbage quality, stability and persistence of biomass yield as well. Forage legumes are considered the backbone of the ley farming in southern regions of Slovakia or in upland and mountain areas with high proportion of natural habitats, where it is necessary to produce high-quality conserved forage for winter. Alfalfa and red clover are the most widespread legume species used in ley farming, especially in Slovakia. During 2014-20219, the area of used permanent grasslands occupies approximately 518 thousand ha, of which 38 % were habitats. In general, permanent grasslands are oversown by grass-legume mixtures, except for habitats, where according to Regulation of the Government of the Slovak Republic No 342/2014 Coll. that lays down the rules

for granting support in agriculture in relation to the schemes of decoupled direct payment as amended, only sowing of habitat specific grass species is allowed. On arable land, grass-clover mixtures are included in crop rotations especially in areas with a slope of more than 12°. In compliance with the National Rural Development Plan of the Slovak Republic, in these areas at least 40% of soil cover has to be maintained in autumn and winter (from November 1st to March 1st). In 2020, grass-clover mixtures occupied app. 213 thousand ha in Slovakia. Grass-legume mixtures are included also in measurement for great bustard (*Otis tarda*) conservation. Within the measurement of Conservation of habitat of great bustard (*Otis tarda*) it is required to implement basic crop rotation where

- at least 4 main crops are included,
- the total share of winter cereals, oilseed rape, fodder crops, grasses on arable land and catch crops is at least 70%, of which
 1. a proportion of oilseed rape or fodder crops of at least 15%,
 2. share of grasses on arable land is at least 5%.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

23 – Grassland with legumes

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

In this context, lucerne has the greatest productive potential in south regions with lower total sum of rainfall. Red clover is cultivated mainly in upland and mountain areas with a total annual rainfall of more than 700 mm. Similarly, clover grows across a wide range of soil and moisture conditions growing well in humid areas. It does not like climatic extremes that result in drought or flooded conditions. Quantitative ranges for different agroclimatic regions not readily available for different species and varieties.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : P13 - Teagasc (Ireland) clarified that if clover is naturally occurring it is fine but reseeding of organic soils/peatlands is not recommended due to biodiversity and carbon losses.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

In this context, clover grows well on a wide range of soil types and under a range of edaphic properties. Clover does not perform well where there is high soil N. Where required, grass-white clover swards must contain an annual average sward clover content of at least 20% to be considered productive. This level of white clover is necessary to ensure N fixation to replace chemical N fertiliser. Swards should be reseeded or over sown with white clover seed when average sward clover content drops below 20% (Teagasc Green Book, 2020 Wall and Plunkett (eds)). Does not perform at very high or low pH with 7.0 pH optimum for white clover.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Uncertain
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect

Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

Grass-lucerne mixtures for limiting soil factors: ground water level less than 1.5m, optimal pH 6.5-7.5.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

In sheep farming systems clover survival can be encouraged by rotational grazing rather than continuous sheep grazing as sheep preferentially graze clover plants. Grass-white clover swards must contain an annual average sward clover content of at least 20% to be considered productive. This level of white clover is necessary to ensure N fixation to replace chemical N fertiliser. Swards should be reseeded or over sown with white clover seed when average sward clover content drops below 20 (Wall and Plunkett, 2020).

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Grass clover sward
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

24 - Intercropping (association)

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Growing two or more crops simultaneously on the same field. Crop intensification is in both time and space dimensions. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Intercropping is defined as 'growing two or more crops simultaneously on the same field'. Crop intensification is in both time and space dimensions. The basic principle of this practice is to increase the crop diversification by association (several crops on the same parcel in the same time: intercropping, strip cropping, companion crop), or by multiple cropping (several crops on the same parcel, but not in the same time: crop succession, winter cover crop) . Since the latter (cover crops) is a separate measure (15), we focus solely on crops that are grown on the same parcel at the same time. Likewise, intercropping with annual crops and trees is not considered, as agroforestry is a separate measure (14).

Commonly tested or practiced intercropping systems include:

- Maize-soybean
- Maize-grass
- Maize-wheat
- Barley-pea

- Wheat-pea
- Wheat-beans
- Wheat-lentil
- Wheat-cabbage
- Carrot-onion
- Potatoes-grassclover

The intercropping literature is dominated by studies on cereal/legume mixtures.

We were struggling with the difference between `intercropping' and `strip cropping', as the latter is a separate measure, while both measures encompasses growing two or more crops in alternated strips.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

24 – Intercropping (association)

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

No

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Soil nutrient levels and fertilization

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Uncertain
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Uncertain
Large-scale corporate farming	Uncertain

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Uncertain
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	No
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	No
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

There are no general climatic factors that limit all possible forms of intercropping. It is important to choose the right crop for each situation, taking climatic factors in consideration. A wide range of plants, each with different benefits can be selected. Determine the challenge or combination of challenges of the farm (e.g. nitrate leaching or soil erosion) to tailor the needed crops (Mallast et al., 2014).

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

Not necessarily limiting, but it does have an effect. Soil nutrient levels and fertilization: in legume-barley intercropping systems, the intercropping advantage (as determined by the LER value) is reduced with increasing levels of N fertilization and increases with the proportion of pea in the intercropping system (Jensen et al., 2020).

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Intercropping was defined as growing two or more crops, excluding trees to prevent overlap with agroforestry. Therefore, intercropping is not compatible with vineyards, fruit trees, olive groves and agroforestry and I selected 'no' for these systems. Though, many examples exist of the combination of annual crops with vineyards (e.g. a commercial steep-slope vineyard with shallow soils characterized by a high presence of coarse rock fragments in the Mosel area of Germany was intercropped with aromatic plants (Dittrich et al., 2021)) or olive groves (e.g. olive trees in combination with leguminous crops or cereals is a traditional practice in Greece (Mantzanas et al., 2021)).

Whether intercropping is feasible highly depends from the context. Technically, intercropping should be possible for all the above mentioned agricultural systems, on the condition that the selected crops provide mutual benefits and fit in the specific agro-ecological context. However, intercropping might lead to other challenges, such as additional costs and labour. Since the feasibility is highly related to the context and combination of crops, I selected 'uncertain' for the remaining agricultural systems.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Intercropping can increase the utilization efficiency of resources such as light, heat, water, and fertilizer to effectively improve the primary production of land per unit area (Yin et al., 2020), but highly depends on the local circumstances and crop combinations. A list of the effects on soil challenges reported in literature from various experiments in Europe are listed below:

Carbon sequestration:

- Intercropping can increase carbon sequestration, mainly due to increased root production in strip intercrops compared to monocultures (Jensen et al., 2020).
- Intercropping grass with maize results in a higher amount of soil organic matter compared to monocultures (Deru et al., 2014).

Emissions:

- Legume-based intercropping may reduce N₂O emissions.

Soil erosion:

- A wheat-mustard intercropping system in France caused lower runoff than a no-till system, but did not reduce erosion (Martin, 1999).
- A vineyard-thyme intercropping system resulted in higher soil erosion (Dittrich et al., 2021).

Soil structure:

- Cultivating maize and grass in alternating strips has proved to benefit the soil structure. Intercropping maize with grass also facilitates harvesting without damaging the soil structure.
- Increased rhizosphere processes as a result of intercropping can manifest particularly via the role which the belowground biota play in soil structural dynamics. Increased soil cover and reduction in runoff rates, erosion and nutrient leaching.

Soil biodiversity:

- Research has shown that the diversity of insects is two-four times higher in intercropping than in monocultures, especially soil organisms (beetles, centipedes, spiders). Intercropping provides a suitable habitat for natural enemies, reducing the occurrence of damaged crops.
- Soil biotic communities are affected by plant diversity, with increase in abundance, diversity and activity of functional groups. Attendant rhizosphere-located processes can facilitate nutrient uptake between component crops.

Nutrient use efficiency:

- The competitiveness of cereal crops in terms of nitrogen absorption allows them to capture residual mineral nitrogen from previous crops, whereas the symbiotic fixation of atmospheric nitrogen by legumes provides a cleaner resource for its needs while helping to meet the nutrient requirements of its partner (Mamime & Farès, 2020).
- Intercropping of field pea and spring barley in a Danish conventional cropping system showed that it is possible to obtain similar grain yields in an intercropping system without N fertilizer as in a sole barley crop receiving 80 kg N ha⁻¹ (Jensen et al., 2020).
- Measurements of nitrate leaching have shown that intercrops have lower leaching rates than grain legumes grown as sole crops and lower N₂O emissions than sole crops (Jensen et al., 2020).
- Intercropping can improve plant yields and phosphorus use efficiency. Increased N use efficiency and the transfer of atmospheric N to soil has been measured in legume-cereal intercrops.
- Intercropping of grain legumes and cereals improves the use of soil N resources and reduces the requirement for synthetic fertilizer N (Jensen et al., 2018).

Water storage capacity:

- Intercropping can increase water use efficiency of crops via optimizing the soil moisture environment for crop development (Yin et al., 2020).
- A commercial steep-slope vineyard with shallow soils characterized by a high presence of coarse rock fragments in the Mosel area of Germany was intercropped with aromatic plants. Soil moisture was consistently lower in the topsoil due to intercropping, and was statistically significant at the end of each crop cycle (Dittrich et al., 2021).

Peat degradation:

- Studies on intercropping as a measure to alleviate peatland degradation in Europe are limited, literature on focusses mostly on (oil palm plantations) in tropical areas.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Multiple cropping
 - 2 Mixed cropping
 - 3 Companion crop
 - 4
 - 5
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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

25 - Intercropping (relay)

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Relay Intercropping is the practice of growing two or more different crops, with different growth characteristics and development requirements, in the same season and the same field. In Switzerland, the practice is applied with winter wheat and soybean. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Relay Intercropping is the practice of growing two or more different crops, with different growth characteristics and development requirements, in the same season and the same field. In Switzerland, the practice is applied with winter wheat and soybean.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

25 – Intercropping

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Vegetation period must sustain both crops, e.g. winter wheat and soya.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Not adaptable to droughty, poorly drained, or very heavy clay soils

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Uncertain
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Uncertain
Large-scale corporate farming	Uncertain

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Uncertain
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Unknown Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Mechanical weed control is limited in the rows, therefore weed control in organic farming is challenging.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

The two overlapping crops increase the nutrient use efficiency and provide permanent soil cover, either directly by the living plants or by the plant residues. It seems plausible that this in turn reduces erosion, and leads to enhanced soil structure and increased microbial activities and diversity. The increased biomass production could lead to higher SOM inputs and thus to higher SOC. How the higher input of SOM affects greenhouse gas emissions remains unknown. In any case, we reviewed no evidence on the claimed effects on the soil.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

—
1
2
3
4
5
—

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

26 - Legume integration

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The integration of leguminous crops for improved soil quality and the fixation of N. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Annual and perennial N-fixing plants are discussed here.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

26 – Legume integration

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Pulse crops can be categorized into cool-season (dry peas lentil, lupins and chick pea) and warm- season (common bean, soybean, pigeonpea, mungbean, urd beans, cowpea) crops based primarily on their ability to emerge in cool season conditions and on frost tolerance.

The key climatic factors influencing the food legumes are insolation, temperature, day length and water availability.

Forage legume species are sensitive to drought stress.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : Cultivation of forage legume or mixtures with grasses are suitable for peatlands.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Forage legume species are sensitive to ground water level, water infiltration through the soil, phosphorus deficiency or availability, pH <4.5 and > 8.5.

N₂ fixation can be affected by physical (compaction, oxygen saturation, moisture), chemical (pH, salinity, mineral N, P, K, microelements) and biological (rhizobial strains, competition between introduced and indigenous strains, microbial parasites and predators) factors of soil.

There are no common climatic factors limiting the growth of legumes.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect

Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Avoiding N₂O, CH₄ emissions from soils is not always beneficial effect due to different agricultural management.

To avoid soil erosion and peat degradation needs to cultivate perennial legume or legume-grass mixes.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Grain legume
 - 2 Forage legume
 - 3 Nitrogen-fixing plants
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

27 - Diverse sward of permanent grasslands

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Grasslands with a high level of multifunctionality in order to optimize the provision of environmental goods and biodiversity preservation, on one hand, and on the other, economic efficiency and provision of quality food. (Source of definition: Multisward.eu)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Diverse sward refers to the number of species only. Sward diversity represents a continuum from a low number of species to naturally occurring high species rich grasslands. The EU definition of permanent grasslands indicates that they must not be reseeded more than once every five years - this is not included in the project definition. The project definition is more specific to multifunctionality: Grasslands with a high level of multifunctionality in order to optimize the provision of environmental goods and biodiversity preservation, on one hand, and on the other, economic efficiency and provision of quality food. The project definition does not refer at all to sward diversity. The use of the term 'optimise' implies a balance, whereby all of the functions must be achieved as opposed to maximising in favour of either for example, biodiversity on the other hand economic efficiency. The project definition would indicate active management however, often diverse swards occur naturally in less intensive systems where reseeded is not routinely done or species rich grasslands. However, most research is concerned with the multifunctionality of diverse swards in relation to environmental goods, biodiversity and economic efficiency and in practice, active management favours those that show to be more multifunctional.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

27 – Diverse sward of permanent grasslands

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The practice is not limited by climate however, the species composition should be tailored to localised conditions.

For example, Timothy and Burnet species works better on wetter soils while deep rooting species such as chicory and cock's foot are suitable for drought conditions. Both chicory and plantain like warmer conditions during establishment. Yarrow, Lucerne and Cock's foot prefer dry soil conditions. Chicory - performs better on higher fertility and free draining soils in warm condition. Plantain - also like warmer conditions. In general, pan-European research indicates that 4 to 6 species can perform well across a broader climate gradient.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : It depends - If established naturally as semi-natural grasslands this is okay. Under active management that includes reseeding practices, liming or fertilisation this practice is not recommended owing to trade-offs in terms of biodiversity and carbon losses. Extensive grazing management is acceptable.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The practice is not limited by soil properties however, the species composition should be tailored to local soil properties.

For example, Timothy species works better on wetter soils while deep rooting species such as chicory are suitable for drought conditions and require a deeper profile not suited to shallow soils (i.e. <30cm).

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	No
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	No
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	No

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect

Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

Legume persistence prefer higher annual minimum temperatures (Brophy, 2017). Specific species may have individual limiting climatic factors but the composition of the sward can be changed to adapt. Notably, the application of diverse permanent grasslands is wide but just requires tailoring to specific regions.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

Soil profile depth that too shallow resulting in low water availability under drought conditions for certain species e.g. certain species such as Timothy that prefer wetter conditions will be affected, conversely species selection in favour of more drought resilience species should be selected for freer draining soils in drier locations.

Salinisation outside tolerance levels of species.

pH outside species range.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Regarding Q12 in relation to slope gradient classes If mixed species swards are established naturally all slope classes are possible. Reseeding or other mechanised practices is not recommended on slope gradients from strongly sloping and above.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Mixed species swards
 - 2 Multi species swards
 - 3 Biodiverse swards
 - 4 Herbal Leys
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

28 - Perennial crops

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A plant that normally lives for more than two years. Trees and shrubs are perennial plants. Some perennials die back to the roots each winter but new shoots grow again in the spring. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

/

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

28 – Perennial crops

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	NA
gently sloping (2-5%)	NA
sloping (5-10%)	NA
strongly sloping (10-15%)	NA
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

NA -- comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	NA
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	NA
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	NA
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	NA
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	NA
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	NA
Large-scale corporate farming	NA

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	NA
Conservation Agriculture	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

No data

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

1	NA
2	NA
3	NA
4	NA
5	NA

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

29 - Strip cropping

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Strip cropping is a method of farming which involves cultivating a field partitioned into long, narrow strips which are alternated in a crop rotation system. (Source of definition: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Strip_farming)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Strip cropping is a method of farming, which involves cultivating a field partitioned into long, narrow strips that are alternated in a crop rotation system. There are multiple forms of strip cropping, such as field strip cropping, contour strip cropping, bufferstrip cropping or wind strop cropping (EOS, 2021). Here we focus on field strip cropping. Other inventory sheets treat contour and buffer strip cropping. Field strip cropping is often applied in but not limited to vegetable crops.

A practice abstract designed within the DiverIMPACTS Project (Van Apeldoorn et al., 2020) gives an overview over this practice.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

29 – Strip cropping

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The climatic limitations of the grown crops apply to this practice.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

There not known other soil properties that limit the application of strip cropping

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Uncertain
Large-scale corporate farming	Uncertain

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Unknown Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Among the sources we reviewed Trinchera et al. (2021), Van Apeldoorn et al. (2020) and Juventia et al. (2021) none focused on the effects of the practice to particular soil challenges. Erosion susceptibility may be reduced by the differing cropping schedules that may reduce the area of bare soil.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Strip Farming
 - 2 Field Strip Cropping
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

30 - Undersowing

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Sow a later-growing crop on land already seeded with another crop. (Source of definition: <https://www.lexico.com/definition/undersow>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Undersowing can be done before or after the main crop is sown, or simultaneously (Mallast et al., 2014). To prevent overlap with intercropping (22), the practice of `undersowing' is demarcated to crops that are sown with the aim to prevent nutrient leaching, provide nutrients, improve the soil structure or reduce soil erosion, rather than for its yield. Many combinations are possible. The most common practices and combinations mentioned in literature are listed below:

- Undersowing under maize with grass (*Lolium perenne*/*Lolium multiflorum*/*Festuca rubra*/*Festuca arundinacea*)
 - Undersowing under spring-sown cereal with grass/clover
 - Undersowing under cereal with (forage) legumes
 - Undersowing under winter oilseed rape with frost-sensitive legumes
 - Undersowing under sugar beets with barley to prevent wind erosion
-

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

30 – Undersowing

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

- Drought
- Length of the growing period

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment : On all soils where crop cultivation is possible, undersowing should be possible as well. However, peatlands are generally under special attention and conservancy management, which creates additional challenges. In case of the Netherlands, most peatlands are grasslands, providing limited options for undersowing. However, the FAO estimated that 58% of the European peatlands is used for cropland. Undersowing in cropland on peatlands has proven to be effective (Lemola et al., 2000).

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

- Soil nutrients
- Weeds
- Soil moisture

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

- Drought: the development of undersown crops is generally slow and marginal until the main crop is harvested. In case of drought, under seeds might wither (Mallast et al., 2014).
- Length of the growing period: in case of a short growing period, the undersown crop might not have the time to fully develop after the harvest of the main crop, and will not be able to provide the opted benefits.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

- Soil nutrients: the soil nutrient levels and/or fertilization needs to be suitable for both the main crop and the cover/catch crop, for example phosphate deficient soils will result in poor clover establishment.
- Weeds: when root weeds are present, undersowing is not recommended.
- Soil moisture content: when the soil moisture content is too low, undersown seeds might not germinate.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

In silvopastoral systems animals graze under trees/shrubs, this is not considered as undersowing. As undersowing under grass is not possible, the silvopastoral system cannot be combined with the practice of undersowing. In theory, undersowing might be possible in the crops of an agrosilvicultural or agrosilvopastoral system.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

The effects of undersowing are strongly related to the combination of crops. Characteristics of the undersown crop that benefit a successful cultivation include the ability to germinate easily, be able to cope with droughts and provide limited competition to the main crop. Properly chosen undersown crops have various environmental benefits.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Living mulch
 - 2 Undersowing cover crops
 - 3 Underseeding
 - 4 Catch crops
 - 5 Living mulch, underseeding, undersowing a catch/cover/green manure crop, use of undersown leys
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

31 - Biochar

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Application of charcoal as a soil amendment. (Source of definition: WOCAT)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The term biochar refers to a ‘‘coal’’ derived from biomass thermal depolymerization processes. It is a neologism that broadly encompasses all organic solid material obtained from the thermochemical conversion of biomass in an oxygen limited environment (pyrolysis). The biochar obtained from the controlled pyrolysis of waste materials or food waste retains most of the carbon in a stable form, limiting its release in the form of carbon dioxide, limiting the emission of greenhouse gases and mitigating the phenomenon of global warming. The particular surface structure of biochar, characterized by pores of heterogeneous dimensions and numerous functional groups and high surface area, makes it possible to use this material in the removal of organic and inorganic contaminants from water. It has a remarkable affinity with organic compounds such as pesticides, herbicides, dyes, which may be present in the run-off waters of agricultural land. If applied appropriately, in areas vulnerable to nitrates and within agricultural lands bordering the buffer strips, it has the ability to increase the activity of water purification and the action of removing pollutants. The biochar microstructure is an ideal environment for the growth of micro-organisms and when applied in the soil it causes an increase in microbial activity, aimed at making an effective contribution to reducing nutrient losses in water, sustainable from the environmental and economic point of view. Thanks to its peculiar

properties, it can be used to protect the environment and combat climate change. The biochar can be used as a product itself or as an ingredient within a blended product, with a range of applications as an agent for soil improvement, improved resource use efficiency, remediation and/or protection against environmental pollution, and as an avenue for greenhouse gas (GHG) mitigation. Generally, it is used to amend the soil. The purpose of use is important because it is what makes the difference between biochar and charcoal. Indeed, between the two it is possible to refer to exactly the same product, but the charcoal will exclusively have an energetic (industrial) finality. During the pyrolysis one can play and on the content of oxidizing agent (more or less O₂ notably), and on the temperature (from 300°C to 700°C) so that the carbon skeleton of the biomass is purified differently. Plus, depending on the composition of the raw material used in the biochar making process (any organic material, from chicken carcass to woody residue...) there is a huge range of final product. Thus, biochars with very different properties will be obtained depending on the parameters of the production process, resulting in a phenomenal variability of final product quality that must be taken into account for soil usage. Not to mention that the way of applying biochar on the soil, and the environmental features of the site are variables that interact with all the previously mentioned parameters, and condition the results of a biochar amendment. The current use of biochar in Europe is very anecdotal, mainly because of legislative brakes (because fertilizing materials are approved at the European level and for the moment biochar is not part of this list, but there is a chance that it will be integrated by 2022).

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

31 – Biochar

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Climatic factors are not limiting. However, some authors suggest that soil temperature can increase biochar decomposition rate.

Also, in temperate climate long term impact of biochar application is increased soil quality and crop productivity.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : Both partners agreed that the use of biochar is suitable for the sustainable management of organic soils and peatlands. In particular, P15 - UL (Latvia) stated that in the paper published in 2011 (Jeffrey et al.; doi:10.1016/j.agee.2011.08.015) biochar application was not studied in different soil types, including histosols. Later there was study on biochar application to peat, that can result in higher strawberry productivity (Tender et al., 2016; <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2016.05.001>). Similarly, P5 - CRAW (Belgium) reported that there were no contraindications, but since agricultural peatlands are already very rich in carbon, the logic is to maintain them instead of adding supplementary carbon via biochar (even though it's not the same type of carbon, since biochar is inert). Biochar would then be better valorised elsewhere, on a soil not as rich in carbon.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The high pH of biochar can limit its applications in semi- and arid soils. Therefore, application of biochar to agricultural soils in these areas are very limited. Soil pH is one of the major factors hindering the application of biochar to agricultural soils. Most types of biochar are of alkaline nature and its application to agricultural soil may negatively affect the availability

of soil nutrients due to increasing soil pH. The pH of the produced biochar is a function of pyrolysis temperature and time; by elevating the pyrolysis temperature and time, the pH of the produced biochars can be higher than 8.5. The 1:2 or 3:4 ratio between tons of biochar applied on the soil and tons humic carbon - in plow layer - present in the same soil should be maintained.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

In this context, one of the limiting factors may be soil pH, as biochar may increase soil pH (Brtnicky et al., 2021). Therefore, biochar application in alkali soils must be reviewed. In addition, the ratio between biochar applied and soil humic carbon has been estimated based on the experience of the interviewed expert as reported in the thesis work. However, making humic carbon - in the ploughing layer - a minority compared to biochar could promote an imbalance of soil nutrients since the two do not have the same functions (biochar is inert and humic carbon is bioactive). Then, as a precautionary principle, it is better not to exceed

this ratio because biochar is still largely unused in Europe (so we are still at the theoretical stage) and as it has a long life span (a few centuries at least), any mistake could afterwards be disastrous for soil fertility during a long time.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

In this context, the following additional information is added:

- 2.1.2: not sure because we have to incorporate the biochar, otherwise it would not stay on the plot.
- 2.1.3: worse scenario than permanently irrigated land (the biochar would float in this case) so to use it with this type of land use we would also have to incorporate it thoroughly into the soil.
- 2.2.2: in the inter-rows yes, but we have to turn them over at some point.
- 2.3/ 3.2.1: yes if we turn over the pasture (to reseed or restore for example) so that we can then incorporate the biochar, otherwise the pasture may be on a slope and the biochar may end up at the bottom of the slope instead of staying on the plot.
- 2.4/ 2.4.1: yes if it is mechanizable at least on the annual part of the system.
- Organic agriculture: uncertain for the moment because the legislation is not clear (there is no organic or non-organic status for the biochar as long as there is no agreement at the European level) and the issue is that organic agriculture is, on the other hand, linked to a strict legislation. Basically, the issue is that it is mainly wood that is used for biochar production (by the producers currently commercializing it), and wood is not considered eligible for the organic label.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Reduced soil CH₄ emissions have been reported from paddy soils (Fu et al., 2021), need additional information on CH₄ emissions from organic soils. Larger effect on soil water storage capacity is reported in sandy texture soils (Zhang et al., 2021; Rehman et al., 2020); Other effects have been well documented in the survey provided materials, also effects are sedimented in various review papers.

- Avoid N₂O, CH₄ emissions from soils : There is a decrease observed directly due to the use of biochar, notably in N₂O emissions.
- Avoid acidification : There is a long term liming effect of biochar, unless there is a lot of sulfur in the biochar, which is rarely the case.

- Avoid salinisation : Depends if it is a soil with sodium excess, if yes and we use a plant that have grown on it (so with too much sodium) it could be a problem.
- Avoid contamination: Could be a beneficial, an adverse effect or even with no effect : because there is a risk of introducing contaminants (PAHs and heavy metals for example), could decrease the effects of active materials (notably pre-emergence herbicide) or phytosanitary products because it plays a role of activated carbon.
- Enhance soil nutrient/use efficiency: The CEC of the biochar will gradually become organic, in connection with the carboxylic groups that will be formed with time (by surface oxidation, or adsorption of fulvic acid on its surface). An organic CEC will retain a lot of calcium, a little less magnesium and not at all potassium, so potentially there will be problematic deficiencies in potassium due to the effect of abundance in calcium and magnesium. But overall though the CEC will increase.
- Enhance water storage capacity: Depends on the interaction with the texture: beneficial effect for coarse textures but very neutral to negative effect for finer textures (see article in documents).

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

1	Biocarbon
2	vegetal coal
3	Biomass of vegetal origin
4	
5	

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

32 - Biochar in cascade use

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The combined and subsequent use of biochar in animal husbandry and as fertilizer component or soil amendment in plant production. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The combined and subsequent use of biochar in animal husbandry and as fertilizer component or soil amendment in plant production.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

32 – Biochar in cascade use

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

None known

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

None known

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

A review of meta-studies by Schmidt et al. 2021 found positive effects on soils for all reviewed parameters, except for CH₄ emissions from soils (see figure). However, there is substantial evidence that CH₄ emissions in animal husbandry can be reduced by biochar application in silage, feedstuff or stable bedding. In any case, no full cascade greenhouse gas emission study was found and reviewed by Schmidt et al., (2019).

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

—

1

2

3

4

5

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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

33 - Biofertilizers

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A broad term used for products containing living or dormant micro-organisms such as bacteria, fungi, actinomycetes and algae, alone or in combination. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Singh et al (in Rakshit et al. 2021) describe different types of biofertilizers:

- Nitrogen-fixing biofertilizers (NFB)
- Phosphate-solubilizing biofertilizer (PSB): bacterial genera such as *Bacillus* and *Pseudomonas* and fungi such as *Penicillium* and *Aspergillus*
- Phosphate-mobilizing biofertilizers (PMB): arbuscular mycorrhiza (AM)
- Plant growth-promoting biofertilizer (PGPB): rhizobacteria (e.g. *Pseudomonas*, *Burkholderia*, *Azospirillum*, *Arthrobacter*, *Azotobacter*, *Klebsiella*, *Serratia*, *Alcaligenes*, *Bacillus*, and *Enterobacter*)
- Potassium-solubilizing and mobilizing biofertilizer
- Sulfur-oxidizing biofertilizer
- Zn solubilizer

- Iron uptake biofertilizers

The authors describe the advantages of biofertilizers (e.g. alive microorganism that can be applied directly to the soil also in organic farming systems or the biological control of plant pathogens), the mode of action (e.g. N fixation, P, K solubilisation, mobilisation), the advantages of liquid vs. carrier-based biofertilizers and the application of biofertilizers (seed treatment, root dipping, soil treatment).

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

33 – Use of biofertilizers

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Also soil microbial community, pH may limit the application.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Adverse Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Unknown Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

For some products the soil should not be too dry or cold

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

1	Effective microorganisms (EM)
2	
3	
4	
5	

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

34 - Cover crop grazing

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The grazing of animals on Cover crops. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

It is the grazing of a plant cover but this cover is a service crop.

In Wallonia (Belgium), CIPAN (intermediate nitrate trap crop) is required by law (cf. Nitrates Directive), so when we talk about grazing CIPAN we are talking about opportunistic grazing, in the sense that we are taking advantage of an obligatory cover crop that has not been valorised until now as anything other than green manure.

Similarly in France and Germany, cover crop grazing is mainly developed with sheep, but it can be done with other animals (poultry, cattle, etc.). The choice of grazing animals depends, among other things, strongly on the pedoclimatic conditions of the site: the soil tends to have a low bearing capacity in winter (which is the intermediate crop season), with much humidity and sometimes even rain. In such conditions heavy animals like cattle risk to alter the structure of the grazed soil, but with sheep there is no complication regarding this issue whatsoever.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

34 – Cover crop grazing

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

- The winter season has to be good enough to grow something, but not good enough to grow a main crop. So it's a practice that's really adapted specifically to temperate regions. Because in the Mediterranean region, as in some places in southern Europe for example, the winter season allows for valuable crops to be grown, so there's no point in putting in an intermediate crop in that case.
- Moreover, even in the temperate regions of Europe, there are conditions of application. The winter season must not be too cold (i.e., it must not freeze too quickly and too early, otherwise nothing grows), nor too short (between the time when the intermediate crop is sown and the time when the crop is grazed, there must be at least a one and a half to two months span, otherwise the cover crop would grow too little biomass and there would be no point in grazing). So in Wallonia, and in general also in the northern half of Western Europe, the intermediate crop can be sown at the latest in early September because then it will be able to grow throughout all October without any problem. And once the intermediate crop has been installed and grown, there are no more constraints as far as grazing is concerned. But in Northern Europe, for example, nothing will grow in October.
- Rainfall: the practice is complicated to implement if there is a drought at the end of the summer (again, because this is the time when the intermediate crops are planted). Indeed, rainfall is needed in late August/early September for the intercrops to grow after sowing. This is a problem in central France, for example, but not in Wallonia, as most years there is a lot of rain at this time.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	
gently sloping (2-5%)	
sloping (5-10%)	
strongly sloping (10-15%)	
moderately steep (15-30%)	
steep (30-60%)	
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment : A report from England says that grazing is not compatible with peatland generation, since "peat formation requires that rates of deposition of organic material exceeds rates of decomposition and mineralisation of this material in a given area"; and "therefore to maximize peat formation, vegetation should not be removed by cutting (harvesting) or grazing".

This report continues by suggesting scenarios about summer grazing being the best way to maintain peatlands, while cultivating a something near them. So at first sight this practice is not compatible with the sustainable management of peatlands since summer is not the intercrop season.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

A soil that retains a lot of water will be problematic in case of high humidity condition: on the one hand because the animals will be forced to walk in water and if their feet are wet all the time it can cause lameness and infections, on the other hand because the structure of the soil will be degraded if it is trampled all the time while being wet all the time.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	No
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	No
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	No
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes

Large-scale corporate farming	Yes
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Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	No Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Adverse Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Unknown Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

We might have to play on the mixture of species that we sow for the intermediate cover in order to have species adapted to the soil specificities. But this is not limiting in any regards. It is important to keep in mind though that some cover plants may be toxic for some animals.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

16 (DLU1) :

- 2.1.2 : maybe yes, irrigation of the land doesn't prevent the practice to be applied, but its just a priori.
- 2.2.1/ 2.2.2/ 2.2.3 : We do not put intercrops in vineyards or in fruit tree plantations. However in general, it is possible to graze animals in orchards, but then this would be inter-row grazing. The latter practice is totally distinct from, and irreconcilable with, cover crop grazing, since one is a question of spatial succession of crops while the other is a question of temporal succession.
- 2.3/ 3.2.1 : because pastures are not turned-over in order to plant intercrops.
- 2.4/ 2.4.1 : because intercrops are exclusively grown between two annual crops.

17 (DFS1) :

There is a greater influence of the cultivated crops than the type of agriculture. From the rest, cover crop grazing would be more an intensive-type practice than extensive because its a way of using better the same surface.

18 (DFS2) :

Agrosilvopastoral : Yes only if there is an annual crop in the cultural system.

Terrace Farming : Yes only if it is an annual crop.

- General comments about potential application of the practice :

The practice is interesting for systems that either are in polyculture-livestock, or ones that can make partnerships - as it is pragmatically practiced in Wallonia and France and Germany since 3 or 4 years (i.e when one livestock farmer cooperates with one cropfarmer, it is a mutually benefiting partnership because there is less costs in bergerie fees for one farmer and it represents less work by the fact of avoiding to have to destroy itself the intercrop for the other one).

Its also particularly useful for organic farming and conservation agricultures systems, because it allows to reduce the passage of machines and allows to reduce external inputs (via added fertility naturally brought by the grazing animals).

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

- Maintain/Increase SOC : with or without grazing, the intercrop in itself is in favor of soil organic carbon.
- Avoiding N₂O, CH₄ emissions from soils : The answer is mixed. To some extent, the practice reduces soil emissions, because there will be much less need for chemical fertilizers, but on the other hand, ammonia is released from the animal's excrement, not to mention that the animal itself emits methane. It is therefore difficult to make a judgement if we look at the complete balance of the animal and soil system.

On the other hand, a French study (see in document references) has shown that if we look at the complete system (and not only the soil), i.e., including all that is saved in the barn with the practice (i.e., not having to feed the animal in the barn, not having to store the manure in the barn and not having to transport the manure to the field), then the practice improves the farm's carbon balance.

- Avoiding soil erosion : There may be a little negligible adverse effect: compared to an intercrop not grazed (and so that is then destroyed right before the next crop), we could argue on the point of the early destruction of the cover by the animal shaving it, however even if the cover is shaved the soil is not for all that naked because the roots are still there and keep the soil together.
- Avoiding contamination : Less anti-slug and less herbicide input when sheeps are used.
- Optimal soil structure : The interculture will aerate the soil well, especially if we mix different species there is a very positive effect on the soil structure but the sheep on the other hand damage the first 5 centimeters.
- Enhance soil biodiversity : Sheep droppings activate soil microorganisms.
- Enhance soil nutrient retention or use efficiency / Enhance water storage capacity / Avoid Peat degradation : No data.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

- 1 intercropping
 - 2 vegetal cover
 - 3
 - 4 Catch crop
 - 5 Intermediate nitrate trap crop (in French also known as CIPAN - Culture Intermédiaire Piège à Nitrate)
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

35 - Inorganic fertilizers

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Application of natural or man-made substances lacking carbon as a soil amendment. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

/

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

35 – Inorganic fertilizers

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

- 1- application during ideal growing conditions (warm, moist soil) with light rain for mobilisation/movement.
- 2- avoid strong rain right after application
- 3- less effective/efficient under hot, dry conditions

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Uncertain
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

- 1- Supply/soil content must be taken into account; crop demand; national/regional fertiliser recommendations should be taken into account.
- 2- Amounts should be adjusted in accordance with the expected crop yields and soil properties (e.g. texture, stone content, rooting depth, water holding capacity).

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	No
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Adverse Effect
Avoid acidification	Adverse Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Adverse Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Adverse Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	No Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

For instance, in Austria mineral fertilisers are used when organic fertilisers are not available or not available in sufficient quantities. This depends mainly on the type of production. If e.g., livestock farming, which is the main production type in the western provinces and no longer conducted in the east of Austria (except for riding horses) and organic farming are practised, mineral fertilisation is used less or not at all. Only selected inorganic fertilizers can be used in organic farming.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Tiefenbacher et al. (2021) reported that 2 mechanisms might play a role for the - controversially discussed - effects of N fertilisation on SOC. On the one hand increased mineral N fertilisation can lead to higher SOC by enhancing above and belowground biomass. On the other hand N fertilisation may fuel the mineralisation of plant litter and soil organic matter and, thus, decrease SOC. The average carbon sequestration potential of mineral N fertilization in agricultural topsoils (0-10/30 cm) was summarised with ---20 to +210 kg C ha⁻¹ y⁻¹. Mineral N fertilisation is connected with enhanced N₂O emissions during the production process and the fertiliser application. Soil acidification occurs with the application of acidic fertilisers, e.g. sulphuric acid ammonia, ammonium sulphate nitrate, ammonium phosphate.

Mineral P fertilisation is a source of trace elements leading to -- possibly adverse -- enrichments in soils and plants (Spiegel et al., 2019). For instance, Cd and U are derived from super phosphate, Cr and V from Thomasphosphate (which is not produced any more).

Enrichment Effects depend on the source of mineral P fertilisers and their concentrations of trace elements, the fertiliser amounts applied and the duration of the fertilisation measures.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 mineral fertilizer
 - 2 chemical fertilizer
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

36 - In-row fertilizer application

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

With in-row fertilizer application, nutrients are applied close to the crop roots, aiming at a higher nutrient use efficiency, reducing losses and higher crop yields. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

With in-row fertilizer application, nutrients are applied close to the crop roots, aiming at a higher nutrient use efficiency, reducing losses and higher crop yields.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

36 – In-row fertilizer application

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

It might be more difficult to find the right moment to apply fertilizer taking into account the risk for soil compaction.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

No

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	No
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	No Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	No Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

The effect of in-row fertilizer application (compared to full-field application) is expected to be larger in case of low (soil) temperatures in spring, and in cases of a suboptimal soil structure.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

Limitations for in-row fertilizer application are not different than for the conventional full-field application.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

In-row artificial fertilizer application is common in the cultivation of maize in the Netherlands.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Place-specific fertilizer application
 - 2 Combined sowing
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

37 - Liming

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Applying neutralizing agents, such as limestone, basic slag, hydrated lime, or quick lime, to soil or water for the purpose of increasing its basicity (pH and alkalinity). (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Applying neutralizing agents, such as limestone, basic slag, hydrated lime, or quick lime, to soil or water for the purpose of increasing its basicity (pH). Liming is considered to provide optimum conditions for growth of many temperate crop species.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

37 – Liming

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Climatic factors do not limit the application of liming

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment : Liming of organic soils leads to increased mineralization and peat degradation (Paradelo et al., 2015).

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

SOM > 10% (organic soils), neutral pH, calcareous soils

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Adverse Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

Liming is not necessary in soils that are calcareous by nature and/or have neutral pH. Liming of organic soils leads to increased mineralization and peat degradation (Paradelo et al., 2015). Applying lime in steep terrain can be limited by technical feasibility.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Some soil amendments are prohibited in organic agriculture. Furthermore, legislation may prohibit lime application in some areas or land-uses (e.g. natural grasslands, wetlands)

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Liming is a well-established practice and many of its short- and long-term effects are the subject of scientific reviews (e.g. Haynes & Naidu, 1998; Holland et al., 2019; Paradelo et al., 2015) or farmer's literature (e.g. Schmidt, 2016; Galler, 2013). Holland et al., 2019 summarize the diverse effects of liming as followed: ``For instance, short-term liming impacts are detected on soil biota and in soil biological processes (such as in N cycling where liming can increase N availability for plant uptake). [...] Liming influences all elements in soils and as such there are numerous simultaneous changes to soil processes which in turn affect the plant nutrient uptake; examples of positive impact for crops are [...] decreased uptake of toxic heavy metals.'' However, liming can also lead to lower nutrient availability. For example, alkaline pH induced by liming may favour the precipitation of calcium phosphate and thus lower the availability of P to plants.

Past (Haynes & Naidu, 1998) and recent studies (e.g. Blomquist et al., 2018; Aviles et al., 2020, Bölscher et al., 2021) on the physical effects of liming found that aggregate stability increased and dispersability decreased. However, the effects on the pore networks differed substantially between investigated sites.

The effect of liming on GHG emissions and soil carbon storage are still under investigation (Paradelo et al., 2015; Kunhikrishnan et al., 2016). The reviewed literature suggests, that

liming decreases N₂O emissions and increases CH₄ oxidation. Furthermore the net long-term effect of liming on SOC sequestration in mineral soils is very likely to be positive. The positive effect may be explained by higher C inputs due to higher productivity.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

38 - Liming (gypsum)

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Spreading of gypsum to minimize soil erosion and the losses of phosphorus bound to soil and dissolved phosphorus from field to surface water as well as to improve the soil structure. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Spreading of gypsum to minimize soil erosion and the losses of phosphorus bound to soil and dissolved phosphorus from field to surface water as well as to improve the soil structure.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

38 – Liming (gypsum)

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The best spreading time is during autumn just before tillage. The soil should be dry during spreading and it should not rain before tilling the gypsum into the soil.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment : It is suitable for clay soils but there is not information available on organic soils.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The soil properties do not limit the application of gypsum. However, the soil must be dry enough to decrease compaction of soil during spreading and to allow soil tillage after gypsum spreading.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	No
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Uncertain
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 gypsum
 - 2 gips
 - 3 kipsi
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

39 - Low emission slurry spreading

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Low emission slurry spreading is a technique used to increase the amount of nutrient available and reduce the loss of nutrients to air or water. There are several different methods used for this practice, each has specific equipment.

(Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Low emission slurry spreading is a technique used to increase the amount of nutrient available and reduce the loss of nutrients to air or water. There are several different methods used for this practice each has specific equipment.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

39 – Low emission slurry spreading

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Precipitation

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The soil water content is critical for LESS methods. Therefore, the following soil properties are important: water holding capacity, ground water level, frequent water logging

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	No
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	No

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

Excessive rainfall could limit the effectiveness of low emission slurry spreading.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

There is a need for further research to fully determine the potential area of low emission slurry spreading.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

There is a lack of evidence for most of the soil challenges which have been listed. therefore, it is difficult to be sure about the effects in every case.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 LESS
 - 2 trailing shoe
 - 3 trailing hose

-
- 4 shallow injection
 - 5 splash plate
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

40 - Mulching

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A protective covering, usually of organic matter such as leaves, straw, or peat, placed around plants. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

/

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

40 – Mulching

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	NA
gently sloping (2-5%)	NA
sloping (5-10%)	NA
strongly sloping (10-15%)	NA
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

NA -- comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	NA
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	NA
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	NA
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	NA
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	NA
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	NA
Large-scale corporate farming	NA

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	NA
Conservation Agriculture	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

No data

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

1	NA
2	NA
3	NA
4	NA
5	NA

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

41 - Mulching (roller crimper)

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The Roller crimper technique was developed by the Rodale Institute (Pennsylvania, USA) and is used to terminate a cover crop (mixture) in its generative, flowering phase. The roller crimper pushes the plants down and lightly crushes their stems, leaving a dead mulch layer on top of the soil. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The Roller crimper technique was developed by the Rodale Institute (Pennsylvania, USA) and is used to terminate a cover crop (mixture) in its generative, flowering phase. The roller crimper pushes the plants down and lightly crushes their stems, leaving a dead mulch layer on top of the soil.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

41 – Mulching (roller crimper)

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

During dry summers there might be insufficient biomass production from the cover crop to get a mulch layer that is sufficiently weed suppressing.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

Less productive soil might be a problem when these do not allow for enough biomass production of the cover crop.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

A roller crimper can be applied in certain terrace farms on the condition that the area of the terraces is large enough.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

42 - Organic fertilizers and amendments

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Application of carbon-rich fertilizer derived from organic materials, including treated or untreated livestock manures, compost, vermicompost, sewage sludge and other organic materials or mixed materials used to supply nutrients to soils. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The description of this practice includes the specification 'to supply nutrients to the soil'. Biochar does not necessarily add nutrients to the soil and is included as a separate measure. For these reasons, biochar is not considered. The focus is on (processed) animal manure, sewage sludge and compost.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

42 – Organic fertilizers

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Growing season and temperature are the two most important climate limiting factors to be considered when organic fertilization are used.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment : P2 - WR (The Netherlands) clarified that adding nutrients to the soil affects the decomposition of peat in various ways. Applying organic matter can both stimulate or inhibit peat decomposition, depending on various aspects, such as the soil N availability (Agtmaal et al., 2018).

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

No other soil properties are considering as limiting factors.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Uncertain

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

I1 - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

In this context, P2 - WR (The Netherlands) clarified that for limiting climatic factors the following solutions can be adopted:

1- Growing season: Applying readily available nutrients to the soil at times when nutrients are not required by an actively growing crop risks the loss of a substantial proportion of the applied fertilizer to the water or air. This generally means avoiding applications during the autumn/winter period when losses by leaching are the greatest across most of Europe (Misselbrook et al., 2019). Nutrient availability of organic substances is difficult to forecast, which makes it difficult select the right moment of application to match nutrient availability with crop requirements.

2- Temperature: low temperatures reduce the rate of mineralization of organic matter because of lowered microbial activity, lowering the nutrient provision of organic fertilizers. Hot dry conditions may lead to losses via ammonia volatilization (Misselbrook et al., 2019).

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

In this context, P2 - WR (The Netherlands) added the following explanation and suggestions: Dutch farmers usually apply a combination of artificial fertilizers and manure (70% and 50% of N originate from manure for dairy and arable farms respectively). 70% of the domestic produced manure is annually applied on agricultural fields in the Netherlands (360Mton N/year).

Composting and applying compost has gained interest in the last few years, partly because discharging crop residues is becoming more expensive. Fertilizer restrictions are becoming more strict, limiting the possibility to apply sufficient amounts of organic matter via manure, making compost a suitable alternative (e.g. pig slurry contains 45gOM/kg while compost contains 200gOM/kg). At the moment +/- 1.5Mton compost is applied on agricultural fields. Apart from manure, only 1-10% of applied N originates from organic fertilizers for dairy and arable farms respectively.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

In this context, P2 - WR (The Netherlands) clarified that positive and negative effects (only when supported by literature) are observed in the following cases:

Positive effects:

Carbon sequestration:

- Applying 1 Mg/ha.year of carbon by means of compost results in a carbon sequestration of 0,26 Mg C/ha.year. Applying 1 Mg/ha.year of carbon by means of farmyard manure results in a carbon sequestration of 0,20 Mg C/ha.year. After 4-7 years of repeated farm compost application the soil organic C content had increased significantly (+ 13-17%) in respect to the unamended plots .
- The use of organic manure fertilizers has been shown to increase soil C and crop yields compared to mineral fertilizer use alone .
- Modelling the effects of applying manure (38m³/ha) or manure+compost (16-29m³/ha+6-20t/ha) shows that the SOM slightly decreases when applying manure annually while the SOM increases when applying a combination .
- Implementation of biochar to the soil decreased CO₂ emissions and increased soil carbon content (7%) .
- Soil organic content increases significantly under urban sludge amendment, representing an improvement of 30% in relation with the initial SOC in a corn field in Portugal (Ferreira and Boulet, n.d.).

Acidity:

- The repeated application of farm compost led to higher pH-KCl (+ 0.10 - 0.42 pH units) compared to the unamended plots².
- The application of farmyard manure resulted in a small (not significant) pH increase, by which the effect was more pronounced after repeated farmyard manure applications (> 5 year). Compared to mineral fertilization, the application of cattle slurry increased soil pH (Mallast et al., 2014).

- Applying urban sludge amendment resulted in a higher soil pH (pH between 6 and 7) than for the control (from 5.0 to 5.5) (Ferreira and Boulet, n.d.).

Soil structure:

- Besides an improvement of aggregate stability, the addition of farm compost reduced bulk density in the top layer (on average -0.02 g cm^{-3})².
- Morphological analysis of the crop profiles showed greater compaction under mineral fertilization than under organic amendment, resulting in a higher proportion of compacted clods in the middle layer of the profile. This has consequences on water transfers, with hydraulic conductivity six to seven times higher under organic amendment than with mineral fertilisation. These structural modifications can be attributed to the role of the earthworm macrofauna, whose abundance and biomass are strongly favoured by organic inputs .
- A 1% increase of SOM increases plant-available water by 0.6 mm⁴.
- Farmyard manure application increased aggregate stability in the top soil (<10 cm). The positive effect was mainly observed in loamy soils. However, more data are needed to confirm these findings (findings are mainly based on data from long-term field experiments in the Atlantic climatic zone) (Mallast et al., 2014). Farmyard manure application significantly reduced bulk density. However, more data are needed to confirm these findings (Mallast et al., 2014). Farmyard manure application significantly reduced penetration resistance. However, more data are needed to confirm these findings (findings are mainly based on data from long-term field experiments in the Atlantic climatic zone) (Mallast et al., 2014).

Soil fertility:

- The most salient effect of organic fertilizer amendments is the enhancement of nutrients and SOC. Compost is valuable due to high content of humified organic matter. Elevated SOM content affects soil structure by increasing aggregate stability, available water capacity and water infiltration. Soil N contents were reported significantly higher with compost amendments than with mineral fertilisation and to increase N supplying capacity. Some compost types (sewage sludge c., manure c.) significantly increase P and K in the soil .
- Compost application was also accompanied by a significantly higher ammonium lactate extractable P and K content compared to the unamended plots².
- Improves soil fertility through nutrient content and availability, soil structure and microbiological activity; impacts plant growth and health directly and indirectly (Barão et al., 2019).
- Applying urban sludge amendment in a corn field in Portugal consistently resulted in much higher levels of macro nutrients as Total Nitrogen, Available Phosphorus and available potassium than for the control with mineral fertilizer amendment (Ferreira and Boulet, n.d.).

Soil biodiversity:

- Regular compost amendment increases biotic activity, microbial biomass and earthworm abundance, which enhances mineralization of organic matter and resistance against pests and diseases. Compost-mineral fertilizers increase earthworm activity⁷.
- The addition of compost has led to an increase in the abundance of soil macrofauna, regardless of the type of waste composted. Thus, for an average density of 191 (± 126) ind.m⁻² found in soil with no amendment, increasing density values were observed for the different treatments: 251 (± 201) ind.m⁻² for soil with green waste and sewage plant sludge and 425 (± 371) ind.m⁻² for soil with cattle manure .
- The repeated application of farmyard manure clearly enhanced bacterial soil life. Application of organic amendments to the soil is expected to increase the bacterial population as was the case in our field trials when compost was applied. Compared to e.g. farmyard manure, the effect was less pronounced though. The observed trends can partly be linked with the quality or decomposability of the applied amendments. Compost with a usually higher carbon to nitrogen (C:N) ratio contains more recalcitrant compounds, remaining after the composting process over several months, which are mainly decomposed by fungi, while readily decomposable compounds such as organic acids and carbohydrates present in farmyard manure with a lower C:N ratio are preferentially utilized by soil bacteria (Mallast et al., 2014).
- There were 4 times more earthworms present under urban sludge amendment than under mineral fertilizer amendment in corn fields in Portugal (Ferreira and Boulet, n.d.).

Nutrient use efficiency:

- Application of poultry manure reduced the Nitrate leaching from in water cycle from 14.4 kg/ha to 1.4 kg/ha compared with mineral fertilizer .
- A meta-analysis of compliant reviewed experiments revealed significantly lower N₂O emissions for organic as opposed to synthetic fertilizers (23% reduction). When organic materials were segregated in solid and liquid, only solid organic fertilizer emissions were significantly lower than those of synthetic fertilizers (28% reduction in cumulative emissions) .
- Application of wood chips led to temporary N immobilisation (high C/N-ratio), in autumn it led to decreased risk of nitrate leaching during winter; in spring it led to less crop available N (Tits & Elsen, n.d.).

Yield:

- Experiments indicate a yield increase of 7-10% when applying a combination of manure and compost .

Soil erosion:

- The application of organic manure is considered to reduce negative effects of winderosion (Paauw et al., 2012; Selin Norén et al., 2021).

Peat degradation:

- Adding nutrients to the soil affects the decomposition of peat in various ways. Applying organic matter can both stimulate or inhibit peat decomposition, depending on various aspects, such as the soil N availability (Agtmaal et al., 2018).

Negative effects (only when supported by literature)

Nutrient use efficiency:

- In the dry regions of the Pannonian climate (Austria), the risk of nutrient leaching into the groundwater is increased. Nutrients are not diluted when they are leached into the groundwater .
- Organic fertilizers can cause increased CO₂ and N₂O emissions compared to mineral fertilizers .
- Organic fertilisers may contribute in increasing greenhouse gas emissions. For example, Escuer-Gatius et al. (2020) proved that high-temperature hay biochar application into soil increases N₂O fluxes .
- The fertilizer value can range for different organic fertilizers. Thus it can be difficult to use efficiently. The efficient use of organic fertilizer can be a challenge in relation to obtain the yield potential, and may lead to increased N leaching due to more difficult synchronisation as compared to mineral fertilizer .
- Animal manures pose a risk of nutrient loss to adjacent waterways following application. In the UK there are management restrictions and regulations to ensure best practice is adhered to in terms of manure use, such as application distance from water courses, nutrient loading (N&P) and weather conditions at time of application. Animal manures also contribute to gaseous emissions of nitrous oxide, methane and ammonia. The physiochemical characteristics of biochar are influenced by feedstock type, production method and temperature. Therefore, characterisation and matching specific types to suit their purpose is essential for a positive outcome. Organic fertilizers such as farmyard manures are very variable in their composition and nutrient content, which can cause issues where specific nutrient ratios are required .
- Our study indicated an increase in N₂O emissions after compost application. Compost application resulted in increased N₂O emissions in the Atlantic central climatic zone and in lower emissions in the Mediterranean region (Mallast et al., 2014). In our study, N₂O emissions slightly decreased after the application of farmyard manure compared to mineral fertilizer alone. Further, the N₂O emissions tended to increase with higher clay contents, probably due to higher risk for soil compaction, thus generating anaerobic conditions leading

to higher denitrification rates (Mallast et al., 2014). N₂O emissions were more than 5-fold following cattle slurry application compared to mineral fertilization but more data is needed to confirm these findings (Mallast et al., 2014).

Contamination:

- The application of composts could be accompanied by potential hazards to soil and humans, caused by heavy metals and organic persistent pollutants. Sewage sludge composts contained the highest amounts of nitrogen (2.98%), phosphorus (4.44%) and organic matter (47.6%), and the highest potassium content (1.20%) was found in mixed municipal composts after mechanical-biological treatment. After having tested all the composts, green waste composts had the lowest content of the following nutrients: nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and sulphur. High molecular weight PAHs dominated in green waste, sewage sludge and mixed municipal waste composts, and the opposite tendency was observed on mixed municipal waste composts after mechanical-biological treatment; low molecular weight PAHs were abundant .
- Concentrations of heavy metals in soil are slightly higher under urban sludge amendment for copper and chromium, and with a major dispersion of the result in term of interquartile value. Nevertheless differences are not significant and the levels of heavy metal concentration maintains always very distant from the limits imposed by the law (Ferreira & Boulet, n.d.).

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Farmyard manure
 - 2 Compost
 - 3 Animal manure
 - 4 Slurry Digestate
 - 5 Sewage sludge
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

43 - Variable rate fertilizer application

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Variable rate fertilizer application allows crop producers to apply different rates of fertilizer at each location across fields. (Source of definition: <https://www.ag.ndsu.edu/agmachinery/precisionagriculture/variable-rate-technology>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

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CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

43 – Variable rate fertilizer application

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Climatic factors are not limiting

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

In agricultural soils there are no limiting factors

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	No Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	Beneficial Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

1	variable rate nitrogen fertilization based on remote sensing
2	
3	
4	
5	

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

44 - Drainage systems, water table management and flooding

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Process of directing excess water to or away from root zones by natural or artificial means. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Improved drainage of agricultural soils with excess water can improve plant growth conditions, increase yields and reduce emissions. The measure can also reduce compaction as saturated soils are more likely to compact during field operations. Drainage can be carried out by installing subsurface permeable pipes in the ground that will contribute to transport soil water quicker in poorly drained lands. Surface ditching is another way of removing water from the soil surface and avoid flooding when the rainfall rate exceeds the infiltration capacity.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

44 – Drainage systems, water table management and flooding
i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

The importance of the practice is increasing with climatic changes and increased precipitation. Improved drainage can improve plant growth conditions and yields while reducing flooding, erosion rates, nutrient losses and GHG emissions. A limit is, however, that the practice can contribute to increasing flood peaks during large precipitation events as water is transported more rapidly downstream.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment : Drainage of organic soils is resulting in emissions of the greenhouse gasses carbon dioxide (CO₂) and nitrous dioxide (N₂O) to the atmosphere. Organic soils are characterised by very high levels of organic matter.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The practice is limited by soil texture and has the highest cost-effect on fine and less permeable soils like clay/silt, while it is less applicable on coarser soils such as sandy soils.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	No
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes

2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	No

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	No Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect

Enhance soil biodiversity	No Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	No Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Drainage is suitable in agricultural systems situated on relatively flat or leveled land of poor natural drainage to prevent water logging.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Lower soil saturation can decrease N₂O emissions and compaction risk. Increasing the water infiltration capacity of the soil can also contribute to reduce surface runoff rates, hence avoiding soil erosion. Reducing soil erosion will also reduce nutrient losses, but mainly by P. N leaching can under certain soil conditions increase with drainage.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

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- 1 Drenering
 - 2 Drenerings system
 - 3
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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

45 - Drip irrigation

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A form of irrigation which applies water to the root zone through tubes/tapes either above or below the soil surface.

(Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

A form of irrigation which applies water to the soil very slowly under low pressure from a system of pipes and outlets (emitters or drips). Most of the time, water is applied close to plants either above or below the soil surface so that only part of the soil in which the roots grow is wet. In this survey, the answers concern this type of device. In some plantings, it is not possible to install irrigation just above or below the surface. For instance, in hop gardens, the drip irrigation system can be installed at height. The orchards also use a system of multiple pipes with a distance to the sides of the trunk, alternating the sides of the watering and supporting a larger wet zone and root zone. In some innovative systems, the amount of water applied by the drip irrigation system is controlled from a monitoring of the water status of the soil by soil sensors.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

45 – Drip irrigation

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

- Precipitations
- Temperatures and length of dry warm period

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment : Classical drip irrigation devices generates very localized wetting: the wetting pattern around the water outlets is of the order of 20 to 50 cm in diameter. This localized irrigation does not humidify the entire soil and therefore limits the biological and organic processes.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

- hydraulic conductivity
- texture : sandy soil
- stone content : stony soil

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Adverse Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Adverse Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	No Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	No Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

- Low precipitations :
 - > During spring: Drip irrigation is not sufficient to raise seedlings in a dry spring. The technique must be then coupled with a sprinkling irrigation.
 - > In dry weather, pipes can be damaged by biting insects in search of water.
- Temperatures and length of dry warm period : the system may be inappropriate in areas subject to extreme heat waves. In case of failure, the system is not resilient for long because part only of the soil is wetted.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

Hydraulic conductivity : a good hydraulic conductivity is required to spread water in soil with a surface drip sytem.

Top soil texture : sandy soils are not suitable for the use of drip irrigation as they do not allow lateral water transfers.

Stone content :

- o The installation of a buried drip irrigation system in stony soil is difficult.
- o In stony soil, it can be difficult to create and maintain a sufficient wet soil volume.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

- Buried drip irrigation is well suited for irrigate trees and facilitating their deep-water supply. The technique can be used at the start of plantations and then must be removed so that the trees act autonomously on water withdrawals because this is their role in an agroforestry system. Drip irrigation does not benefit surface crops in this case.
- Irrigated trees do not resist the wind, practical to adapt to a climatic context not very windy.
- Pastoralism poses a risk of crushing drip irrigation systems.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Generally, drip irrigation has no effect or negative effects on storage issues (water, nutrients, biodiversity, salts) as the practice wets very localized volumes limiting the processes requiring water intake. This is particularly the case in arid areas where there is little or no natural water supply.

Significant drip erosion may occur when drip irrigation system are installed at height.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 drip irrigation
 - 2 trickle irrigation
 - 3 micro irrigation
 - 4 localized irrigation
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

46 - Integrated Constructed Wetland for grey water treatment

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The use of an Integrated Constructed Wetland (ICS) on an intensive dairy farm to primarily treat soiled water, typically removing through flowing organic matter, nitrogen and phosphorus to ensure the protection of receiving waters and flood attenuation. The ICS can provide a number of other ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration and biodiversity. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The use of an Integrated Constructed Wetland (ICS) on an intensive dairy farm to primarily treat soiled water, typically removing through flowing organic matter, nitrogen and phosphorus to ensure the protection of receiving waters and flood attenuation. The ICS can provide a number of other ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration and biodiversity.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

46 – Integrated Constructed Wetland for grey water treatment

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

No

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Uncertain
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Soil texture and depth to rock as water may be lost to groundwater

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	
2.1.3 rice fields	
2.2.1 vineyards	
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	
2.2.3 olive groves	
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	
Avoid acidification	
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	
Avoid salinisation	
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	
Enhance soil biodiversity	
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

If soil is very free draining, a liner can be used instead or a soil type with a higher clay content can be used.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

1 Constructed Wetland

2

3

4

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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

47 - Irrigation scheduling

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The preparation of the irrigation scheduling programme takes into consideration the soil moisture holding capacity, the plant physiology (root depth, growing stages, crop coefficient, etc.) and the climate. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

/

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

47 – Irrigation scheduling

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

There are no climatic factors limit to the application of this practice. Usually some irrigation systems are put in the field only during the crop growing season to not deteriorate the tool during winter period when it's not used.

Where precipitations are good and there are no water stress during summer period, it's not necessary to irrigate.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	No
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

I1 - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Beneficial Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

Irrigation scheduling based on: soil water balance

- Irrinet (developed by the Water User Association (WUA) Canale Emiliano Romagnolo and implemented within the measure 10.1.2 of the Rural Development Programme 2014-2020 Emilia Romagna Region)
- IRRIFRAME (represent the spread out of Irrinet to the whole irrigated areas in Italy, managed by public body (i.e WUA))
- IRRI (Tuscany Region)
- IRRISIAS (Sicily Region)
- IRRINET Sardegna

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 austomatic irrigation
 - 2 irrigation system
 - 3 irrigation suggestion and advice
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

48 - Monitor soil salinisation

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Monitoring the salt content of the soil to avoid soil salinisation. (Source of definition: EJP SOIL)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The provided definition can be implemented by also considering the following improvement: Soil salinity is the accumulation of water-soluble salts in soils to levels that impact negatively crop production and soil functions. Soil salinisation can occur through natural processes as physical or chemical weathering and transport processes from salty geological deposits or groundwater. Secondary salinisation is caused by human interventions such as inappropriate irrigation practices, use of salt-rich irrigation water and/or poor drainage conditions. Arid, semi-arid, and dry sub-humid regions are more prone to soil salinity. The indicators used to assess the salt content of the soil are: soil electrical conductivity of the saturation extract (EC_e), exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP), and sodium adsorption ratio (SAR) in soil samples, apparent soil electrical conductivity (EC_a) with geospatial field measurements.

In EU LUCAS 2022 campaign the parameter of electrical conductivity (EC) and Na is recommended only in regions with salinity problems (predominantly southern EU MS, but also regions with irrigation, where likely saline aquifers are concerned, as well as coastal agricultural plots). LUCAS Soil data is used for studies at national scales, potentially reflecting the lack of operational soil monitoring systems and timely data in many Member States. The release of

new datasets (on salinity, sulphur, plant protection products and soil genetics) will ensure continuous development of applications. In EEA ETC/ULS Report (2021) the soil salinity state is measured by the total salt content (% EC) and exchangeable sodium (pH unit ESP %). In the EU, the ESO will be providing regular reports on the status and trends of EU soil resources and will cover the main threats to soil health considered in the EU Soil Thematic Strategy (Soil erosion, Soil organic matter decline, Soil contamination, Soil sealing, Soil compaction, Soil acidification, Soil salinization, Soil biodiversity loss, Landslides and mass movements).

This practice is to be applied only in places where natural or human-induced conditions justify it, namely primary or secondary salinization processes occur. Tailor made solutions must be provided for minimizing the risks in each case/scenario. The need to monitor soil salinisation it is about the fact that an increase in the concentration of soluble salts in the soil and in soil solution, is harmful to plants, either by specific toxic effects or by the high osmotic potential of the soil solution, which reduces soil water extraction capacity of the plants (Ayers and Westcot, 1985). The accumulated salts include sodium (usually the most important) and Ca, Mg and K salts.

On the other hand if the Na⁺ ion gains preponderance in the soil exchange complex (sodicization), can cause the loss of one or more soil functions. Sodium has a negative effect on soil properties and plant growth, promoting clay expansion and/or dispersion, altering soil pore geometry that, affects soil intrinsic permeability, water retention and crop productivity (Keren, 2000). Sodium dynamics is associated with the dynamics of other cations, namely calcium and magnesium.

Perspectives of climate change for the coming decades, including the increase in temperature and in the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere may also interfere with soil salinization, as the use of water by plants is potentially influenced by high concentrations of CO₂ leading to lower conductance of leaf stomas and an increase in photosynthetic rates (Kirschbaum et al., 1996). Especially in the hotter and drier regions, soil water, associated with dissolved salts existing in the deep layers of the soil, will undergo a greater capillary ascending movement that may result in the accumulation of salts in the superficial layers of the soils.

In the Mediterranean region, land degradation associated with soil salinisation may worsen at increasing rates in the coming decades, owing to the expected increase in irrigated areas and the increasing scarcity of good quality waters, where the emergence of the need for preventive measures (Bowyer et al., 2009). It is estimated that 25% of irrigated cropland in the Mediterranean area is affected by moderate to high salinization leading to moderate soil degradation (Mateo-Sagasta and Burke, 2011). Furthermore, soil salinization is regarded as a driver for desertification, and has a close association with land degradation processes such as arable land abandonment and soil erosion (D'Odorico et al., 2013).

Geophysical methods such as electrical resistivity tomography (ERT) and electromagnetic induction (EMI) techniques are being used as a promising alternative to traditional techniques for soil salinity assessment as it allows to take non-invasive, reliable, rapid and repeatable measurements which can be used to cover large areas in less time and at a smaller cost. These techniques measure the soil apparent electrical conductivity (ECa) which is primarily a function of soil salinity, soil texture, moisture content, and cation exchange capacity. However, in saline soils, ECa is primarily dominated by the spatio-temporal variability of soil salinity. Among geophysical methods, EMI techniques have been used increasingly to estimate soil salinity due to the fast and non-invasive nature of this method. EMI instruments measure the soil apparent electrical conductivity, which represents a weighted integration of the soil electrical conductivity in a soil volume.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

48 – Monitor soil salinisation

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

In general, there are no climatic factors that limit the application of this practice since the several methods used to evaluate soil salinity can be used alternatively. However, there are limitations derived from the applicability context of this practice, for example, in higher temperatures that favour evaporation at the soil surface. Soil salinisation, and the related threat of sodification, occurs mainly in the arid, semi-arid and dry sub-humid regions in Europe where $0.05 < P/ET_0 < 0.65$ (Rubio and Recatalá, 2006). The monitoring results of soil salinisation/sodicisation must be analysed case by case because they depend on various climatic factors including:

- distribution of precipitation - the amount of rain during the autumn-winter period, when dealing with summer crops. If the precipitation that occurs after harvesting periods is enough to wash the salts from the root zone or the soil profile.
- when in irrigated crop production, the calculation of crop evapotranspiration (ET_c) and the adequate irrigation needs are important. Also the irrigation efficiency, since low watering efficiencies are sometimes enough to meet the needs of the salts washing from the root zone. For example, low washing fractions (<10%) are generally supplied by irrigation inefficiency. Also the electrical conductivity of the irrigation water ($EC_w < 1 \text{ dSm}^{-1}$) is necessary to prevent salinisation risks induced by irrigation.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : These soils have completely different soil properties. Bulk density is very low (down to 0.05 g cm^{-3} : Päivänen, 1973; Eggelsmann et al., 1993; Bridgham et al., 2001), organic matter content can reach almost 100% (Päivänen, 1973; Hobbs, 1986) and cation exchange capacity is much higher (up to $200 \text{ cmolc kg}^{-1}$: Puustjärvi, 1956) compared to mineral soils.

There are not many studies on monitoring soil salinity in these soils and attributed to a high CEC there are no major salinity risks. A particular study by Walter et al. (2018) performed geoelectrical surveys to monitor soil salinity referring that most models are calibrated for mineral substrates, and can compensate for additional influences on conductivity, such as field-water content and cation exchange capacity. This is valid for salinities (pore-fluid conductivity) between 0.6 mS cm^{-1} and 12 mS cm^{-1} . Salt dynamics at inland salt meadows is important because groundwater level fluctuations and associated capillary rise are critical for the survival of salt-adapted plants (halophytes). To conserve halophytes, groundwater levels may need to be adjusted so that capillary rise is still large enough to provide the rooting zone with salts.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

In general, there are no soil properties that hampers the application of this practice since there are several methods available to evaluate soil salinity. For example, in soils with frequent water logging, there might be limitations on the use of electromagnetic induction (EMI) techniques, since the dominant factor will be soil moisture content and interfere with the capacity to evaluate soil salinity. In such cases, soil sampling must be performed although, more expensive and time-consuming. The main soil properties that limit the use of this practice derived from the applicability context of this practice and the monitoring results of soil salinisation/sodicization must be analysed case by case because they depend on various factors including:

- Shallow water table (e.g., $< 2 \text{ m}$), particularly in arid and semi-arid environments, evaporation at the soil surface (and transpiration from plants) acts as a driver in combination with the adhesive and cohesive forces of capillary rise to draw water upward to the soil surface. Salts in the water are then deposited as the water evaporates causing salts to accumulate at the soil surface.
- the type and properties of soil (e.g. medium to fine textures with low hydraulic conductivity - $K_{\text{sat}} < 1 \text{ cmh}^{-1}$ (Weil and Brady, 2017) and $\text{pH} \approx 8.5$);
- soil salinity given by the indicators (according to Weil and Brady, 2017): (1) EC_{e} , is regarded as standard and is measured in the soil saturation paste extract ($\text{EC}_{\text{e}} > 4 \text{ dSm}^{-1}$, for simplification reasons, soil solution extracts of higher soil:water ratios can be used, as long as there is an established correlation with EC_{e}), (2) sodium adsorption ratio (SAR) gives a comparative concentrations of Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} in soil solutions ($\text{SAR} > 13 \text{ dSm}^{-1}$), (3) exchangeable sodium percentage (ESP) identifies the degree to which the exchange complex is saturated with sodium ($\text{ESP} > 15 \text{ dSm}^{-1}$).
- soil salinity given by the EMI field methods, measures the soil apparent electrical conductivity (EC_{a} , dS m^{-1}), which represents a weighted integration of the soil EC in a volume of soil ("bulk soil EC"). Using modelling procedures, EC_{a} data can be used to

provide a volume specific distribution of the soil bulk electrical conductivity (in mS m^{-1}). A calibration between and electrical conductivity measured in the saturated soil paste extract (ECe , dS m^{-1}) is needed.

- Several critical values for field-water contents for geoelectrical salinity monitoring are reported: achievable in 45--80% in peat and 20--75% in sand substrates (Rhoades et al., 1999, McKenzie et al., 1989), 70% of field capacity (McKenzie et al., 1989).
- the resistance of each crop to the salinity of the soil and irrigation water. Tables with crop resistance to salinity of either soil or irrigation water can be found at Ayers and Westcot (1985);

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes

Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

I1 - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	No Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	Beneficial Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

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1
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4
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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

49 - Monitor the quality of irrigation water

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Monitoring the quality of the irrigation water to avoid soil contamination and salinisation
(Source of definition: EJP SOIL)

Specificities or other description of the practice

/

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

49 – Monitor the quality of irrigation water

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

/

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	NA
gently sloping (2-5%)	NA
sloping (5-10%)	NA
strongly sloping (10-15%)	NA
moderately steep (15-30%)	NA
steep (30-60%)	NA
very steep (>60%)	NA

Management of organic soils/peatlands

NA -- comment : NA

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

/

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	NA
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	NA
2.1.3 rice fields	NA
2.2.1 vineyards	NA
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	NA
2.2.3 olive groves	NA
2.3 Pastures	NA
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	NA
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	NA

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	NA
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	NA
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	NA
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	NA
Large-scale corporate farming	NA

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	NA
Conservation Agriculture	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	NA
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	NA
Terrace Farming	NA

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

No data

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

1	NA
2	NA
3	NA
4	NA
5	NA

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

50 - Paludiculture

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Paludiculture is the productive use of wet peatlands. It includes traditional peatland cultivation (reed mowing, litter usage) and new approaches for utilization, for example the energetic use of biomass of wet peatlands.

(Source of definition: <https://mowi.botanik.uni-greifswald.de/en/paludikultur/paludikultur.php>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Paludiculture is the productive use of re-wetted peatlands formerly under agriculture or forestry as paludiculture should not take place on pristine mire or on peatlands re-wetted for nature conservation. At present, paludiculture crops on bog peat mainly comprise Sphagnum (peat moss) as horticultural substrate. On fen peat, besides energetic use, biomass might be used as construction material (e.g. Phragmites for roof thatching, Typha spp. for insulation material, Alnus glutinosa for timber).

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

50 – Paludiculture

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Precipitation + groundwater inflow + surface water inflow > evapotranspiration + lateral and vertical losses

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	No
strongly sloping (10-15%)	No
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : The practice is specifically for organic soils only.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Groundwater level > 10 cm below soil surface

Sphagnum farming: Soil = bog peat

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	No
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	No
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

The climate and the hydrogeological setting should generally allow for peat forming conditions, i.e. a surplus of water. Depending on the specific site conditions, additional water might be needed. Besides soil properties (bog peat vs. fen peat), the nutrient supply by surface and groundwater is decisive for the choice of appropriate crops.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

High water levels, i.e. near the soil surface, are required to protect the peat from mineralisation and to allow for optimum growth of paludiculture crops.

Sphagnum farming should take place under nutrient-poor conditions, while fen species might grow under a range of nutrient levels. Nutrient supply by peat and water will determine yields.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Linked to the potential area of application of the practice (17 and 18):

In most cases besides wet grasslands and traditional reed cutting, the implementation of paludiculture does encompass a change of the farming system and the produce. Therefore, the area of application does not depend on a specific farming system, but on the occurrence of organic soils and factors such as the share of organic soils in the agricultural area of a specific farm, the number of farms in a water management unit as well as the feasibility and costs of water management.

There are so far no defined practices for paludiculture in organic or conservation farming, but there should be no principle problems as, for example, the application of fertilizers and pesticides on water saturated soils is anyway forbidden. If terrace farming is conducted similarly as for paddy rice paludiculture could look very similar.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Paludiculture intends to preserve the peat, avoid peat degradation and thus reduce CO₂ emissions, which works well when the water level is kept close to the soil surface. In this case, nitrous

oxide emissions can be avoided. On the other hand, methane emissions might be increased. This does not seem to be a challenge in Sphagnum farming, but data on fen paludiculture with aerenchymous plants is still missing.

Wind erosion is a problem for drained peatlands and will be avoided by re-wetting. As the application of fertilizers and pesticides on water saturated soils is forbidden, contamination will be reduced.

Decomposition of peat causes the release of nutrients (especially nitrogen), and this will be reduced by re-wetting. Furthermore, especially fen paludiculture crops thrive under nutrient-rich conditions, and this paludiculture can contribute to cleaning nutrient-rich surface water.

Water storage capacity might be enhanced, but catchment scale studies are lacking so far.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Wet peatland agriculture
 - 2 Sphagnum farming (specific to bogs)
 - 3 Sphagnum cultivation (specific to bogs)
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

51 - Variable rate irrigation

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A sprinkler irrigation technique that allows the water doses to be modulated at each nozzle or group of nozzles on the equipment. It aims to optimize water application by taking into account the variability of the environment and particularly soils or crop development. The technique can apply for water and what can be transported by water like fertilizers and when authorized some pest control products.

(Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

It is a sprinkler irrigation technique that allows the water doses to be modulated at each nozzle or group of nozzles on the equipment. It aims to optimize water application by taking into account the variability of the environment and particularly soils or crop development. The technique can apply for water and what can be transported by water like fertilizers and when authorized some pest control products.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

51 – Variable rate irrigation

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Wind speed or direction

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	
steep (30-60%)	
very steep (>60%)	

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment : There is no study on the use of VRI in organic soils/peatlands.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Soil infiltration capacity < irrigation flow

The most profitable situations concern large field with heterogeneous soils (mainly texture).

Soil or crop heterogeneities scale that can be considered is ranging from 0.1 to 0.5ha.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes

3.2.1 Natural grasslands

No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	No
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	No
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

I1 - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Adverse Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	No Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

The most profitable situations concern large field with heterogeneous soils. Soil heterogeneity must have large structures.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Variable rate irrigation management
 - 2 Site-specific irrigation management
 - 3 Site-specific variable rate sprinkler irrigation systems
 - 4
 - 5
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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

52 - Biofumigation

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Biofumigation is based on the incorporation of fresh plant mass into the soil, which will release several substances able to suppress soil-borne pests. Among these substances are found the MITC (methyl isothiocyanates) highly toxic to pests and pathogens. Plants from Cruciferae family release large amount of these toxic compounds in soil and are considered the best material for biofumigation. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The term 'biofumigation' was originally coined by J.A. Kirkegaard to describe the process of growing, macerating / incorporating certain Brassica or related species into the soil, leading to the release of isothiocyanate compounds (ITCs) through the hydrolysis of glucosinolate (GSL) compounds contained in the plant tissues (Kirkegaard et al., 1993). This can result in a suppressive effect on a range of soil borne pests and diseases. Since then, the term 'biofumigation' has been used rather loosely, to describe any beneficial effects derived from the use of green manures, organic amendments and composts. Here, biofumigation is considered in its strictest sense as referring to the use of glucosinolate-containing plant material with the intention of enabling ITC-mediated pest and disease suppression. Biofumigation could be considered as a 'natural' alternative to chemical fumigation to control a variety of soilborne diseases'' (Clarkson et al., undated). Biofumigation using naturally produced plant compounds to manage plant-parasitic nematodes. Fresh glucosinolate-rich (GSLs) Brassicaceae crops are

chopped and incorporated into the soil that releases highly toxic volatile organic compounds (VOCs). Cellular disruption and enzymatic hydrolysis of GSL release degradation products, specifically isothiocyanates (ITCs) capable of killing or antagonizing plant-parasitic nematodes. This practice also reduces infections by the cephalosporium fungus and weed competition, incorporates organic material in the soil that is advantageous for soil structure and for the availability of nutrients.

The mini-paper of Clarkson et al. (undated), the factsheet of Michel & da Cara García (undated) and the video of Michel (2020) provide ample information on the mechanisms and best practices related to biofumigation. All information described here originates from these 3 sources. Biofumigant crops can be used in different ways, including incorporation of biofumigants, intercropping and rotations with biofumigants, as well as incorporation of seed meals and other processed biofumigants (Clarkson et al., undated).

The biofumigation practice against corn-parasitic nematodes described here is being used by a farmer in MDN in PT (Quinta da Choldra). This exploitation has precision agriculture farming of maize irrigated with center-pivot. In this field, root-knot nematodes and the cephalosporium fungus were reducing the maize yield. To avoid the use of chemical pesticides, this farmer chose to use Raphanus, a biofumigation crop from the Brassicaceae family, associated with black oat and barley to cover the soil after maize was harvested (winter time Nov-Mar) and to incorporate in the soil before maize seeding (Mar). The innovation is related to the fact that is scarcely used in our country. In this precision agriculture farming exploitation it is applied to aim at reducing root-knot nematodes and prevent wounds in the roots of young corn and reducing infections by the cephalosporium fungus. It is an efficient technique but becomes very expensive and unnecessary in areas without the presence of phytopathogens. This farmer seeded the biofumigation crop mixture only in areas affected by the pests with a significant reduction in production to reduce costs and to recover more easily the investment made. This crop mixture has small seeds and a special seeding machine is needed, which represents an extra cost (in this case a machine was rented). What is worthy of mentioning is that this farmer made informative videos available online (links are provided below) with the costs of application of this practice: Raphanus and black oat seeds 11Kg/ha with 5€/Kg cost; the service of seeding costs 50€/ha; consumption and emissions of 15L of diesel equivalent to 45Kg CO₂. The time of incorporation of the biofumigation crop in the soil has to be carefully managed since it has to be incorporated green to take advantage of the biofumigation effect and at the Brassica flowering stage. This practice is used in PT in the rainy season, it might be needed to wait until it is possible for the machines to incorporate the green biomass into the soil using a shredder and then a harrowing followed by a roller. The crop should be shredded as finely as possible before soil incorporation for efficacy. The efficiency depends mainly on the following factors: the Brassica species used, which determines the type of isothiocyanates (ITCs) released; the cultivar used that will determine both the glucosinolate-rich (GSLs) concentration in tissues and the total biomass produced, and hence the potential amount of GLS buried in the soil;

and the timing of the destruction of the fumigant crop. To maximize biofumigation, it should be destroyed at the beginning of the flowering stage when biomass and GLS contents in plants reach their maximum values (Kirkegaard and Sarwar 1998; Sarwar and Kirkegaard 1998). One disadvantage is that after more than two decades of studies on biofumigation, the method is not widely used. Probably due to the reported efficacy still is lower than the chemical products. One of the greatest advantages is environmental since it reduces contamination by avoiding the use of nematicides and fungicides. It covers the soil in the rainy season that prevents soil compaction at the surface and helps in improving soil structure, and reduces weeds. There are no reports on negative impacts on beneficial microorganisms associated with this method and it is not host-specific (ITCs can inhibit a series of soil-borne diseases). Brassicas' can be used as green manure crops and they grow faster (appreciated by farmers).

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

52 – Biofumigation

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Biofumigation is applicable wherever the biofumigant crops can be grown or where processed biofumigant plants are available. Irrigation may be necessary in dry climates (Michel & da Cara García, undated).

Rainfall or irrigation is needed at the time of plant incorporation in the soil, to ensure effective hydrolysis of GSLs (Morra and Kirkegaard, 2002), as well as efficient breakdown of plant tissues. The biofumigant potential of a crop relies on: achieving as much biomass as possible and crop access to long day lengths and high ultraviolet (UV) radiation, which is important for the production of the precursors to the toxic volatiles released on soil incorporation.

Depending of the environmental zone, autumn-established biofumigants for overwintering have lower potential than summer biofumigant crops. Examples of crops: Indian mustard is a summer crop (needs high UV radiation) with growing period of 8--14 weeks; oil radish is a winter crop and incorporation occurs in spring.

2 week gap between incorporating a biofumigant and planting a new crop. This is to avoid phytotoxic effects in the new crop from biofumigant organic matter breakdown.

warm soils ($>10^{\circ}\text{C}$) -- for incorporation of biofumigant material, which helps toxic gases move through the soil. Low soil temperatures limit efficacy.

Climatic limitations will also be dependent on the plant pests or pathogens to be targeted. They have different thermal limits and optimal temperature requirements depending on their species.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping ($<2\%$)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep ($>60\%$)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

According to Michel & da Cara García (undated), lighter-textured soils with low organic matter content are better suited for bifumigatio because the sorption of reactive molecules to soil organic matter and clay minerals limits the efficacy. According to the same source sufficient soil moisture is necessary for the mechanism related to bio fumigation to work.

If soils < 50% of field capacity: summer crops may need irrigation prior to maceration and incorporation.

75% < Soil moisture < 100%: moist, but not sodden. The right soil moisture content is so critical that irrigation should be considered if the equipment is available rather than waste the crop by destroying it in the wrong conditions.

Soil temperature 10°C: to maximise volatile gas dispersion through the soil after incorporation.

The ideal timing for maceration and incorporation of summer biofumigants is when the crop is at early to mid-flowering when the foliage is still succulent.

Isothiocyanates are highly toxic volatile compounds and their effectiveness depends on many factors including pH, temperature and soil moisture. In volatile toxicity assays, isothiocyanates were more toxic at higher temperatures compared to lower temperatures (5–20 °C tested, in vitro and with soil (moisture content 75% of field capacity); sand (pH 7.2, 3.26% OM), loam (pH 4.9, 6.77% OM), and peat (pH 5.69, 31.55% OM) (Matthiessen et al., 2005)

Soil texture: lighter-textured soils with low OM content are better suited (Kirkegaard, 2009), since isothiocyanates get fixed to OM by sorption, and are therefore less active against soil-borne pathogens and nematodes. Lower OM content occurs less sorption of the isothiocyanates.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain

3.2.1 Natural grasslands

No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	No
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Uncertain
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Uncertain
Large-scale corporate farming	Uncertain

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Unknown Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Biofumigation is often applied in vegetable crops.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

The reviewed sources indicate that biofumigation may replace the application of other pest control agents and therefore may reduce soil contamination. The increased input of organic matter may lead to higher levels of soil organic matter, better soil structure, as well as higher soil water storage capacity. However, we did not review literature on these claims.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Biofumigation against plant-pathogens
 - 2
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

53 - Integrated pest management

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A pest control concept that uses the best available mix of technologies for a particular pest problem, it promotes practices available to farmers and permits pest control with the least use of chemicals to get high yields and maximum profits. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

In the 90s it was proposed to extend the concept of IPM to the wide definition of the integrated production/Integrated crop management.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

53 – Integrated pest management

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

According to my knowledge climatic factors do not limit the application of integrated pest management. It is applied mainly in developed countries but located in different climatic zones.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment : According to my knowledge IPM does not apply to management of organic soils/peatlands.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

According to my knowledge soil properties do not limit the application of integrated pest management. It is applied in different soil types.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Uncertain

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	No
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	No Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	No Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	No Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	No Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Integrated pest management (IPM) is mainly applied on permanent crops (fruit trees, berry plantations, olives) but also on annual arable crops. It can also be relevant for some types of agroforestry systems.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Theoretically, the IPM is aimed to avoid pesticide contamination and enhance soil biodiversity. However, the reality often looks quite different.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Integrated production
 - 2 Integrated crop management
 - 3 Integrated farming
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

54 - Mechanical weeding

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Removal of undesirable vegetation by mechanical means. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Use of mechanical levers to control weeds in crops, after crop planting (during the crop season, not in intercropping).

It consists in weed management between sowing and harvest, during cultivation (e.g. for straw cereal: from November to April, for spring crop like maize: from May to June or July).

Mechanical weeding has two goals: 1) destroying weeds to prevent them from significantly competing with crops (direct effects), and 2) stopping weeds from bolting to prevent future infestations in the field and to limit deposits in the weed seed banks (control seed propagation, indirect effects).

Mechanical weeding consists of shallow tillage with a variety of tools often categorized as hoes or harrows. It includes whole crop cultivation, inter-row cultivation and intra-row cultivation.

According to the tool used, mechanical weeding can destroyed weeds in several ways: tearing weeds into pieces, cut or dislodge roots (uproot weeds), dig up and rip up weeds, or bury young weeds by moving the soil.

Mechanical weeding induce also soil loosening, through the use of tools (also named cultivators).

Different factors determine when the moment is right for implementing mechanical weed control, including crop and weed growth stage, and climatic conditions before and after intervention. Soil properties need also to be taken into account, as well as weed type (mechanical weeding can be efficient for annual dicots and grasses, but not for perennials crops).

Previously referred as tertiary tillage, cultivating tillage is now suggested (Cloutier et al., 2007, Rueda-Ayala et al., 2010).

It can be designated using the name of the tools used (tine weeder = tine harrow, row crop cultivator (for hoeing operation) = hoe, rotary hoe = rotative weeder).

Possible confusion: use of a mechanical weeding tool at another time, between two crops (during summer, for example).

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

54 – Mechanical weeding

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

- For Arvalis, the French arable crops R&D institute, the notion of available day or field readiness is used. Field readiness is defined by the combination of soil workability (soil suitability for cultural operations) and soil trafficability (soil capacity to support machinery during traffic without soil physical degradation).
- The general climatic conditions are those allowing soil tillage: ``drying`` conditions resulting in a friable and dried out soil (slightly dry on the surface, conditioned by the temperature and the wind but with different threshold value depending on the soil type). The climatic conditions are also important after the operation, and there should be little to no rain in the days that follow the operation to prevent cut weeds from re-establishing themselves.
- For more precise rules:
- No rain on the day of the use/application of the practice.
- Climate after passage: 2 to 4 days without rain after the operation (the exact day number depends on ETP, and thus on temperature) to hope for practice efficiency: weeds that must be mechanically destroyed must be able to be dried to avoid transplanting (planting out).

There is a risk of weed transplanting if it rains after passage. Thus, this practice is easier to use in spring (in theory). Mechanical weeding is more used on spring crops (maize, sunflower, soybean, beet), using cultivator type tools that are more aggressive, more flexible than the tine harrow.

- On an ``average`` year: from 15th-20th of October to 20th of February/beginning of March: there is a very low probability of available days for mechanical weeding (for example for straw cereals, winter cereals). Mechanical weeding can be used anyway, especially in systems where other levers not available and even if not easy to implement (organic agriculture).

Mechanical weeding is more suited to spring crops (maize, beetroot, sunflower, spring barley, soybeans): longer favourable weather slots (more available days). - As any cultivation practices, mechanical weeding can induce wind soil erosion (Borrelli et al., 2017). Thus, it should not be done in windy conditions, especially for soils prone to wind erosion (which is estimated to be the case for a significant part of European soils).

- Additionally, mechanical weeding in late autumn or early spring may provoke frost damage to the crop after treatment mainly due to root injury and reduced drought resistance.
- In general, the efficacy of the mechanical weeding will depend on soils conditions, that impacts weed control efficacy and the degree selectivity regarding the crops. Every tool used for mechanical weeding needs to be adjusted. Its degree of aggressiveness is determined by the tine angle and vibration speed (affected by harrow speed) for the tine harrow, the hoeing depth and speed for the rotary hoe, and for the row cultivator by the rigidity of the shanks to which the sweeps are attached, the orientation of the sweep and the sweep type.
- Linked to the climate of the year, two other points are important to consider:
- The weed stage is important: good weed stage is up to 1 leaf for cotyledon weeds, and up to 2 leaves for dicotyledonous weeds. There is an exception when using a cultivator, which can allow passing on more developed weeds (up to 4 or even 6 leaves).
- The stage of culture is important: Mechanical weeding cannot be used on germinating crops. From 2-3 leaves the tine harrow can be used, up to 1 node for a straw cereal. Row crop cultivator can be used from 3 leaves and up to 1 - 2 nodes. For maize, the use of tine harrow is possible, but hoe is preferred. It can be used from 2-3 leaves and up to 7-8 leaves (the limit is the tractor passage, unless tractor is a little different as it used to be).
- There are two main categories of tools:
- Full field homogeneous work tools (tine harrow, rotary wheel, rotative weeder): recommendations are in relation with the crop and weed stages. These tools can be used for very young/poorly developed weeds. The objective is to be selective in relation with the crop, i.e. to be aggressive enough to destroy weeds but not to damage the crop. The intervention needs to be not too early so that the culture is sufficiently established but not the weed.
- Inter-row tools (cultivators): these tools are simpler to use, works better for more developed weeds.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Uncertain
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain

moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

All the tools used for mechanical weeding works most efficiently on soils that are well drained, level and packed. Certain tools are recommended or eliminated depending on the type of soil.

- Soil drainage level: the rotary hoe can be used on somewhat wet soils (it can be employed sooner than the tine harrow after rainfall), but the soil should be allowed to dry somewhat to ensure effective weed control (i.e. prevent cut weeds from re-establishing themselves). The row cultivator is effective for well drained soils (but not to dry).
- If the soil presents a frequent water saturation: mechanical weeding is not used.
- For the slaking/crusting silt soils: tine weeder (tine harrow) is eliminated, the rotary hoe is recommended for its aeration effect (destruction of slaking crust).
- Heavy soils: better to use rigid tine harrow.
- Shallow calcareous clay soil: the rotary hoe is eliminated and the tine harrow is recommended.
- Stoniness/gravel content: some tools behave better in stony ground. The tine harrow is to be preferred and behaves better than the rotary hoe (not effective on heavy stone/gravel contents or loose soil).
- Cloddy soils: they can be problematic for the use of the tine harrow. Crop seedlings risk being buried under soil clods.

Plant leftovers/fragments that remain at the soil surface is a significant constraint. Sufficient burial of plant leftovers/fragments is necessary for mechanical weeding to be possible, which means that mechanical weeding is more appropriate for systems based on conventional soil tillage (or sufficiently deep soil tillage). Plant leftovers/fragments obstructs the passage of the mechanical weeding tool. Tine weeder (tine harrow, weed harrow) does not support plant

leftovers/fragments. Rotary hoe and rotary weeder are more efficient (even if not easy in case of plant leftovers/fragments).

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

I1 - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	No Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Adverse Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Adverse Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

- Data from Arvalis field experiments and expertise (expert knowledge). Summary of Arvalis field data (distributed in France, mostly south Loire), including all types of tools (but mostly tine harrow used on straw cereals).
- Data about climatic factors, weed control efficacy, degree of selectivity and advices on the most suitable tool can be found in ITAB (2012) report.
- Arvalis developed an internal decision support system (J-DISPO, but the evolution towards another tool called J-DISTAS is in progress) calibrated with this data.
- Wind erosion
- Weed and crop stage, ITAB (2012).

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

- Arvalis field experiment results and technical expertise (expert knowledge) in France. The technical report ITAB (2012) summarize advice on the most suitable tools regarding the soil properties.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Regarding Land-use, related practice can be used for grassland maintenance but it is different (it's not weeding, but mechanical maintenance). Grassland harrows are used for maintenance (leveling and spreading of molehills to avoid soil in the fodder/mow meadows, spreading and homogenization of effluents in Pasture meadow). Maintenance of the meadow, not weeding.

Regarding agricultural systems:

Conservation agriculture:

- Yes: more difficult. Plant residues make difficult the use of mechanical weeding and reduces its efficiency. Certain tools can be used as they behave better (rotative weeder).
- Uncertain: depending on the practices implemented
- No: in case of no tillage + cover crop

Organic farming: it is the only mechanical weeding technique possible.

Regarding European Farming Systems: Mechanical weeding can be used in any type of farm (there are no technical limits), but it is not used everywhere: it's a question of equipment availability in relation to the working time required.

Limits/brakes:

- Labour and material availability problem. Due to the dependence on climatic conditions to ensure the success of mechanical weeding, it is often necessary to operate the entire surface of the farm during short time slots. The labour and materials are not always available to do this.
- Access to equipment. It depends on the strategy of work, investment, tool sharing.

Today, large-scale tools are developed to respond to major farm surface issues. The interest of farmers pushes for the development of equipment. Some cooperatives for the use of agricultural equipment have equipment to share, but constraints remain related to tool availability (most of farmers need to use the same tools at the same time because of the few available days).

- For very small extensive farms, tools may be too expensive.

- For larger surfaces, the working time is too long and the application can be difficult because of the reduced time window and rather uncertain.
- Decision to use the practice: mechanical weeding is more delicate than phytosanitary product based practices, especially because of the available days. Mechanical weeding have more specific time slots, which conditions for the day of the intervention and the days after.
- About weeding efficiencies, mechanical weeding is not superior to other techniques.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

For all categories: depends on the type of soil, the tools used. Nothing is systematic.

Maintain / increase SOC:

- No direct effect
- Possible indirect negative effects:
 - Mechanical weeding may enhance mineralization of organic matter. It's not very well quantified, but there are feedbacks from farmers and field experiments. This induction of the mineralization can favour crop growth.
 - Fuel consumption can be increased (depending on the target, there may be several passages. For organic farming, there can be up to 4-5 passages. For mixed weeding systems, there are 1 to 2 passages).

Avoid soil erosion: depends on the tools, the type of soil, the climatic conditions after the mechanical weeding

- Possible positive effect (but less important than negative effects), due to the destruction of the slaking crust for silty soils. Rotary hoe and row crop cultivator can break the slaking crust.
- Possible negative effects:
 - Due to tool passage that induce soil erosion, especially on hilly areas (side effect of soil tillage in general). Mechanical weeding can cause soil erosion because it includes soil surface tillage and needs to have no plant leftovers to be efficient. Row crop cultivator can promote erosion because of the deeper soil tillage it induces. It leaves erodible soil, which can be a problem if it rains after mechanical weeding.
 - Wind erosion can be induced by/after mechanical weeding in dry conditions (but like any soil tillage).

Avoid contamination:

- Possible positive effect: mechanical weeding causes less contamination than chemical weed control does, because it limits herbicides use.

Optimal soil structure:

- Possible positive effect: especially at the soil surface, because of the destruction of the slaking crust for loamy soils. It is mostly valid for spring crops.
- Possible negative effect: if practice used under bad conditions. If the soil is too wet there are risk of compaction due to machinery passages (especially if multiple passages), or if the soil is dry on the surface but still wet at depth (risk of deep compaction). Machines used for mechanical weeding are not very heavy but not very wide either. It induces closer tractor passages I the field (which thus induces higher compaction).

Improve soil biodiversity: depends on the tool used.

- Possible positive effect: if it induce soil aeration, it promotes aerobic microorganisms activity.
- Possible negative effect:
- disturbance for surface organisms. For example, it can be negative on ground beetles and partridges.

Improve soil nutrient retention / utilization

- Possible positive effect if mineralization is favoured, and nutrient use efficiency is improved as the competition for nutrients between weeds and crop is reduced. Moreover, there are some evidences that mechanical weeding could prevent from nutrient leaching compared to Herbicide weed control (Formaglio et al., 2020).

Improve water storage capacity

- Possible positive effects:
- If the slaking crust is destroyed, better infiltration from soil surface to deeper soil layers is favoured. And water use efficiency is improved as the competition for nutrients between weeds and crop is reduced.
- Mechanical weeding can breaks ip the soil capillaries, preventing from water evaporation under warm and dry growing season.
- Possible negative effect:

- Mechanical weeding dries up the first soil centimetres.
- If mechanical weeding is done under bad conditions and induces soil compaction, this can have adverse effects on water infiltration.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

- 1 Mechanical weed control
 - 2 Tertiary tillage (Previously)
 - 3 Cultivating tillage
 - 4 Tine weeder
 - 5 Tine harrow, Row crop cultivator, Hoe, Rotary hoe, Rotative weeder
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

55 - Nematode protection

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

One way to control the undesired nematodes is to treat their larvae with microorganisms that are harmful to the nematode larvae. (Source of definition: <https://agro.au.dk/en/current-news/news/show/artikel/nematode-protection-mechanisms-to-be-elucidated/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The name of the practice is not clear, since it misleads to crop protection using nematodes as protectors against plant diseases and not the use of microorganisms to control undesired nematodes. The description presented has an inaccuracy since it refers to nematode larvae (a designation no longer used) instead of referring to nematode juveniles (the immature stages from J1-J4 before the adult forms).

A more adequate name for this practice is ‘‘microbial biocontrol of plant-parasitic nematodes’’.

The following description is suggested: ‘‘One way to control the undesired nematodes is to use some microorganisms as biological control agents that can parasite or prey plant-parasitic nematodes, can compete or antagonize them in result from the toxicity of secondary metabolites produced by these microorganisms.’’ Several studies have described the use of biological control agents against plant parasitic nematodes, with promising results. This is the case of fungal species, such as *Paecilomyces lilacinus* (syn. *Purpureocillium lilacinum*), *Pochonia chlamydospora* (Manzanilla-Lopez et al., 2013) *Trichoderma harzianum*, *T. viride* (Amarasinghe &

Hemachandra, 2020), and other *Trichoderma* spp. (Huong et al., 2009); the bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* (Narasimhamurthy et al., 2017), *B. cereus*, *B. firmus* I-1582 (Ghahremani et al., 2020) and the rhizobacterium *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (Seenivasan et al., 2012). These bioagents coupled with other control measures are a potential strategy to be included in integrated pest management programmes.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

55 – Nematode protection

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Several microorganisms can be used as biocontrol agents and their ability to proliferate or multiply in the rhizosphere is intimately associated with the soil. There are complex interactions between biocontrol microorganisms, the nematofauna and the host plant and it becomes difficult to generalise climatic limitations. The soil microflora competes with the introduced biocontrol agents for scarce energy sources that can significantly affect the performance of the biocontrol. Soil moisture rarely limits the growth of most fungi but affects the dispersal of spores. Bacteria are more vulnerable to moisture levels than fungi but are unlikely to be damaged by levels that enable plant-parasitic nematodes to survive. The tolerance to desiccation depends on the microorganisms. In the same way, they have different thermal limits and optimal temperature requirements depending on their species. Thus, the soil moisture content and the temperature command the performance and persistence of biocontrol agents.

Soil temperatures: 10--15 °C (temperate regions for much of the growing season); 20--25 °C (warm climates) at 10-cm depth. Such ranges have direct effects on the biocontrol agents' growth and sporulation and on the plant-parasitic nematodes rate of development (Kerry 2000). In a general way, we can refer that an intense summer drought with a lack of precipitation might compromise the use of this practice in a non-irrigated farming system.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment : It is a practice putatively suited for peatlands/organic soils although little information is available. Peats are a natural habitat for nematodes and it is normal to find nematodes in them. Most nematodes are bacterial and fungal feeders but harmless root feeders can also be found, all of them determinants for the soil food web. For a good interpretation and to set up the appropriate biological control measures it is necessary to identify nematodes to

species level. High water tables and low soil temperatures are commonly held to be the primary reasons for low peat decay rates. The slow diffusion of oxygen through water (approximately 10^4 times slower than in air) (Crank, 1976) means that decomposition in the majority of northern peat profiles proceeds at slow, anaerobic rates, in the absence of oxygen, and depth to the water table is seen as a strong predictor of peat decay rates (Strack et al., 2004). Similarly, multiple studies have observed strong increases in anaerobic decomposition rates with increases in soil temperature (Hogg et al., 1992; Silvola et al., 1996; Scanlon and Moore, 2000). In peat soils, the control of the water table, soil moisture, oxygen levels, and soil temperature are important factors to consider when choosing microorganisms as biocontrol agents.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Due to the variety of microorganisms that can be used as biocontrol agents and the variety of farming systems in which this practice can be used, limitations are context-specific. The soil texture and structure must be suitable for the added microorganisms. Kerry (2000) reported that the great bulk of soil (2500 t/ha) to plow depth (20 cm) brings difficulties for the thorough biocontrol agents' incorporation and renders uneconomic broadcast treatments. Soil moisture rarely limits the growth of most fungi but may affect hyphal growth and spore dispersal. Bacteria are more vulnerable to moisture levels than fungi but are unlikely to be damaged by levels that enable plant-parasitic nematodes to survive. The tolerance to desiccation depends on each microorganism. Also these microbes have different thermal limits and optimum temperature requirements depending on the species. Additionally, a shallow groundwater level or frequent water logging can be a limitation for some microorganisms. If the biocontrol agents are applied by spraying the soil surface, very fine soil textures can difficult their motility when not in presence of irrigation or precipitation.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Uncertain

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	No Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

There are economic factors influencing the grower's perception on how to manage the plant-parasitic nematode pests, such as the high cost of the biocontrol agents relative to other management options, the price of the commodity per hectare, and the value of the crop in the agricultural market. In high market value crops (e.g. niche market crops) the cost of the microbial nematicide can be affordable. The low-value crops such as major row crops (e.g. maize, cotton, chickpea, and lentil) and some perennials (e.g., pigeon pea) are often unreachable for the microbial nematicide marketing because the crop value is low. Considering these economic constraints, we classified as uncertain the potential application of this practice in the farming systems extensive small-scale, extensive farming in less favoured areas, larger-scale crop farming and large-scale corporate farming.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Biological control of plant-parasitic nematodes
 - 2 Microbial pesticides against phytoparasitic nematodes
 - 3 Microbial nematicides
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

56 - Precision of herbicide application

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A smart spraying system in agriculture is a targeted spraying system with efficient application of chemical and low cost for the environment. A smart sprayer generally includes a targeted detection system and spraying system, in which the targeted sensor is the foundation of the precision spraying management. (Source of definition: Song and Sun, 2015, doi 10.1080/10798587.2015.1015781)

Specificities or other description of the practice

There are different sub-categories of smart spraying. All the aliases filled in in section 4 C2 above represent in fact a different way of practicing smart spraying.

Boom section cut-off is used to avoid double overlaps and also spillovers out from a plot during the passing of a tractor-sprayer : while spraying in full, parts of the boom section that are in overlap with spots already sprayed or are outside a plot, stop spraying. Sprayer nozzle cut-off is the exact same thing expect that it is at a finer precision level, it can be used typically to follow the curved contours of a plot in order to spraying only inside the plot.

Assisted or automatic driven tractor sprayer is when the tractor-sprayer is equipped with a GPS-RTK antenna (accurate to within 2 cm). There is an on-board console linked to this antenna, in which the farmer/technician can create/encode a guide line : i.e he makes a passage with the tractor-sprayer from a point A to a point B (it can be a straight or curved line) and the

console records the distance traveled, the spatial positioning into the field, and every piloting event happening on the tractor-sprayer. Once a guide line is encoded the tractor-sprayer can roll by itself (and spray in full as he rolls), piloted by the console which follows the guide line it have previously recorded. In the case of a square field, the advantage is that once one straight guide line is encoded we can use it as many times as needed to cover the entire field surface, we just need to move to the side the tractor-sprayer by the distance of its width when it arrives at the end of a line, and proceed the entire spraying from line to line.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

56 – Precision of herbicide application
i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

These limiting factors are more related to spraying in general than to smart spraying.

A certain amount of humidity is necessary: ideally, spraying should be done early in the morning or late in the evening. The ideal humidity for spraying pesticides is 80%, above 95% the product will runoff like if it was after rain and below 60% fine drops risk to vanish before the product is absorbed by the leaves.

Wind: you cannot spray at more than 15 or 20km/h (there are legal guidelines for the exact speed). If you spray fine drops at such wind speed, they fly away and you have drift. Which means you are spraying next to the target, including sometimes at the neighbor's house or in the water, etc. This sometimes leads to having areas where you have been with the sprayer and there has been no product and so you have patches of weeds (in the case of weed control) that may still be present. So you're spraying, but you don't have the quality of the spray behind you. In consequence, we have to see that the wind affects the size of the drops we can use : when there is no wind, we can afford to use very fine drops that will cover the foliage properly, when there is more wind, we work with larger drops.

Rain: we do not spray when it rains or just before, because it will clean the treatment. And after a rain, we have to wait until the soil is dry again because the sprayer will start destroying the soil by making a channel through wheel tracks .

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

The following factors are more related to the machine than to the practice.

The soil has to be not too much wet : following the amount of water it contains we have to wait or not until the water has infiltrated to start spraying. If we spray on a wet soil the treatment will runoff.

You need a floor that stands up, with some structure. Able to support the load of the machine.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	No
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain

Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	No

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	No Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	No Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	No Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	No Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

We can have changes in treatment efficiency depending on the composition of the soil. Because there are complexes that will form with the clay, the humus also. But it doesn't really affect the practice of smart spraying, but rather the product used and the quantity of it applied.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

It is incompatible with submerged crops, there would be unmanageable water contamination problems. But when it comes to types of irrigation like water cannon and drip, there is no accounting problem.

In fact, what you have to consider is that the more water there is in the crop, the more you will tend to favor percolation and you have to avoid that with smart spraying. Because we must avoid the infiltration of pesticides in the water table by giving them time to degrade as much as possible on the first centimeters of the soil.

For orchards people prefer in general to use backpack sprayer instead of buying a 300K euros sprayer. But it is doable though.

It is the economic situation of each farm that comes into play. You have to have an economy of scale with this kind of machine (sprayer). But simply, it can be found on small farms through agricultural contractors.

There are products registered to be sprayed in organic agriculture (see here : <https://fytoweb.be/fr/guides/phytoprotection/liste-de-produits-phytopharmaceutiques-autorises-en-belgique-en-agriculture>) but the use of a sprayer is not certain though not contraindicated a priori.

In agroforestry it will depend on the spacing. We also have to remember that a sprayer boom cannot hit too many obstacles. Another thing is that if we have too high trees that can obstruct the GPS signal. Indeed the GPS signal works very fine in an open field but close to a building or an object, as it is just a wave length as another it will ricochet and ultimately lose its precision. Otherwise it may be doable with small sprayers.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Variable rate application of pesticides (VRA)
 - 2 Assisted, or automatic, sprayer operation
 - 3
 - 4 High frequency spraying
 - 5 Sprayer
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

57 - Soil solarization

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Solarization is a soil disinfection method consisting of covering a moistened soil with a thin transparent plastic film, for 4-6 weeks during the part of the year with the highest sun radiation and temperatures. (<https://www.best4soil.eu/factsheets>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

A non-chemical method for improving soil thermal-physical properties and controlling pests and pathogens. Depending on specific countries seasonality and farming period, this method can be used as a pre-plant and as a post-plant treatment. It is compatible with chemical soil treatments and also biological soil amendments after solarization.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

57 – Soil solarization

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Continuous solar irradiation. Maximal ambient temperature for a period of 4-6 weeks. Minimal wind.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	No
sloping (5-10%)	No
strongly sloping (10-15%)	No
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Soil moisture - >70% of field capacity

Soil irrigation - >50 cm deep

Slope gradient - non to minimal

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	No
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	No

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	No
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

I1 - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	No Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	Adverse Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Adverse Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

The key of this method is solar radiation that affects soil temperature. For the most effective result, soil temperature has to reach 40-50 degrees celsius for a period of at least 4-6 weeks. As this is achievable only by continuous solar radiation this method needs to be adapted to the specific region and season. Shady areas may not be effectively treated by solarization therefore in cloudy or cold regions soil solarization can be applied mostly in greenhouses.

The best effect can be achieved in leeward areas as the wind can disperse the trapped heat and may loosen or damage the plastic sheets.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

Wet soil conducts heat better than dry soil and makes soil organisms more vulnerable to heat. The soil under the plastic sheets must be saturated to at least 70 percent of field capacity in the upper layers and moist to depths of 50-60 cm for soil solarization to be effective. It is recommended that soil is subjected to furrow or drip irrigation at a watering rate of not less than 30 mm/m² for a period of two days prior to the solarisation technology application. If the soil is very light and sandy, or if the soil moisture is less than 50 percent of field capacity, it may be necessary to irrigate a second time - during the solarization process.

Although the only limiting factors are soil moisture and slope gradient, for better results it is recommended to use this method for soils with higher organic matter content in topsoil as they are more favourable to absorb more solar radiation and reach higher temperatures achieving better results. For lighter coloured soils, the addition of charcoal or organic material such as manure may give the limited effect of raising soil temperature.

Before applying this method, all plant residue needs to be removed from the soil surface as minimal disturbance of the soil is recommended after solarization for a minimal chance of soil recontamination.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Solarization is not practical for rice production but can be used on rice nursery soils for the production of healthy seedlings. Conventional tillage can show positive influences by enhancing soil thermal efficiency compared with conservation tillage.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Continuous application of soil solarization may cause some negative impacts on the soil. For example, beneficial soil microbial communities can be affected in the long term because of the modification of soil temperature and moisture. Depending on the material used for covering the soil, it may lead to greenhouse gas emissions, decreasing organic matter contents due to the shifting of the edaphic biocoenosis. In some cases, continuous soil mulching can cause soil water repellence and the risk of high salinity could appear.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Solar heating
 - 2 Plastic mulching
 - 3 Soil trapping
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

58 - Buffer strips

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Conservation buffers are small areas or strips of land in permanent vegetation, designed to intercept pollutants and manage other environmental concerns. (Source of definition: https://www.nrcs.usda.gov/wps/portal/nrcs/detail/national/home/?cid=nrcs143_023568)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Buffer strips with permanent vegetation cover locate generally between agricultural fields and a receiving water bodies or main ditches having several benefits. At first, the buffer strips prevent the application of fertilizers, manure, and pesticides too close to an adjacent water body, brook, or main ditch since these operations as well as soil tillage are not allowed in buffers. They also control erosion on the slope and retain sediment, nutrients, and other pollutants from surface runoff. In addition, they enhance the biodiversity and especially can increase the number of pollinators.

Particularly, grass buffer strips effectively reduced the leaching of particulate phosphorus and nitrogen.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

58 – Buffer strips

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

In Mediterranean climates, the summers are so warm or hot and dry that the vegetation of buffer strips may dry out and not work properly when autumn rains begin. Therefore, the area of Mediterranean South was excluded from the systematic map made by Haddaway et al. in 2018.

In Boreal climates, above-ground vegetation dies during winter frosts. If the grass cover of the buffer strips is poor, they will not work properly during snow melt and spring runoffs. During last decades, several events of snow melt and rainfall during winter season have also added the challenges. In addition, phosphorus liberation from the decaying grass to spring runoff causes problems. (Uusi-Kämppe & Jauhiainen 2010).

A Field experiment to investigate nutrient leaching was established in 2011 on a clay loam. The field site is located about 15 km south of Uppsala in eastern Sweden (59°43'0'' N; 17°41'21'' E). The experimental field is about 0.42 ha (72 × 50 m), with a slope in the north-south direction of about 1%. At the lower part of the field, grassed buffer strips were established as follows: A) Control, which is managed in the same way as the main field; B) Grass buffer strips; C) As B, but the grass harvested once a year. Each treatment was 6 m by 6 m, and is replicated in four blocks. Each plot is drained with a central 6-m long drain pipe at 1 m depth. The rest of the field is not drained. Surface runoff and drainage water are led to an automated measuring and sampling station. The samples were analyzed for phosphorus, nitrogen and organic carbon. On average, the leaching of particulate phosphorus via drainage tiles was reduced by 17 % in the grass buffer strips but the effect of harvesting the grass on reducing leaching was very little. Nitrate leaching was reduced by 28 %. Surface runoff was scarce during the experimental years and its data was insufficient to draw conclusions.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Uncertain

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : Buffer strips prevent erosion and retain soil particles and nutrients in all soil types. In peatlands as well as in (potential) acid sulfate soils, the wide buffer strips allow the raise of ground water level preventing the oxidation of deep soil layers and decomposition of peat as well as decreasing leaching of acidity and metals from acid sulfate soils.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

This method works if there is enough soil and water for plant growing. The grass should be harvested annually to remove nutrients from the strip. In stony places, for example grazing may be a good option for harvesting. In parcels with a sub-drainage, deep-rooted plants like willow in the buffer strip may clog drainage vents and drainage pipes causing the problems of water logging in the field. Some seed weeds like thistle may spread from buffer strips to cultivated area. Mowing the buffer strips during the growing season would help, but it is not always possible in the narrow strips without messing up the crop.

The suitable width of buffer strip depends on the erodibility of the protected field and slope. The longer, steeper or more erodibility the slope, the wider strip is needed. It is important to establish and maintain a right kind of buffer strip in the right place. In flat areas, a headland of 1-m-wide is enough along the main ditches and a buffer strip of 3-m-wide along brooks, whereas more than 10-m-wide buffer strips are needed around watercourses surrounded by fields with steep and long slopes with high erodibility. Buffer strips are well suited to sites where groundwater level needs to be raised, such as peat soils and (potential) acid sulfate soils.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

Under high nutrient loading from the source area, buffer strips can become saturated and act as a source of pollutants, thus limiting their long-term effectiveness. In saturated buffer strips nitrification can increase greenhouse gas emissions and can result in nutrient swapping. During spring runoff in boreal areas, snow melting waters or spring rainfalls in buffer strips may leach soluble phosphorus from phosphorus saturated soil surfaces or above-ground plant cover into spring runoff (Uusi-Kämppä and Jauhiainen 2010). In spring, several events of freezing and thawing liberate soluble phosphorus from the grass residue into water (Uusi-Kämppä et al. 2011). Biomass removal e.g. via mowing can prevent nutrient saturation, increasing the longevity of buffer strips. In some studies wooded buffers have been less effective than grass buffers at intercepting sediments and sediment bound pollutants. It should be noted that wooded buffers must not be so dense that they overshadow surface vegetation and thus increase erosion. Instead, zoned buffers that combine strips of riparian woodland and grass are effective, but they can sometimes take large areas out of agricultural production. Trees may, however, be effective in retaining soluble nutrients and especially young fast-growing tree individuals are good at absorbing nutrients.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Buffer strips have been in general use for a few decades in several European countries. At first, the practice was voluntary and farmers were skeptical of the loss of cultivated arable land without monetary compensation. Nowadays, 2 to 5 meter wide buffer strips belong to the requirements of the cross-compliance of CAP aid. Also Ecological priority areas required by CAP can be sometimes regarded as such buffer strips. In CAP, environmental support is paid if wider buffer strip areas are established. The vegetation of these wide buffer strips has to harvest annually e.g. by mowing and removing the grass residue or grazing. Mowing may cause problems if a suitable machine is missing or if there is no place where the grass could be utilized. Also, access to the grass strip with the tractor and mowing machine during the growing season can be problematic so that the crop plant is not trampled.

Buffer strips can be different kind of:

- A buffer strip is normally located in the lower end of the field nearby a ditch, river, brook or lake. Sometimes, the strip may surround all the whole framing parcel.
- Contour buffer strips alternated down the slope with cultivated areas which are farmed on the contour. They are similar to contour strip cropping, but grass strips are usually narrower.
- So called grassed waterways are established on concentrated water flows in fields to decrease water flow and thus decrease the erosion process on a channel.
- Riparian buffer strips often contain the natural area of stream bank as well as the grass, bush and tree strips along the channel.

Models, such as RUSLE, may be used to predict the erosion risk areas where wide buffer strips would be effective for trapping sediment and nutrients.

For instance, in Norway, 8-m-wide buffer strips are established in areas with flooding or erosion. The grass must be harvested to receive production subsidies, but it might sometimes turn into unfit animal feed due to sedimentation.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Increase of SOC

Avoid Soil sealing: Driving on tractors and other implements should be avoided in buffer strips. Occasionally, machines are driven or turned in buffer strips, which can cause tractor wheel depressions on wet ground. After that water flow along them and not infiltrate into the ground as it should.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Riparian buffer zones
 - 2 Vegetated strips
 - 3 Buffer zones
 - 4 Field margins
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

59 - Hedgerow

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

A closely planted line of shrubs or small trees, often forming a boundary or fence. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Hedgerows are important managed linear field boundaries and have potential to influence ecosystem function in agricultural systems. Hedges are composed of perennial shrubs or shrubs and trees and are important for the provision of regulatory ecosystem services, including water quality, flood risk reduction, soil erosion prevention, shelter provision for livestock and climate change mitigation (via carbon storage). Hedgerows have benefits for carbon sequestration, soil conservation, habitat improvement, biodiversity, shading, landscape diversity and societal services. They provide a habitat for wildlife e.g. birds, native pollinators and parasitoids. They act as a wind-break in the landscape, reducing the risk of wind erosion. Hedgerows protect soil from degradation and are thought to provide a reservoir of soil biodiversity for the adjacent farmed fields.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

59 – Hedgerow

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

There are no climatic restrictions as hedgerow species must be chosen according to the climatic conditions of the region. However, climate may influence rate of establishment and ability of hedgerows to thrive.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment : Hedgerows are not natural vegetation for peatlands. On the contrary, shrubs on peatlands are an indicator for altered hydrology that should be avoided. They can cause drying, shading and can displace natural plants.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Corresponding to climate there are no restrictions to adopt hedges. Thus, they can be adapted to suit farm type, in terms of composition, hedge species and soil type. Particularly, hedgerow species must be chosen according to the soil properties.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes

2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	Adverse Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

Limiting factors also included parts of the AFBI answers, as they highlighted good points. The rates of establishment must be considered a secondary limitation mainly due to socio-economic constraints and not directly relevant for climate.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

There are no limiting soil factors to establish hedgerows. It is possible to have hedges also on very steep slopes. The problem can be referred to the establishment and management on slopes higher than 60%. However, this is a socio-economic constraint and not a soil limiting factor.

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Hedgerows are a type of agroforestry. They are compatible with both cropland and livestock. Moreover, hedges are an important part of the agricultural landscape and their value is recognised within many agri-environmental schemes. Thus, in some agri-environmental zones such as in UK removal of hedges from farmland does not respect the cross-compliance.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

The following additional references were added for better understanding of the beneficial effect on 'Maintain/increase SOC':

1- Axe MS, Grange ID, Conway JS (2017) Carbon storage in hedge biomass---a case study of actively managed hedges in England. *Agric Ecosyst Environ* 250:81--88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2017.08.008>

2- Drexler S, Gensior A, Don A (2021) Carbon sequestration in hedgerow biomass and soil in the temperate climate zone. *Reg Environ Change* 21, 74. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-021-01798-8>

For the Effect on 'Avoiding N₂O, CH₄ emissions from soils', no effects on CH₄ could be observed in a study on hedgerows in Canada, for N₂O there were significant differences but only during the growing period. Thus, the following reference was suggested:

1- Thiel, B., M. Krzic, S. Gergel, C. Terpsma, A. Black, R. Jassal & S. M. Smukler (2016) Soil CO₂, CH₄ and N₂O emissions from production fields with planted and remnant hedgerows in the Fraser River Delta of British Columbia. *Agroforestry Systems*, 91, 1139-1156.

For the beneficial effect on 'Avoid soil erosion' the following reference was listed:

1- Van Vooren, L., Reubens B, Broekx S, De Frenne P, Nelissen V, Pardon P, Verheyen K (2017) Ecosystem service delivery of agri-environment measures: A synthesis for hedgerows and grass strips on arable land. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 244, 32-51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2017.04.015>

For the adverse effect on 'Avoid salinisation', the evidence base for the quantification of the effect is quite small. However, studies have found adverse effects of hedgerows on soil salinisation due to altered hydrology. In detail, the following reference was provided:

1- Grimaldi C, Thomas Z, Fossey M, Fauvel Y, Merot P (2009) High chloride concentrations in the soil and groundwater under an oak hedge in the West of France: an indicator of evapotranspiration and water movement. *Hydrological Processes* 23, 1865-1873. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.7316>

For the beneficial Effect on 'Avoid contamination', the following reference was suggested:

1- Thomas, Z. & B. W. Abbott (2018) Hedgerows reduce nitrate flux at hillslope and catchment scales via root uptake and secondary effects. *Journal of Contaminant Hydrology*, 215, 51-61.

For the beneficial Effect on 'Optimal soil structure', beneficial Effects have been found directly beneath the hedgerow (please see Thiel, B., S. M. Smukler, M. Krzic, S. Gergel & C. Terpsma (2015) Using hedgerow biodiversity to enhance the carbon storage of farmland in the Fraser River delta of British Columbia. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 70, 247-256.); this does not automatically include positive impacts on the adjacent field.

For the beneficial Effect on 'Enhance soil biodiversity', the following references were suggested:

1- Gulvik ME (2007) MITES (ACARI) AS INDICATORS OF SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND LAND USE MONITORING: A REVIEW. *POLISH JOURNAL OF ECOLOGY* 55:415-440.

2- Rivest et al. 2020 (Rivest, M., Whalen, J.K. & Rivest, D. 2020: Variation of soil microbial and earthworm communities along an agricultural transect with tree windbreak. *Agroforest Syst* 94, 1639--1649. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10457-019-00476-3>) found that this can not be concluded in general among taxa but different soil organisms do react differently.

For the beneficial Effect on 'Enhance soil nutrient retention', hedgerows have positive effects more in the sense of avoided contamination (nutrient interception), but can also be beneficial for the adjacent fields, especially if they are prone to erosion. Thus, the following reference was suggested:

1- Van Vooren, L., Reubens B, Broekx S, De Frenne P, Nelissen V, Pardon P, Verheyen K (2017) Ecosystem service delivery of agri-environment measures: A synthesis for hedgerows and grass strips on arable land. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 244, 32-51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2017.04.015>

Regarding the Unknown Effect on 'Enhance water storage capacity', additional references were suggested. Water availability for neighbouring crops could be affected negatively, as hedgerows do increase canopy interception and dry out the soil due to increased evapotranspiration:

1- Herbst M, Roberts JM, Paul PTW, Gowing DJ (2006) Measuring and modelling the rainfall interception loss by hedgerows in southern England. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 141, 20244-256. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agrformet.2006.10.012>.

2- Ghazavi G, Thomas Z, Hamon Y, Marie JC, Corson M, Merot P (2008) Hedgerow impacts on soil-water transfer due to rainfall interception and root-water uptake. *Hydrological Processes* 22, 4723 -- 4735. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.7081>).

However, the impact on the water balance varies depending on precipitation conditions, slope, hedgerow structure, etc., and extends into the field to different extents. Moreover, this can be counteracted by shading effects of the hedgerow and increased water infiltration underneath the hedgerow, which have a positive effects on water availability:

1- Holden, J., R. P. Grayson, D. Berdeni, S. Bird, P. J. Chapman, J. L. Edmondson, L. G. Firbank, T. Helgason, M. E. Hodson, S. F. P. Hunt, D. T. Jones, M. G. Lappage, E. Marshall-Harries, M. Nelson, M. Prendergast-Miller, H. Shaw, R. N. Wade & J. R. Leake (2019) The role of hedgerows in soil functioning within agricultural landscapes. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 273, 1-12 showed that hedgerows can be beneficial for reducing flood risks.

Hedges are not sealing the soil and therefore there is no effect. This has also been mentioned by AFBI for UK. In detail, it was found that they increased water infiltration underneath the hedgerow, which have a positive effects on water availability.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Hedges
 - 2 Bocage
 - 3 Knick
 - 4 Shelterbelt
 - 5 Windbreak
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

60 - Retention ponds

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Retention ponds can provide both stormwater attenuation and treatment. They are designed to support emergent and submerged aquatic vegetation along their shoreline. Runoff from each rain event is detained and treated in the pool. The retention time promotes pollutant removal through sedimentation and the opportunity for biological uptake mechanisms to reduce nutrient concentrations. (Source of definition: https://www.susdrain.org/delivering-suds/using-suds/suds-components/retention_and_detention/retention_ponds.html)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Retention ponds are often constructed wetlands where natural purification processes occur. They can be established by expanding or by damming up a stream. The construction often consist of a sedimentation pond where the particles and particle bound nutrients can sediment, followed by a wetland filter that aims to slow down the water velocity so that the more fine fractured sediments are removed and nutrients are taken up by the vegetation. The different parts of the retention pond are normally divided by lower thresholds or permanent dams. Prior to the outlet the water is led into a dam for further sedimentation, which is an important feature to make the retention pond more efficient during flood events. A retention pond should represent 0,1-1% of the catchment area and be located as near the pollution source as possible. In addition to improving water quality, retention ponds can contribute to flood mitigation and increased biodiversity.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

60 – Retention ponds

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Climatic factors are increasing the need for this practice as larger precipitation events has increased the flood and erosion risk. The ponds do, however, need to be cleared out of sediments in order to be efficient and have a sufficient volume. The interval of this operation varies, but is likely to decrease with increased precipitation rates.

During large magnitude events there might be a risk of resuspension of deposited sediments.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	No
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Very high ground water level could limit the application of the pond as it would limit the capacity of the pond and retention properties.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	No
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Yes

2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

I1 - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	No Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	No Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	No Effect

Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

The measure can be costly for the establishment and maintenance phases. Nevertheless, it can be more affordable because it can potentially be subsidised by policy measures. The highest cost-effect are obtained for farms with severe erosion issues.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Maintenance of SOC in terms of decreasing soil loss by erosion. Potential effect on N₂O emissions and soil compaction due to reduced water logging of fields. Enhanced water storage capacity if the measure is efficient as the soil is potentially less saturated.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Sedimentation ponds
 - 2 Constructed wetlands
 - 3
 - 4
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

61 - Semi-natural habitat creation

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Permanent woody or herbaceous areas in agricultural landscapes such as permanent grasslands, grassy field margins or ditch banks, tree or shrub hedgerows, woodlands.

(Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/faoterm/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Semi-natural habitat by surrounding landscape may be modified and increase biodiversity composition. Protect biodiversity and to maintain human welfare. Furthermore, the definition can be implemented as: Small woody and herbaceous areas in agricultural landscape are generally associated with a high species richness of flora and fauna, including presence of rare and threatened species. They also have a high cultural and historical value. Particularly, in Slovakia, Introducing of grassy field margins into agricultural landscape have been implemented through the Regulation of the Government of the Slovak Republic No. 75/2015 Coll. laying down the rules for provision of support in relation to measures of the Rural Development Programme. The composition of the mixtures for moist and dry environmental conditions is specified in the Regulation No. 75/2015. The payments and support are focused mainly for arable land in lowlands. The aim of the Rural Development Plan was to set up 12 thousand ha of multifunctional field margins. Nevertheless, only 1% of the planned grassy margins were established during 2014 - 2018. In Slovakia, the national inventory of woody and herbaceous vegetation in agrarian landscape was performed in 2011-2012. Woody and herbaceous vegetation

was considered as a one of the elements of the Traditional Agricultural Landscape (TAL). Based on this study, these elements of the traditional agricultural landscape were divided into 5 groups:

1. TAL with occurrence of woodland -- not more than 10% of the site covered by woods,
2. TAL with spatial woodland formation,
3. TAL with solitaire trees dominant
4. TAL with lines of trees or shrubs dominant,
5. TAL with small woodland dominant.

The most common dominant woodland structure was lines of trees and shrubs, with significant occurrence in TAL of arable-land and grassland and TAL with dispersed settlement. The proportion of woodland was relatively low, as TAL with low occurrence of woodland (36 %) was the most extended subtype of TAL. In 2014, TAL covered app 44 thousand ha, out of which only 10 thousand ha were supported by agri-environmental payments, largely under measures for implementation of organic farming and preservation of biodiversity.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

61 – Semi-natural habitat creation and enhancement
i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

This practice is very flexible, elements can be selected or self-seeding plants for different soil structure and meteorological conditions in the area of the practice application. The negative effects of higher temperatures and amount of precipitation depends on the proportion of semi-natural habitats within a site. Semi-natural habitats are generally not limited by climate.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

All soil types are suitable for this practice. It is important to choose the right element of the practice (plant species, etc.). However, lack species associated with very acid or base-rich soil. Also, potassium and magnesium deficiency resulting from repeated hay cutting and removal appeared to restrict the diversity of species on some semi-natural sites.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain

2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Uncertain
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

I1 - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N2O, CH4 emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Soil acidification is an environmental problem that is driven by various factors and was documented on grasslands. Results of the 57-years study showed, that soil has been significantly acidified under non-fertilized and fertilized treatments as well.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 grassland habitats
 - 2 historical structures
 - 3 ecological elements, pollinators habitat
 - 4 flower-rich margins
 - 5 field strips, semi-natural green area
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

62 - Conservation Agriculture

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Conservation Agriculture is a agricultural system that promotes minimum soil disturbance (i.e. no tillage), maintenance of a permanent soil cover, and diversification of plant species. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/conservation-agriculture/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Conservation Agriculture (CA) is based on a combination of the following practices: no tillage/ minimum tillage, cover crops, crop diversification and permanent soil cover. Thus the three core principle, which must be fulfilled conjointly are:

- 1- No tillage or minimum soil mechanical disturbance.
- 2- Permanent soil cover i.e., maintain crop residues or stubble in arable crops or preserve groundcovers between rows of trees in permanent crops. This is useful to increase soil organic matter and water infiltration into the soil, inhibit weeds, and reduce water evaporation the soil surface. In this context, at least 30% of the soil must be covered after seeding to effectively protect soil against erosion. However, it is recommendable to leave more than 60% of the soil covered to have almost complete control over soil degradation processes.
- 3- Diversification of cropping systems by using rotations, crop sequences, and crop associations, involving annual and perennial crops.

In Northern Europe such as Sweden, A challenge with cover crops (CC) in Sweden is the short growing season that is shorter the further north you go. The growing season is limited by temperature and daylight. To ensure a good establishment of a CC they must generally be sown before the 15th of August. In the south of Sweden this is doable, but further north it is not, because the main crops have not been harvested by that time. Some farmers solve this by sowing the CC at the same time as they sow the main crop. Some sow the CC when they do the last weed-harrowing after emergence of the main crop (organic farms). Some have self-built machinery to sow the cover crop in the established stand of the main crop. Some accept this limit and only plan for CC after main crops that are harvested early.

Another challenge for CC is the regulations for receiving subsidies. They are limiting, and farmers find them a nuisance. The main points of criticism are: the dates for when a CC has to be sown and terminated are limiting, you cannot sow any species you want as a CC nor that you can sow a cocktail of species, you have to apply for subsidies that span over 5 years and must pay back the money received if a CC establishment fails, or the alternative subsidy which is only for one year but still has to be applied for in the spring and it is impossible to know what the weather will be like in August when it is time to sow the cover crops. So, the farmer must be conservative and not apply for the whole potential area and therefore miss opportunities if the weather at the end of the summer does permit establishment of CC.

There are a few organically certified farmers that are interested in CA and strive to achieve this without the use of herbicides. They are often inspired by cropping systems from Germany and Austria. The challenge with CA in organic production is to achieve no-till without increasing the perennial weeds over time, and to terminate the CC. In conventional systems this is done by herbicide applications. One solution is to do a shallow (5 cm deep) pass with a rotary tiller. The sward of the CC is cut off and in dry weather the cut off parts will dry down and the C is successfully terminated.

Some farmers combine this with a treatment of a lactic acid bacteria solution (fermented molasses and water). The low pH (3,5) in the solution combined with the activity of the lactic acid bacteria further breaks down the CC residue. After 7-14 days the CC is dead, and the main crop can be sown. The system with terminating cover crops by using a roller crimper (e.g used at Rodale institute in the U.S) is generally considered to not work under Swedish conditions since the main crops (small grain cereal) must be planted before the cover crop is mature enough to be roller-crimped. However, it might work for vegetable production in Sweden. CA is not widespread in Sweden. But there is a growing interest in soil health and alternative farming methods in Sweden as well as globally. Many farmers practicing CA seek a lot of knowledge themselves from youtube and facebook. Many also travel to international conferences mainly in the U.K or USA. These farmers are often frustrated with the knowledge they find from institutions in Sweden (universities, the crop consultants). They feel that these

institutions are not up to date with current knowledge and that they cannot receive advice that is adequate within CA.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

62 – Conservation Agriculture

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Generally, climatic factors are not considered limited factors in most of the Countries such as Slovenia. Therefore, conservation agriculture can be used under various climates. However, agro-melioration measures must be generally taken for soil water table control in gley soils.

Conversely, in Northern Countries such as Sweden, a challenge with cover crops (CC) is the short growing season that is shorter the further north you go. The growing season is limited by temperature and daylight. To ensure a good establishment of a CC they must generally be sown before the 15th of August. In the south of Sweden this is doable, but further north it is not, because the main crops have not been harvested by that time. Some farmers solve this by sowing the CC at the same time as they sow the main crop. Some sow the CC when they do the last weed-harrowing after emergence of the main crop (organic farms). Some have self-built machinery to sow the cover crop in the established stand of the main crop. Some accept this limit and only plan for CC after main crops that are harvested early.

In Mediterranean Countries such as Italy, precipitation and drought can be the most important climatic factors that can limit the application of conservation agriculture. However, if the right practice is chosen no limitations are detected. It is important to select the right practice to manage weeds especially when precipitation is higher than 700 mm per year or consider the length of summer drought if spontaneous vegetation cover is performed. For instance, in Po Plain (one of the most important areas in Mediterranean North where conservation agriculture is applied) no climate limitations are detected for the application of conservation agriculture. Important results are obtained in the LIFE HelpSOIL project (<http://www.lifehelpsoil.eu/en>).

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Uncertain
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : In Slovenia (P21 - ULBF), it has been recognized that conservation agriculture is much better than conventional plough, although it is more aggressive than no-tillage.

In Italy (P14 - CREA), it has been highlighted that the adoption of conservation agriculture allow to achieve improved crop performance by favoring the management of all the interrelated aspects of soils.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Generally, stone content of soils might be a limiting factor. For instance, in Slovenia, it has been observed that stones are not an obstacle for the adoption of conservation agriculture. Moreover, superficial (up to 10 cm deep) soil loosening can sometimes not be enough to amend the soil compaction caused by heavy machinery. Occasional sub-soiling is advised in such cases. Interestingly, the compaction is more prone to develop in sandy-loam than in loamy-clay soil.

Similarly, in Italy it has been highlighted that in the Mediterranean North and South agro-environmental zones, the stone content of the soil (ranging from 15% to 30%) is not a specific limitation for conservation agriculture, but stones are a general limitation for arable land management. Moreover, an effective drainage is required for the success of conservation agriculture practices to avoid water stagnation in heavy soils.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Uncertain
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Uncertain
Large-scale corporate farming	Uncertain

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

In Slovenia, it was found that humid and warm climate of Alpine-south promotes fast development of thermophile weeds which ‘‘explode’’ with growth in July. Moreover, the Composting Tillage is less effective in weeds suppression than moldboard plough, therefore weed control should be more intense. In Italy, it was observed that in Southern Italy (under Mediterranean North and South conditions) table grapes managed as organic or conservation agriculture did not show significant differences in grapevine water status compared to other treatments. Moreover, vines under these practices performed the highest net photosynthesis rate from shoot growth to veraison. The introduction of cover crops in rotation did not affect cluster weight, berry weight, and juice composition.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

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bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

63 - Organic Agriculture

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Organic agriculture is a holistic production management system which promotes and enhances agro-ecosystem health, including biodiversity, biological cycles, and soil biological activity. It emphasizes the use of management practices in preference to the use of off-farm inputs, taking into account that regional conditions require locally adapted systems. This is accomplished by using, where possible, agronomic, biological, and mechanical methods, as opposed to using synthetic materials, to fulfil any specific function within the system. (Source of definition: <http://www.fao.org/organicag/oa-faq/oa-faq1/en/>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Description provided by the coordinators was clear and no other specificities are needed.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

63 – Organic Farming

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

This practice is applied all over world in very different climatic zones. Thus, climatic factors do not limit the application of organic farming. For instance, in Alpine South and in Mediterranean South environmental zones, some limitations can occur. Particularly, in Alpine South, the most important climatic factors that influence the adoption of organic farming are represented by: length of growing period (number of days) defined by number of days with daily average temperature $> 5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ 180; thermal-time sum (degree-days) for Growing Period defined by accumulated daily average temperature $> 5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ 1500 degree-days. In the Mediterranean South, the main climatic limitation is represented by dryness: Ratio of the annual precipitation (P) to the annual potential evapotranspiration (PET) $P/PET = 0.5$. Thus, pre-evaluation of drought status in those environmental zones is recommended before adopting organic farming.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Yes -- comment : Additional information and references were added to better clarify if organic farming is suitable for the sustainable management of organic soils or peatlands in the agro-environmental zones. Reviews and meta-analyses generally support the perception that organic farming systems are more environmentally friendly than conventional farming systems. For example, such aggregate studies have found that organic farming systems consistently have greater soil carbon levels, better soil quality and less soil erosion compared with conventional systems. John P. Reganold and Jonathan M. Wachter . Organic agriculture in the twenty-first century. Nature Plants 2015. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/nplants.2015.221>

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Soil properties do not limit the application of organic farming. It is applied in different soil types. However, at least in the UE, organic farming tends to be more common on less fertile, weaker (sandy) soils, such as those of Mediterranean basin or Anatolia region.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Yes
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Uncertain

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Beneficial Effect
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

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Comments or references linked to climatic factors

The main reference for the limiting climate and soil factors are defined in the REGULATION (EU) No 1305/2013 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on support for rural development identified the limiting climate and soil factors for agricultural activities, not specifically for organic farming. Following this regulation, Italy has defined the methodological approach for Designation of areas facing natural and other specific constraints, based on pedoclimatic and biophysycal criterion

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

For Anatolia region, other references can be considered to better understand the positive effect of organic management on soil organic matter increase over the years (please see the References section).

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Ecological farming
 - 2 Biological farming
 - 3 Organic agriculture
 - 4 Ecological agriculture
 - 5
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

64 - Agroforestry

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Agroforestry is the practice of deliberately integrating woody vegetation (trees or shrubs) with crop and/or animal systems to benefit from the resulting ecological and economic interactions. (Source of definition: agforward.eu)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Agroforestry -- ``farming with trees'' - has been defined in various ways by different authors and depending on the (local) context and the purpose of the definition (e.g. to describe the agronomic or biophysical status of the system or to delineate the system in terms of rules and regulation).

Agroforestry is a human made ecosystem that combines forestry with agriculture and/or livestock by incorporating various ecosystem elements into time and space. Agroforestry usually has social benefits as well, next to economic and environmental benefits. It can be defined as ``the practice of deliberately integrating woody vegetation (trees or shrubs) with crop and/or livestock production systems to benefit from the resulting ecological and economic interactions'', according to H2020 AGFORWARD project. This definition is similar to those adopted by the World Agroforestry Centre (ICRAF), the European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF), and the Association for Temperate Agroforestry (AFTA). For the first time, Lundgren and Raintree in 1982 explained that in agroforestry systems there are both ecological and economic

interactions and defined those systems as ``a collective name for a land-use systems and technologies where woody perennials are deliberately used on the same land-management unit as agricultural crops and/or animals, in some form of spatial and temporal arrangement''.

In 1992, Sommariba defines agroforestry as a form of multiple cropping which satisfies at least three basic conditions:

1. There are at least two species that interact biologically
2. At least one of the species is a woody perennial
3. At least one of the plant species is managed for forage, annual or perennial crop production.

Other definition are reported as follows:

ICRAF definition: ``A dynamic, ecologically based, natural resource management system that, through the integration of trees in farm- and rangeland, diversifies and sustains smallholder production for increased social, economic and environmental benefits'' (Leakey 1996)

USDA definition: ``The intentional growing of trees and shrubs in combination with crops or forage. [...] agroforestry is distinguished from traditional forestry by having the additional aspect of a closely associated agricultural or forage crop.'' (USDA 2011)

EU legislation definition: ``Land use systems in which trees are grown in combination with agriculture on the same land. The minimum and maximum number of trees per hectare shall be determined by the Member States taking account of local pedo-climatic and environmental conditions, forestry species and the need to ensure sustainable agricultural use of the land.'' (Article 23 of Regulation 1305/2013)

In general, we could conclude that agroforestry refers to any integrated land use management system where trees and/or shrubs are deliberately combined with an agricultural crop or livestock on the same land. In a well-functioning agroforestry system, both components have a neutral or positive influence on each other, and negative interactions are avoided as much as possible through careful design. Agroforestry can also provide ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration, shade for livestock, erosion control or air purification.

Several types of agroforestry can be distinguished, resulting in different farm functions, products and ecosystem services, such as silvopastoral systems, silvoarable systems, homegardens, riparian buffer strips or forest farming. From inventories performed (e.g. Mosquera-Losada et al. 2016) it can be seen that silvopasture, followed by homegardens are the most extensively used agroforestry practices in Europe.

Italy has 1.4 million ha under agroforestry, covering about 11% of the total utilised agricultural area. At European level, Italy represents the fourth largest area for livestock agroforestry systems and the second largest area for silvoarable and agroforestry with high value trees. Due to the several agro-environmental zones (from Alpine South to Mediterranean South), Italy has a wide range of agroforestry systems, which are often rich in biodiversity. These wide range of agroforestry systems can favor diversified landscapes, valuable for recreation and tourism. The agroforestry systems in Italy and associated innovations are considered in terms of silvopastoral system, olive trees and arable production systems. As innovative strategy, agroforestry certification is also considered. Silvopastoral systems refer to the integration of trees in livestock farms or to the use of livestock in woody crops such as forests (e.g. forest grazing) or orchards (e.g. olive groves). Currently, about 10.1% of the Italian utilised agricultural area is managed by silvopastoral systems that integrate trees with livestock production, mainly in marginal areas. The most important benefits of these systems include mitigation of GHG emissions, livestock adaptability to climate change, and the increase of nutritional quality of livestock products. Other positive examples of biodiversity increase can be given such as beneficial insects and opportunities for larger animals. In order to prevent overgrazing to favor forest regeneration, the grazing pressure can be reduced by using rotational, mixed or precision grazing. In the Alpine South, wood pasture is typically semiextensive and grazed by cattle. The structure includes both low-density tree populations and mosaics of small woods among pastures and shrubland. The larch wood pasture is a traditional system with high landscape and ecological values, which integrates cattle, sheep, pasture, and timber production. Moreover, in this zone, there is a growing interest in goat grazing in forests, due to the increase in dairy goat products. In the Apennines (Med Mountainns), the main agro-silvopastoral systems are based on extensive and semi-extensive management for small herds of sheep and beef cattle, grazing continuously or moved to forest clearings and wood pastures from the end of spring to the beginning of autumn depending on the altitude and environmental conditions. The sheep grazing in firebreaks lines has received growing interest because it aims at preventing shrub ingression.

In recent decades, the olive agroforestry (i.e. olive trees intercropped with other crops and/or grazed) has been increasingly recommended and adopted, both

to prevent soil erosion and soil degradation and to increase biodiversity. Agroforestry on arable lands can improve land productivity, reduce pollution and address climate change by sequestering more carbon than conventional arable systems. Agroforestry certification requires the establishment of sustainable management criteria and guidelines. Well-managed agroforestry systems can also provide opportunities to minimize land abandonment. Regarding the farmers perception of agroforestry systems, they agree that the effects of agroforestry on production and the environment were generally positive, whilst those related to management were generally negative. Farmers perceived positively the business opportunities from adopting agroforestry because multifunctional systems and diversification increase agricultural resilience.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

64 – Agroforestry

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

No climatic factors limit the application of agroforestry in the different agro-environmental zones across Europe.

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

As for climatic conditions, soil properties will certainly determine to a great extent the options for tree (and crop) species or variety choice. Particularly water related parameters such as ground water level, frequent water logging, WHC, ... will determine which species will be excluded or not. Fruit trees for example, generally are not suited for locations with a frequently high water level, while on the other hand, species such as willow, alder or poplar do not perform well on dry soil conditions.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes

2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	
Avoid contamination	Beneficial Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Beneficial Effect

Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Beneficial Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

Given the huge variety of agroforestry systems and hence the ability to adapt design, species choice and management to the local pedoclimatic conditions, there are no major climatic factors limiting the potential application of this practice. Nevertheless, indeed these climatic features will determine to a great extent what the options are in terms of (tree and crop) species choice, system design and their performance.

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

Agroforestry can have a beneficial effect, no effect and an adverse effect on soil acidification. Often the abovementioned potential (beneficial) effects depend to a great extent on the tree species selected (e.g. certain trees will have a beneficial effect on avoiding acidification, while others will have an adverse effect) as well as on design or management (e.g. the impact on erosion reduction depends strongly upon the orientation of the tree lines relative to the slope and on the management of the strip below the trees).

The permanent agroforestry systems maintain a continuous cover that reduces evapotranspiration and salts accumulation in topsoils. Generally they increase soil quality and fertility, by also reducing soil GHG emissions as well as degradation of peatlands.

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

-
- 1 Agro-selviculture
 - 2 Silvo-pastoral system
 - 3 Agro-silvo-pastoral system
 - 4 Silvo-arable system
 - 5 Mixed and inter crops (herbaceous and woody crops)
-

NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

65 - Terrace Farming

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Dry-stone or earth-banked terraces built in cropland or permanent crops (Source of definition: WOCAT)

Specificities or other description of the practice

Terrace can be used with slopes on average higher than 45°, where any other type of terrace could not be implemented and are dedicated exclusively to tree crops, especially chestnut or olive trees. Also, in the terracing the steps adapt from time to time to the natural emergencies of the slope, so that along the same level curve the size of the line can vary, remaining however on a larger size than the average values of the terraces, also allowing destinations for arable land or grassland crops.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

65 – Terrace Farming

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

Not specific climatic condition limit the application of the practice

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	No
gently sloping (2-5%)	No
sloping (5-10%)	
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Yes
steep (30-60%)	Yes
very steep (>60%)	Yes

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment :

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

Not specific soil properties limit the application of the practice

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Uncertain
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Yes
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Yes
2.2.3 olive groves	Yes
2.3 Pastures	Yes
2.4 Heterogeneous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	Yes
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Yes

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Uncertain
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	No
Large-scale corporate farming	No

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Yes
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Unknown Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Unknown Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Unknown Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Unknown Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

/

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

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OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

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bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

66 - Soil compaction risk modelling

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

Use of computer models to predicts the risk of soil compaction by farm machinery. The model estimates the risk of compaction for realistic operating conditions. (Source of definition: <http://www.terranimoworld>)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The management practice ‘‘compaction risk modelling’’ aims at preventing (harmful) soil compaction. The basic principle of this approach is to estimate soil stress induced by agricultural machinery (based on machinery characteristics including wheel load, tyre dimensions, tyre inflation pressure, etc.) and estimate soil strength (typically for a given soil texture and soil moisture), and compare stress with strength. If $\text{stress} > \text{strength}$, then there is a risk of soil compaction.

There are a range of models that would allow a farmer/land user to evaluate the compaction risk before driving into a field, and depending on this, decide not to do the field operation (if that is an option) or to use different machinery. Such compaction risk models can also be useful for long-term planning, e.g. when purchasing new machinery or new tyres, and also in identifying compaction risks in crop rotations (combination of heavy machinery and moist/wet soil conditions) that could then result in a change of crop rotation.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

66 – Models for soil compaction risk assessment

i-SOMPE – Adoption of soil management practices

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

no

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Uncertain
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Uncertain
moderately steep (15-30%)	No
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

Unknown -- comment : In principle yes, but we have little knowledge about compaction of organic soils, and only little data on mechanical properties of organic soils are available.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

No in principle, but the models are generally not adapted to high stone contents or shallow soils.

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	Yes
2.1.3 rice fields	Uncertain
2.2.1 vineyards	Uncertain
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	Uncertain
2.2.3 olive groves	Uncertain
2.3 Pastures	Uncertain
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	Uncertain

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Yes
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Yes
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Yes
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	Uncertain
Terrace Farming	Uncertain

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	Beneficial Effect
Avoid acidification	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Beneficial Effect
Avoid soil sealing	Beneficial Effect
Avoid salinisation	Unknown Effect
Avoid contamination	Unknown Effect
Optimal soil structure	Beneficial Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	Beneficial Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Beneficial Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	Unknown Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

Compaction can potentially be prevented in any systems and any conditions

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMES OR ALIASES

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NULL

bibliography: references.bib

Inventory of soil management practices across Europe

67 - Humus Balance Calculator

GENERAL DESCRIPTION

The soil organic matter (SOM) content of a soil is of central importance for soil fertility and is strongly dependent on soil management. Humus balance calculators allow farmers to estimate whether the SOM content of a particular field is likely to increase, remain stable or decrease. (Source of definition: Own)

Specificities or other description of the practice

The soil organic matter (SOM) content of a soil is of central importance for soil fertility and is strongly dependent on soil management. Humus balance calculators allow farmers to estimate whether the SOM content of a particular field is likely to increase, remain stable or decrease.

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

CURRENT APPLICATION (~ MID 2021)

67 – Humus Balance Calculator

-- No geo data for this item --

-> the level of adoption was not assessed for this practice

POTENTIAL AREA OF APPLICATION OF A PRACTICE

Climatic factors that limit the application of the practice

None known

Slope gradient classes

flat to very gently sloping (<2%)	Yes
gently sloping (2-5%)	Yes
sloping (5-10%)	Yes
strongly sloping (10-15%)	Yes
moderately steep (15-30%)	Uncertain
steep (30-60%)	No
very steep (>60%)	No

Management of organic soils/peatlands

No -- comment : The current humus balance calculator of Agroscope is not suitable to assess organic soils.

Other soil properties that may limit the application of the practice

None known

Land-use

2.1.1 Non-irrigated arable land	Yes
2.1.2 permanently irrigated land	No
2.1.3 rice fields	No
2.2.1 vineyards	No
2.2.2 fruit trees and berry plantations	No
2.2.3 olive groves	No
2.3 Pastures	No
2.4 Heterogenous agricultural areas (including 2.4.1 Annual crops associated with permanent crops, 2.4.4 Agro-forestry areas)	No
3.2.1 Natural grasslands	No

European Farming Systems

Extensive small-scale, semi-subsistence farming	Uncertain
Extensive farming in less favoured areas	Uncertain
Medium intensives, mixed farming systems	Yes
Intensive, larger-scale crop farming	Yes
Large-scale corporate farming	Yes

Main agricultural systems

Organic Farming	Yes
Conservation Agriculture	Uncertain
Agro-Forestry (Agrisilvicultural)	No
Agro-Forestry (Silvopastoral)	No
Agro-Forestry (Agrosilvopastoral)	No
Terrace Farming	Yes

IMPACTS OF THE PRACTICE

***I1* - Does the practice contribute in a significant way to address one or multiple soil challenges ?**

Maintain/increase SOC	Beneficial Effect
Avoiding N ₂ O, CH ₄ emissions from soils	No Effect
Avoid acidification	No Effect
Avoid soil erosion	Unknown Effect
Avoid soil sealing	No Effect
Avoid salinisation	No Effect
Avoid contamination	No Effect
Optimal soil structure	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil biodiversity	Unknown Effect
Enhance soil nutrient retention/use efficiency	No Effect
Enhance water storage capacity	Unknown Effect
Avoid Peat degradation	No Effect

REFERENCES AND USEFUL LINKS

General

/

Comments or references linked to climatic factors

/

Comments or references for limiting soil factors

/

Comments linked to the potential area of application of the practice

The current version of Agroscope's humus balance calculator is parametrized according and applicable to typical Swiss arable farming systems.

Comments or references linked to soil challenges

/

PICTURES AND VIDEOS

Link to picture files with full resolution

- [empty] ...

OTHER DOCUMENTS

Other information

LOCALLY USED NAMES, SYNONYMS OR ALIASES

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bibliography: references.bib